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INSTITUTO SUPERIOR TÉCNICO

**Agent-based Simulation of Electricity Markets: Wind Power Integration and
Retail Competition**

Hugo Miguel Loureiro Algarvio

Supervisor: Fernando Jorge Ferreira Lopes, Ph.D.

Co-Supervisor: João José Esteves Santana, Ph.D.

**Thesis approved in public session to obtain the PhD Degree in
Sustainable Energy Systems**

Jury final classification: Pass with Distinction

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Abstract

The challenges posed by the global warming across the globe led to the definition of key objectives for the integration of renewable energy in all sectors of activity. The European Union (EU) set ambitious targets for the use of renewable energy, as the main source of energy, in the transport sector, in buildings and in the production of electricity. These targets led to increasing shares of variable renewable energy (VRE) in the electricity markets (EMs) across Europe. One of the main issues is that VREs have a variable production so they increase the uncertainty of the net load. Retailers face the same problem when forecasting the consumption of their clients. As the current European markets have been designed for dispatchable power plants, VRE producers and retailers have several deviations that need to be settled in the balancing markets, increasing the prices of these markets and the penalties to pay. Accordingly, in 2009, the EU presented the “Third Energy Package” that has the goal of increasing competition and harmonizing market prices across Europe, by contributing to the liberalization of retail markets and the harmonization of the rules of wholesale markets. So, the work performed in this thesis has the goal of finding solutions to mitigate the problems associated with the deviations of VRE producers and retailers, mainly by improving the operation of these agents and testing changes to the current market designs.

Currently, the EU has been developing legislation to create a pan-European wholesale market of electricity, and also to support the integration of VRE, and the active participation of the demand-side in markets. The new EU legislation consists in significant changes in some elements of the market design and the implementation of equal rules in all EU markets. Some of these elements of market design and operation have been studied in this work, in particular: a gate closure close to real-time operation, aggregated bids, a market time unit up to 15 minutes, active participation of VRE producers in all temporal horizons (from bilateral contracts to balancing markets), active participation of consumers, especially in balancing markets, and new market products to integrate VREs. The results obtained allow to conclude that these elements of market design can contribute to the integration of VREs, increasing their market value and consequently the social welfare of consumers. However, some modifications of market design elements may contribute to a faster retirements of slow power plants, that do not have the flexibility that such changes require. Furthermore, the development of new market products adapted to VRE producers and the demand-side is very important to support the active participation of these agents in EMs, to increase the efficiency of power systems, and to reduce pollution and price while producing electricity.

The competition in retail markets has also been studied in this work, with the development of a risk-return optimization model for portfolios of end-use consumers that may lead to more efficient portfolios to retailers and lower tariffs to consumers. The experimental results allow to conclude that risk-averse retailers with more ambitious profit-seeking strategies can get higher outcomes from these markets.

Keywords: Electricity Markets, New EU Legislation, New Market Designs and Products, Portfolios of End-use Consumers, Retail Competition, Variable Renewable Energy.

Resumo

As alterações climáticas devido à industrialização da sociedade trouxeram novos desafios e levaram à definição de novos objetivos para a introdução de energias renováveis em todos os setores de atividade. A União Europeia (UE) colocou objetivos ambiciosos em relação à utilização de renováveis como fonte primordial de energia, no setor dos transportes, nos edifícios e na produção de eletricidade. Estes objetivos têm levado ao aumento da penetração das energias renováveis variáveis (VREs) nos mercados Europeus. Um dos grandes problemas é a produção variável destas tecnologias, contribuindo para a incerteza do balanço energético. Os retalhistas também partilham este problema devido à incerteza no consumo dos seus clientes. Deste modo, em 2009, a UE publicou a primeira proposta de regulação do Mercado Interno de Eletricidade no âmbito do “Terceiro Pacote de Energia”, cujo principal objetivo consiste em harmonizar as regras e os preços dos mercados grossistas e fomentar a liberalização dos mercados retalhistas, procurando contribuir para um aumento da energia transacionada entre os diversos mercados Europeus. Assim, o trabalho desenvolvido nesta tese tem como principal objetivo obter soluções que possibilitem mitigar o problema da incerteza das VREs e da procura, procurando otimizar a operação dos agentes tendo em conta os modelos dos mercados de eletricidade atuais, e testando alterações a esses modelos que contribuam para uma operação mais eficiente. Atualmente, a UE tem criado diversa legislação que visa: a quase total liberalização do setor da eletricidade, a criação de um mercado grossista Europeu e a integração das VREs nos mercados.

A nova legislação da UE consiste em alterações significativas a alguns elementos do desenho do mercado, bem como na implementação de regras iguais a nível Europeu. Alguns destes elementos do desenho de mercado foram estudados neste trabalho, em especial: o fecho dos mercados mais perto da operação, permitir ofertas agregadas nos mercados, reduzir a unidade de tempo do mercado de 1 hora para pelo menos 15 minutos, permitir a participação ativa dos produtores de VRE em todos os horizontes temporais (desde os contratos bilaterais aos mercados de balanço), incentivar a participação ativa dos consumidores, em especial nos mercados de balanço, e permitir aos operadores de mercado que criem novos produtos que visem a integração das VREs. Estes elementos contribuem para a integração das VREs, aumentando o seu valor de mercado e consequentemente o bem-estar social dos consumidores. Assim, estas mudanças podem contribuir para o encerramento das centrais mais poluentes e lentas. Concluindo, os novos produtos de mercado adaptados às VREs e à procura podem ser muito importantes para suportar a sua participação ativa nos mercados de eletricidade, aumentando a eficiência do sistema e reduzindo a poluição e o preço de produção da energia elétrica.

Também foi estudada a competição no mercado de retalho, com a otimização risco-retorno de carteiras de consumidores, tornando-os mais eficientes para os retalhistas e obtendo-se tarifas mais baixas para os consumidores. Os retalhistas avessos ao risco que procuram lucros elevados têm vantagem neste mercado.

Palavras-chave: Carteiras de Consumidores, Competição no Mercado de Retalho, Energias Renováveis Variáveis, Mercados de Eletricidade, Nova Legislação da UE, Novos Desenhos e Produtos de Mercado.

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Nomenclature

BM	balancing market
CG	conventional generation
CPP	critical-peak pricing
CVaR	conditional VaR
CfDs	contracts for differences
DAM	day-ahead market
DLC	direct load control
DM	derivatives market
DR	demand response
DSM	demand-side management
EBG	Electricity Balance Guideline
EC	European Commission
EIME	European Internal Market for Electricity
EM	electricity market
ENTSO-E	European Network of Transmission System Operators for Electricity
EU	European Union
FCR	frequency controlled reserve
FCT	Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia
GDP	gross domestic product
GenCos	generation companies
IBP	incentive-based program
IDM	intraday market
IF	impact factor
ISO	independent system operator
Ind	industrial
K-NN	k-nearest neighbor
LCom	large commercial
LMP	locational marginal pricing
MAS	multi-agent system
MATREM	for Multi-Agent Trading in Electricity Market

MIBEL	Iberian Electricity Market
MTS	multivariate time series
NRMSE	normalized root mean square error
OTC	over-the counter
PBP	price-based program
RES	renewable energy sources
RTP	real-time pricing
Res	residential
SCom	small commercial
SJR	Scimago Journal & Country Rank
SL	street lighting
SMP	system marginal pricing
SOA	state of the art
TOU	time-of-use
TSO	transmission system operator
UTS	univariate time series
VPP	virtual power player
VRE	variable renewable energy
VaR	value-at-risk
WA	wind aggregator
WPP	wind power producer
aFRR	automatic-activated frequency restoration reserve
mFRR	manually-activated frequency restoration reserve

Greek letters

α	confidence level
$\chi_i, \beta_i, \delta_i$	regression variables
Δt	contract duration
ϵ_t	error
λ	risk attitude
$[\gamma]$	difference between costs matrix
μ	expected return average
σ	standard deviation

Roman letters

$[Cov]$	covariance matrix
$[r]$	r matrix
$[w]$	consumer weight matrix
C_h	retailer's cost

c_j	consumer agent
E_{t-1}	electricity consumption
I	investment
K_h	period discriminator
P_t	electricity price
$q_{0,h}$	quantity acquired in the DAM
$q_{c_{c_t},h}$	quantity in contracts
$q_{dev,h}$	imbalanced quantity
$q_{j,h}$	consumer consumption
$q_{s,h}$	bid to each IDM session
r	expected return
r^*	cut-off return
R_f	risk free
R_h	hourly return
R_p	risk premium
$RES\%_{t-1}$	renewable percentage
Ret	retailer agent
T_h	minimum tariff
$T_{j,h}$	tariff

Subscripts

\hat{D}	selected past day
c_t	contract number
D	target day
h	period of the tariff
i	period number
j	consumer number
s	IDM session
t	current period
L, M, K	lags

Chapter 1

Introduction

This chapter introduces the motivation of this work (section 1.1), its main objectives (section 1.2) and the key contributions (section 1.3). Finally, section 1.4 presents the structure of the thesis.

Traditionally, the organization of the electricity sector was based on vertically integrated electric power companies, which produced, transported and distributed energy without any competition. Liberalization began in the earlier nineties and had basically separated the functions of electricity generation and retail from the natural monopoly functions of transmission and distribution. This process has led to the implementation of a wholesale market, where producers provide the energy to retailers, and a retail market, where retailers guarantee its delivery to end-use consumers. Furthermore, market forces determine now the price of energy and reduce the net cost through increased competition [1, 2]. Also, customers can choose their suppliers based on the best offers.

The participants in electricity markets (EMs) are heterogeneous and autonomous, and follow their own goals and negotiation strategies. Usually, production companies seek to adopt strategies that maximize profit, while consumers adopt strategies that minimize the electricity cost. Most strategies help the negotiating parties to reach mutually beneficial agreements.

Three major markets models are often distinguished [3, 4]: pools, bilateral contracts and hybrids models. A pool is defined as a centralized marketplace that clears the market for sellers and buyers. Sellers and buyers of electricity submit bids for the amounts of power that they are willing to trade. The bids are handled by a market operator, whose function is to coordinate and manage the different transactions between the participants. Bilateral contracts are tradable arrangements of power between two traders. These contracts have the advantage of price predictability in comparison to uncertain pool prices. The hybrid model combines several characteristics of the previous two models. In this model, a pool is not mandatory, and customers can either negotiate power supply agreements directly with suppliers or accept power at the pool market price.

In wholesale markets, day-ahead markets (DAMs) are the largest and most liquid physical markets. The main European markets are Nordpool [5], EPEX [6] and MIBEL [7]. These markets close at 12:00 PM (CET), 12-36 hours before physical delivery in central Europe, or 13-37h in Great Britain, Ireland and Portugal [8, 9]. The trading occurs through an implicit auction where price and quantity are computed for

every hour of the next day, using EUPHEMIA, a hybrid algorithm currently used in the European Price Coupling Region [10, 11]. EUPHEMIA uses the system marginal pricing theory. It may consider simple and complex bids from both supply and demand sides, and may also take into account the physical constraints of the cross-zonal capacity [12, 13]. By computing the price and quantity for each bidding zone, the algorithm also defines the day-ahead flows between bidding zones [14].

Intraday markets (IDMs) may involve auctions, like DAMs, but with several sessions, or operate continuously, using the pay-as-bid scheme, or even using bilateral contracts. Transmission system operators (TSOs) consider the market results of DAMs and IDMs for scheduling the real-time operation. Deviations from schedules have to be balanced in balancing markets (BMs), and the players that deviate need to pay (or receive) the imbalance prices.

BMs are required and imposed by the European Network of TSOs (ENTSO-E). Operationally, TSOs have the responsibility to ensure that the power reserve values for BMs are within their control zone, based on ENTSO-E requirements. In Europe, there are three key types of load-frequency control products negotiated in BMs. During real-time operation, primary or frequency controlled reserve (FCR) is the first product to be activated, after grid disturbances, incidents or imbalances between production and consumption, that result in frequency oscillations. It must be activated up to 15 seconds and the disturbances have to be extinguished in 30 seconds. In some European countries, FCR is a mandatory and non-remunerated system service for all generators connected to the grid, who have technical capability for fast response. They need to reserve 5% of their nominal power to FCR. Secondary or automatic-activated frequency restoration reserve (aFRR) has to be activated in 30 seconds, taking a maximum of 15 minutes to be completed, replacing FCR. Tertiary or manually-activated FRR (mFRR) must be fully activated in 15 minutes, and can continue active for hours, freeing up FCR and aFRR (see [15–17] for a complete overview).

Derivatives markets and tailored bilateral contracts are commonly used in electricity markets to hedge against pool price volatility. However, if inappropriately chosen, they may actually worsen the benefit, since the eventual random at market clearing time may end up being either too high or too low compared to the contract price. Beyond pool price volatility, there exist other sources of risk associated with engaging in this type of agreements, mainly random generation and network forced outages, load forecast errors, and fuel price uncertainty [18–20]. These risks can be measured using different metrics, such as the value at risk (VaR). Risk management can be useful to decrease these risks, with or without direct association to spot prices. The negotiation of a bilateral contract will therefore converge only if both sides can find a pool/bilateral mix that provides an acceptable compromise between risk and benefit [21–23].

In retail markets, retail competition is performed by retailers proposing multi-part tariffs to consumers. The tariffs are composed of a fixed term (contracted power) and a variable term (energy used), and normally are equal to all consumers inside their consumption segment. In relation to the variable term of the tariff, consumers can also choose between simple or 2-rate, 3-rate or 4-rate prices. In Portugal, at the beginning of the liberalization process, retailers persuaded consumers with discounts to the regulated tariff. Currently, retailers have their own reference prices, and discounts are performed over such prices. So, retailers persuade consumers with significant “virtual” discounts, even if the (final) tariffs they

propose are higher than regulated tariffs. Thus, retailers are profit-seeking agents, following a business as usual strategy, which makes the energy part of the tariff (retail prices) higher, when compared to the wholesale prices.

1.1 Motivation

In 2007, the European Electricity Regulatory Forum (EERF) made the decision to advance with the European Internal Market for Electricity (EIME). In 2008, the EERF designed a Target Model (TM) that considers the harmonization of the market rules in all European EMs to facilitate the cross-border trading across all horizons (forwards, day-ahead, intraday and real-time). In 2009, the European Commission (EC) published the first proposal for regulating the EIME, following the Third Energy Package, that incentivises the liberalization and harmonization of EMs [24, 25].

The harmonization of DAMs can be considered a success, with an area representing more than 85% of the European markets. However, for IDMs and BMs, there are some questions still waiting to be addressed more thoroughly [26–30]. In particular, for IDMs, there are some differences that need to be discussed in detail to achieve a full harmonization, specially related to the market time unit (between 15 min and 1 hour), the gate closure (between 5 minutes and 3 hours), the market coupling (only possible in a few countries), and the trading type (continuous or auction) [31–33]. For BMs, the harmonization is not at an advanced stage, due to their importance for a secure and stable operation of the electricity grid and the necessity of interventions by transmission system operators (TSOs), as well as because of the discrepancy between the adopted schemes for procuring balancing energy in the secondary and tertiary reserve markets in Europe [28]. Currently, only Norway, Sweden, Finland and Eastern Denmark maintain the system balance together. The ENTSO-E has already elaborated a definition of product requirements and a set of rules for a cross-border market for BMs and ancillary services, but there is still a need for uniform pre-qualification rules, bidding times, tendering rules, remuneration rules and minimum bid sizes (see [15, 35, 39] for a complete overview).

Variable renewable energy (VRE), such as solar and wind power, has grown substantially in the past few years. VRE increases the volatility and uncertainty of the net load and has significantly capital costs, but near-zero production costs. These characteristics may influence the results of spot markets [40]. The potential impacts of VRE on EMs need to be carefully analysed to determine if the existing designs are still effective [41–50].

In 2014, the International Agency of Energy (IEA) presented a report where they score key EMs taking into account the best market designs according to their performance to deal with high shares of VRE. IEA took into account eight key dimensions: non-VRE dispatch, VRE dispatch, dispatch interval, last schedule update, grid representation, interconnector management, and system services definition and market. IEA indicated that all physical transactions should be performed through implicit auctions in a centralized pool without feed-in-tariffs (FiTs) or other incentives to renewable energy sources (RES), with an interval up to 10 minutes and updates up to 30 minutes before real-time operation. Furthermore, the reserve requirements should be computed stochastically, taking into account different scenarios for

the shares of VRE, and be remunerated through marginal pricing [51].

On 30 November 2016, EC presented a new package of measures, named Clean Energy for all Europeans, with the goal of facilitating the clean energy transition and the operation of the EIME. In 2017, EC proposed a draft of a new proposal for regulating the EIME [35]. It encompasses legislation for a gate closure of markets closer to real-time operation, balance responsibility for renewable energy sources (RES), portfolio or aggregation bidding, reduction of the market time unit up to 15 minutes, the use of forward contracts by RES, the participation of VRE and demand-response in BMs, among other actions.

Against this background, the first motivation of this work is to analyse the influence of the proposed regulation to market participants, notably the benefits to VRE producers, conventional generation (CG), retailers and consumers generally.

The current electricity markets were designed for dispatchable power plants, so they do not incentivise the active participation of VRE producers without being coordinated with dispatchable power plants [36–38]. IEA has defined the elements of market design and the market rules that should be taken into consideration for an efficient operation of EMs with high shares of VRE. EU is working in new legislation for the EIME to comply with some of the changes to both market design and market rules indicated by IEA. Accordingly, elements of market design, such as gate closures closer to real-time operation and shorter products, and new market rules allowing aggregated bidding, participation of VRE producers in BMs, and balance responsibility for RES, can be important features of the future electricity markets.

The second motivation consists in the hypothesis that a gate closure close to real time operation, as well as wind power aggregation, shorter market products, and the participation of VRE in BMs are important aspects of markets with increasing levels of VRE [17, 52].

Before liberalization, consumers were subject to regulated tariffs, but now they can choose their supplier of electricity and their desired type of tariff. The liberalization of the retail market brought competition between retailers.

The portfolios of retailers composed of end-use consumers are uncertain in terms of consumption, so they are subject to substantial imbalances and consequently to the payment of penalties. Furthermore, retailers have to face the market price volatility, which makes them offer tariffs with high risk premiums to end-use consumers, where the energy-part of the tariff can be significantly higher than the wholesale price. The main problem associated with retailers is that they usually do not optimize their portfolios, following a business as usual strategy, proposing high tariffs, equal to each consumer segment. Accordingly, the third motivation of this work consists in the hypothesis that optimal portfolios of end-use customers (in terms of risk-return ratios) lead to more competitive tariffs to key consumers and stable outputs.

Due to the complexity and risk of EMs, decision making has become increasingly difficult. So, it is important to provide market players with the adequate simulation tools to adapt themselves to the new reality [53, 54]. Multi-agent systems (MAS) are fundamentally networks of software agents that cooperate to resolve issues that are difficult to solve individually [55, 56]. MAS can deal with complex dynamic interactions and support both artificial intelligence techniques and numerical algorithms. Theoretically,

a multi-agent method is a perfect fit to the naturally distributed domain of a liberalised electricity market. Although there are several MAS to simulate EMs (see *e.g.* [57–60]), most of them were developed to simulate traditional market designs. Accordingly, the fourth motivation consists in the hypothesis that a flexible agent-based system able to simulate specific new elements of market design is important for markets with increasing levels of VRE. Furthermore, such a system may be very useful to market participants, facilitating their decision making process and thus helping them to get better outputs from markets.

1.2 Objectives

By modeling and simulating markets, agents and new market mechanisms, the work performed in this thesis intends to respond to the following key research question:

Are the current market designs appropriated for an active and efficient participation of wind power producers and retailers?

By using MATREM [61] (for Multi-Agent Trading in Electricity Market), the main goal of this thesis is to investigate and test new market designs, as well as to analyze the behavior and support decisions of active market players, such as retailers, coalitions of consumers and VRE producers, in order to determine if they can get better outcomes from the market. This thesis also intends to support end-use consumers in their decisions in relation to accept tariffs, demand-side management and demand response. Furthermore, the work presented here also intends to support decision-maker agents, such as system operators, market operators, regulators and legislators, by proposing and testing new market mechanisms and new elements of market design, with the goal of increasing the efficiency of markets and power systems.

More detailed, the work presented in this thesis intends to respond to the following important open questions:

- i *Is the new EC proposal for the internal market beneficial for the European Union?*
- ii *Are the current market designs, rules and products in Europe adequate for high penetrations of VRE?*
- iii *Can VRE producers be active players and be attracted to new investments without feed-in-tariffs or other incentives?*
- iv *Is risk management a good solution to improve the decision-support methodologies of agents?*
- v *Can retailers and consumers benefit from optimized portfolios of end-use consumers?*
- vi *Are aggregation and demand response a good solution to increase the efficiency of power systems?*

To address these questions, the theoretical work is supported by simulations using real-world (or partially real-world) studies, using MATREM, taking into account the following main objectives and tasks:

1. To investigate current market models and to model new elements of market design, new rules and new market products:

- (a) To study the models of day-ahead (European model) and intraday (Iberian model based on auctions) markets, using the system marginal pricing (SMP) algorithm. To develop and test new elements of market design, notably a gate-closure closer to real-time operation and shorter market products;
 - (b) To study the market models of the secondary and tertiary reserve markets, using the marginal pricing theory and the Electricity Balance Guideline (EBG) rules. To develop and test new market rules, notably rules related to aggregated bids, participation of VRE producers in BMs, balance responsibility of RES, and the market time unit. Also, to develop new market products associated with an active and efficient participation of VRE producers in BMs;
 - (c) To study models of standard bilateral contracts and to develop/extend models of non-standard contracts, such as forwards and contracts for differences (CfDs), with the goal of minimizing the price risk;
 - (d) To study and develop a new market product for short-run electronic trading of energy to reduce the deviations in the power system;
 - (e) To model competition in wholesale markets: to study and use optimization models for computing the spot/bilateral mix of producers, the coordination between wind farms, hydroelectric and thermal power plants and consequently, the bids to traditional and adapted spot markets and BMs, such as in new market products;
 - (f) To model competition in retail markets: to develop and use models of retailers and consumers to simulate retail markets competition and results;
 - (g) To study and test DSM measures, DR programs and load-shape goals.
2. To model wind power producers and wind aggregators:
- (a) To equip these agents with models allowing them to participate in the different markets, notably the day-ahead and balancing markets, with the main goal of increasing return, as well as using aggregation and forecast to predict production and reduce errors.
3. To model retailers:
- (a) To study a management process involving three phases, namely risk assessment, risk characterization and risk hedging. To model risk management strategies, utility functions and optimization models to deal with bilateral contracts of electricity;
 - (b) To develop strategies for using a new short-run electronic trading product and to respond to DSM actions of consumers and to purpose DR programs;
 - (c) To develop an optimization model, using a risk management process, and the Markowitz theory, to obtain efficient portfolios of end-use consumers;
 - (d) To develop strategies to negotiate bilateral contracts.
4. Designing real-world case-studies:

- (a) To test and simulate the markets and their participating agents identified in the previous tasks (items 1 to 3) and in the complementary task below;
- (b) To use the MATREM system, notably to create new agents to participate in the different markets, involving information about market prices, bidding strategies, etc. Also, to equip the agents with real-world data (or partially real-world data);
- (c) To quantify key-variables and key performance indicators (KPIs) in real-world simulations.

Complementary objective:

5. To model consumers and coalitions of consumers:

- (a) To develop strategies to negotiate bilateral contracts and to define utility functions to score proposals and support decisions;
- (b) To consider optimization processes to respond to DSM measures and DR programs;
- (c) To adapt the contract-net protocol to allow communication between members of coalitions and to develop intra-team strategies to support decisions and select proposals.

1.3 Core Contributions

This research work, performed to comply with the previous objectives and research questions, is in line with the research objectives defined by the MIT Portugal Sustainable Energy Systems doctoral program and with the objectives defined in the PhD scholarship (“Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia” (FCT), reference PD/BD/105863/2014). Additionally, the work partially covers the objectives of the following projects and tasks in which the National Laboratory of Energy and Geology (LNEG) participates:

- MAN-REM – Multi-Agent Negotiation and Risk Management in Electricity Markets (PTDC/EEA-EEI/122988/2010), funded by FCT;
- IRPWind – Integrated Research Programme on Wind Energy, European project under grant agreement No. 609795;
- IEA Wind Task 25 – task that analyzes and develops methodologies to evaluate the impact of wind power on power systems.

The work performed in this thesis resulted in the publication of thirty-four scientific papers. Twenty-eight conference papers have been presented and published in the proceedings of top level conferences on electricity markets, power systems, sustainable energy systems, multi-agent systems and artificial intelligence. Two book chapters and four journal articles (chapters 3 to 6 of the present document) have been published in books and SCI indexed journals with high impact factor (IF).

1.3.1 Core Articles

The four core articles of this work are the following:

I Hugo Algarvio, Fernando Lopes, António Couto, João Santana and Ana Estanqueiro, “Effects of Regulating the European Internal Market on the integration of Variable Renewable Energy”, *WIREs Energy and Environment*, 8:e346, 2019, Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews, IF 2017: 2.514, Scimago Journal & Country Rank (SJR) 2018: 0.929 (quantile Q2 - Renewable Energy and Environment) [39].

Hugo Algarvio conceived the idea, analysed and criticized the legislation, and wrote an initial draft of the paper. Fernando Lopes performed a deep revision of the initial version of the article, regarding both language and scientific content. António Couto, João Santana and Ana Estanqueiro read a final version of the article.

II Hugo Algarvio, Fernando Lopes, António Couto and Ana Estanqueiro, “Changing the Day-Ahead Gate Closure to Wind Power Integration: A Simulation-Based Study”, *Energies* 12(14), 2019, IF 2018: 2.707, SJR 2018: 0.612 (quantile Q1 - Electrical and Electronic Engineering) [52].

Hugo Algarvio and Fernando Lopes conceived the idea analysed in the paper. António Couto developed the forecast methodology and contributed to the development of the case-study. Hugo Algarvio conducted the real-world study with the help of the MATREM system. Hugo Algarvio and António Couto wrote an initial draft of the article. Hugo Algarvio performed the study, developed the concept and the model for the strategic bidding, and the case-study. Fernando Lopes performed a deep revision of the initial version of the article, regarding both language and scientific content. Ana Estanqueiro read a final version of the article.

III Hugo Algarvio, António Couto, Fernando Lopes and Ana Estanqueiro, “Participation of Wind Power Producers in Day-ahead and Balancing Markets: An Overview and a Simulation-based Study”, *WIREs Energy and Environment*, Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews, 8:e343, 2019, IF 2017: 2.514, SJR 2018: 0.929 (quantile Q2 - Renewable Energy and Environment) [17].

Hugo Algarvio conceived the idea analysed in the paper, performed the study and wrote an initial draft of the article. António Couto developed the forecast methodology and performed a short revision of the article. Fernando Lopes performed a deep revision of the article, regarding both language and scientific content. Ana Estanqueiro read a final version of the article.

IV Hugo Algarvio, Fernando Lopes, Jorge Sousa and João Lagarto, “Multi-agent electricity markets: Retailer portfolio optimization using Markowitz theory”, *Electric Power Systems Research*, Elsevier, vol. 148, pp. 282–294, February 2017, IF 2017: 2.856, SJR 2017: 1.048 (quantile Q1 - Electrical and Electronic Engineering) [62].

Hugo Algarvio and Jorge Sousa conceived the idea analysed in the paper. Hugo Algarvio performed the experimental work and wrote an initial draft of the article. Fernando Lopes contributed to the development of the study and performed a deep revision of the article, regarding both language and scientific content. Jorge Sousa and João Lagarto commented a draft version of the article.

These core papers support the following two main areas (and sub-areas):

- Wind Power Integration and New Market Designs: model and simulation of new elements of market design, rules and market products, such as new strategies that allow an active participation of wind power producers in EMs.
- Portfolio Optimization and Retail Competition: retailers obtain their optimized portfolio based on a risk management model and compete in retail markets for key-consumers.

1.3.2 Discussion of core contributions: Main articles and other publications

This section summarizes the core contributions. It focuses on the work performed and the innovation in relation to the state of the art. Figure 1.1 depicts the state of the art in relation to the design and operation of both energy markets and market participants (grey color), as well as indicates schematically the core contributions of the work performed to the state of the art (green color).

Figure 1.1: Schematic indication of the main contributions of the work performed in the thesis.

Wind Power Integration and New Market Designs

In [63], the authors introduce a modification in the market design, by changing the day-ahead closing time to 6 p.m. (UTC). The authors use the system marginal pricing (SMP) algorithm to compute the day-ahead clearing prices and the K-nearest neighbor (K-NN) method to forecast and compute the energy bids of the wind power aggregator. A case-study was developed using real data from the wind power aggregator. The results of the case-study show that postponing the day-ahead closing time to 6 p.m. can benefit almost all the parties of the electric system, mainly the wind power aggregator and the system operator.

In [64], the previous work was extended by using representative days (of two years of real wind power data) for the wind power aggregator and a case-study with data taking into account the Iberian market (MIBEL). The use of representative days can also give a general overview about the effects of the wind

power forecast errors over the price of electricity. As in the previous work, the results show that there is a significant benefit in postponing the day-ahead market closing time to at least 6 p.m.

The main limitation of using the representative days is that they only represent the wind power production of Portuguese wind farms, not the market behaviour (also influenced by the Spanish variable generation). Taking into account that the wind power aggregation corresponds only to the Portuguese wind farms, in the context of the MIBEL, the behaviour of these wind farms has a slight influence on the market prices (their installed capacity corresponds only to around 10% of the MIBEL's demand). In this context, the use of the representative days can be more important to analyse the behaviour of the Portuguese balancing markets taking into account the typical profiles and errors of wind farms.

In [65], a new probabilistic forecast strategy is introduced to reduce the forecast errors. The strategy consists in obtaining the optimal probabilistic quartiles that minimize the forecast errors in every hour of the day, and is called the "Min. 24h NRMSE" strategy. The use of this strategy brings only a slightly benefit to wind power producers, but a significant benefit to the system and the system operator, by reducing the needs of the tertiary reserve market. However, taking into account that the wind power aggregator corresponds only to Portuguese wind farms, the use of this strategy has a small influence on market prices.

In [66], a study about the various ways that wind power forecast errors can influence the balancing market costs was presented. The goal of this work is to compare the balancing market costs in Denmark, Finland and Portugal. The study is divided in two parts: i) the wind power aggregation is offered only in day-ahead markets, and ii) the wind power aggregation is offered two hours ahead of real-time operation. It was verified that in Portugal the costs of the balancing market are around four or five times higher than the ones in Finland and Denmark, respectively. Also, while in Finland and Denmark the offers of wind power aggregators submitted two hours ahead reduce the imbalance costs around 50%, in Portugal the reduction is only around 30%. Also, the imbalance cost payments for the Portuguese wind farms are almost six times higher than the ones in Denmark and Finland.

In [67], the authors developed a linear programming model to analyse the influence of the investment in new renewable sources over the electric power system. It was verified how a power system composed of a majority of thermal power plants has to be adapted in order to reduce the total costs and maintain the security. The Government incentivized the investment in new renewable sources by offering a feed-in tariff of 80 €/MWh. In a context where the power system has been adapted over time to the introduction of the renewable power plants, the thermal capacity was reduced around 11%. The installation of the renewable power plants corresponded to 30% of the system total capacity and can feed around 15% of the total demand of the system. In this context, the over-cost was 10% (73% from the tariff deficit and 27% for capacity reserve). For the case where any thermal power plant was dismantled, the total over-cost was 17.5%.

In [68], the authors simulated the behaviour of a DAM in situations with increasing levels of wind generation, and also compared market schedules and prices in situations involving either simple and complex (linear) bids. It was verified that large penetrations of variable generation led to a reduction of market prices and the participation of thermal power plants. This can affect the long-term output of these

power plants, resulting in an unsustainable situation and possible insolvencies, without Government actions. Also, complex offers seem to lead to a more fair system, by bringing (to a certain extent) more dynamism to the market, and also by considering power plants with similar prices (marginal power plants), instead of only power plants with the lowest prices.

In [41], the authors studied the main European and American markets from the point of view of the wind power integration. They concluded that the European markets have (sub-) market close to real-time (i.e., intraday and balancing markets) with small liquidity and flexibility (normally one-hour products). The American markets are extremely regulated (do not incentive competition) and do not allow bidding updates close to real-time (around one hour and half before), but have the flexibility that VRE producers need, by considering 5-min markets.

In [69], the authors studied and simulated the “informal” hydro-wind balance in Portugal, concluding that hydroelectricity producers use the hours with lower spot prices (normally with high wind power shares and low demand) to pump, and the hours with higher spot prices (normally peak hours with high demand) to produce.

In [39], the authors presented an overview of the possible effects of the new EU proposal for the internal market of electricity, concluding that the proposal is very positive for consumers, and incentivize the integration of variable renewable energy (see chapter 3 of the present document).

In [52], the authors studied the effect of a day-ahead market gate closure closer to real-time operation in a context involving high levels of wind power. By changing the gate closure from 12 noon to 2 p.m., they concluded that it is possible to increase the wind energy value to markets in more than 11% and to reduce the forecast errors of wind farms around 44% (see chapter 4 of the present document).

In [17], the authors studied the participation of wind farms in the Portuguese balancing market. In a case study where wind farms can participate in the tertiary reserve market, they concluded that changing the market time unit from 1 h to 15 min increases the wind energy value in 6% and reduces the imbalances of wind farms around 10% (see chapter 5 of the present document).

Portfolio Optimization and Retail Competition

In [70], the authors presented a deterministic optimization model to determine the quantity of power that a producer should offer in a pool market and by signing forward contracts with different types of consumers, in order to maximize the profit. Such quantity is limited to the installed power of the producer and takes into account the marginal cost of production. The approach considered involves a deterministic optimization that uses past data from a specific period of time, so all the information is known. A case-study is performed for a week in the past, taking into account the market prices, the marginal cost of production, the consumption of consumers and the tariffs proposed to consumers. The resolution of the optimization problem led us to determine the optimal quantity of energy to be sold in the day-ahead market and by forward contracts. In relation to the forward contracts, the optimization problem also computed the percentage of energy that must be sold to every consumer type, in order to maximize the producer's profit.

In [71], the authors presented a deterministic optimization problem to maximize the profit of retailer

agents. A retailer buys energy in the day-ahead market and then sells it to end-use consumers. The optimization problem takes into account the day-ahead prices, the consumption of consumers, and the tariffs proposed to consumers for a specific period of time in the past. The resolution of the problem allows us to get the optimal weight of each consumer in the retailer's portfolio for the simulated period of time. The article presents a case-study where the optimization was performed for one week.

The work presented in the two previous articles is limited, by considering the past only, i.e., the market prices and the real consumptions of the consumers are completely known. Furthermore, by using a deterministic algorithm, we obtain the optimized portfolio for a specific period of time in the past (e.g., one week), so there is no risk in the portfolio. This kind of approach can be used when all information is known (risk free), to make some optimizations taking into account past results. The optimization of a portfolio of consumers for the future should consider a risk–return optimization.

In [62], the authors presented a model for optimizing the portfolios of retailer agents (composed of end-use customers), using risk management and the Markowitz theory (see chapter 6). They focused on the dual objective of maximizing the return and minimizing the risk associated with portfolios composed of end-use customers. It was verified that the main risk factors that a retailer faces when signing contracts with end-use consumers are the market price volatility and the consumption variability of the consumers. The authors developed three case-studies to illustrate (and test) the model. The case studies involve a retailer (software agent) that wants to optimize its portfolio of clients using real data from the Iberian Market (MIBEL). For moderate risk-averse retailers, the authors concluded that they will only want consumers of the following types: small commercial (SCom), street lightning (SL) and industrial (Ind). This occurs because SCom consumers lead to higher returns (relative values), SL consumers mitigate risk (lower VaR) and Ind consumers lead to higher absolute returns (they are favorable when retailers desire a portfolio with high revenues). Large commercial (LCom) consumers have a consumption pattern similar to SCom consumers, but give a lower relative return. So, when both types of consumers (SCom and LCom) are considered, they increase the risk of the portfolio. Thus, for risk-averse retailers, LCom consumers are not favorable in portfolios with a substantial share of SCom consumers. Residential (Res) consumers have a consumption pattern with high variability, so they increase the risk of the portfolio. Res consumers are only favorable in cases when they give high returns to retailers (risk-seeking agents). For risk-averse retailers, they can be favorable when risk mitigation measures are applied, such as risk sharing.

The main limitations of this work are: i) considers the day-ahead market only, ii) the optimal portfolio only requires specific types of consumers (mainly SL and SCom consumers), iii) does not test the model for retailers with different risk attitudes, and iv) uses clusters of consumers instead of real consumers (real consumption data).

Subsequent work covers the second limitation by using risk sharing contracts [72]. This type of contract can be applied to obtain optimal portfolios with a higher variability of consumers. Preliminary results show that by the use of risk sharing contracts leads to optimal portfolios with a higher variability of consumers and also contribute to efficient portfolios. The use of risk sharing contracts can be important to mitigate the risk factor associated with the market price volatility. The use of demand response (DR)

programs can help to mitigate the risk factor associated with the consumption variability. However, taking into account that risk is measured by considering VaR, the use of DR programs increases the expected return of the portfolio (as expected), but also the VaR of the portfolio, because it increases the variance related to the return.

1.3.3 Classification of the Contributions

The work performed in this thesis is reported in the thirty-four scientific papers mentioned above, meaning that the scientific contributions involve mainly the aforementioned contributions, but also other (complementary) contributions. Accordingly, the author presents below a classification of the various contributions (see Table 1.1).

Table 1.1: Contributions and Publications

Areas (and sub-areas)	Research Questions	Objectives	Core Publications	Other Publications
Spot markets	v-x	1-4	I-IV	[13, 41, 64, 77, 79]
Balancing markets	v-ix	1-4	I-III	[41, 66]
Bilateral Trading and DM	i-iv,ix,xi-xiv	1-5	IV	[73-76]
New market designs	v,viii-x	1,4	I-III	[63, 64, 66]
DSM and DR	iii,iv,xiii	1,3-5	I	[74, 77, 78, 83-85]
Aggregators	ix,xii	1,2,4,5	I-III	[68, 86, 87]
Wind power integration	v-x	1-2,4	I-III	[65, 67]
Risk management	i-ii,xi-xiv	1,2,4,5	IV	[72, 80-82]
Decision support	i-iv,viii-ix,xi-xiv	1-5	II-IV	[68, 72, 76, 80, 81]
Portfolio Optimization	i-iii,ix,xii	1,3,4	IV	[70, 71]
Real-world case-studies	i-xiv	1-5	II-IV	[63, 65, 83, 87]

The contributions (of the complementary publications) are related to some areas and sub-areas listed in the table (and also associated with some objectives and tasks indicated in section 1.2). In particular, these contribution involve the design, modelling and testing of new optimization and bidding strategies to support the participation of agents in EMs, notably spot markets, balancing markets, and derivatives markets. Also, they are associated with: (i) the design and simulation of a new type of contract for risk mitigation, (ii) the optimization models and negotiating strategies for retailers and consumers operating in EMs, using DR programs and DSM measures, and (iii) the design and simulation of consumer coalitions to improve their bargaining power. Taking into account the large number of (complementary) publications, and for simplicity and readability, a detailed discussion of the contributions associated with them is deferred to the next chapter (see section 2.9).

1.3.4 Theoretical and Experimental work: A Comprehensive perspective

As noted, Figure 1.1 depicts the core work performed in this thesis, stating its contributions to the extension of the state of the art. This section tries to put all the work in context, describing its main parts and, fundamentally, the inter-relations between the individual parts. This is done by taking into account the characteristics of the system that supported all the experimental work, namely the MATREM system.

Agents are computer systems capable of flexible action and able to communicate with other agents

to meet their design objectives. ¹ Agents have knowledge bases to store declarative knowledge. In their knowledge bases they have information about their beliefs and goals, as well as beliefs about EMs and their opponents. Each agent can initiate communication with other agents. Agents are modeled and initiated using the JADE platform. They have a goal-based architecture [54].

Generation companies (GenCos) use optimization models to obtain the best share of energy to sell in the DAM and to sign forward contracts, taking into account the prices of future forward agreements, the variable costs of power plants and the forecasts of the DAM prices. They also have optimization models to schedule the allocation of each power plant to satisfy forward contracts and day-ahead commitments taking into account a hydro-thermal-wind-PV optimization problem based on optimization solutions.

The wind aggregator (WA) agent considers the aggregation of WPPs using the K-medoids clustering algorithm [88]. The WA agent follows a strategic bidding process that determines the bids to submit to the DAM, each IDM session, and BMs, and how to use the new market products (based on the wind power forecasts and the cleared bids). The forecasts are obtained using the K-nearest neighbour method [89, 90].

Retailers use a risk-return optimization model to obtain optimal portfolios of end-use consumers based on specific characteristics (such as, risk attitude, expected return and pricing strategies). They use multivariate time series as the forecast methodology, to compute the expected spot prices and the consumption forecast of their portfolios, using real data from spot markets and consumers. They also have information of the prices and quantities of future bilateral agreements with sellers of electricity. Furthermore, they propose the tariffs obtained by their pricing strategies to key consumers, that can accept or reject them. In case any key consumer does not accept a proposal, retailers need to re-plan their portfolios with the current consumers (i.e., those who have already accepted their proposals) and possible (new) key-consumers (the ones that were not in the previous portfolio).

Consumer agents are equipped with utility functions, capable of supporting their decisions in the process of choosing the best tariffs, among the various tariffs that retailers propose to. If consumers do not have information about their consumption, they can use an additive function (and give weights to each period of the proposed tariffs). Otherwise, they can use a multiplicative function or a cost function (involving expected costs based on the prices of the tariffs and the expected consumption).

The new elements of market design cover gate-closures of EMs close to real-time operation (between one hour and fifteen minutes) and shorter products (between fifteen and five minutes). The new market rules consists of allowing aggregated bids in spot and balancing markets, giving balance responsibility to RES and allowing the participation of VRE in BMs. These non-discriminatory actions are positive to enable a full integration of VRE in EMs.

An analysis to the main European markets, mainly DAMs, IDMs and BMs, covering current market designs but also new market products, designs and rules, allows us to conclude that new products should focus on the trade of energy instead of power, gate closures close to real-time and short products. Since retailers and consumers share the imbalance problem with VRE producers, one of the products proposed in this work allows a short-run electronic trade of energy (fifteen minute products) between

¹A detailed description of autonomous agents, particularly their architecture and model, is well beyond the scope of this work. The interested reader can, however, see [2], particularly chapter 8 of that book.

buyers and sellers. The other two proposed products are traded between VRE producers and the TSO, being one based on fifteen minute trades of energy and the other involving the offer of a 15-minute power band by VRE. Both products are traded up to fifteen minutes before real-time operation. The use of these products largely facilitate the reduction of the system imbalances and the integration of VRE.

1.4 Structure

This thesis has six chapters. The second chapter presents an overview of the most important topics related to this work, essentially electricity markets, multi-agent systems, agent models and energy trading models. It also presents an overview of the complementary work performed. This work complements the core work of this thesis.

The third to the sixth chapters present the core work published in the journal articles. These chapters consist of the core publications that sustain the work performed in this thesis.

Finally, the seventh chapter presents the most relevant achievements and conclusions of this work. It also presents the future work.

Chapter 2

Background and Complementary

Work

This chapter presents a literature overview of the most important topics related to this work, specifically electricity markets, MAS, trading models, DR and DSR. It also presents an overview of the complementary work performed in this thesis that complements the core work presented in the previous chapter.

The research community has paid significant attention to autonomous agents lately and a number of important architectures have been proposed in the literature [4, 56]. Important real-world problems have been solved by using the agent-based technology (see, e.g., [91]). The naturally distributed domain of liberalised electricity markets is a perfect fit to multi-agent Systems (MAS). The work performed in this thesis involves the extension of MATREM with new market agents and modules. In [4, 61], the reader may find a complete description of MATREM and a comparison with other MAS for electricity markets. Also, section 2.1 presents the main characteristics and limitations of some important tools for energy markets presented in the literature.

Wind power integration in EMs is an open issue, and several new market designs have been proposed to fit VRE in markets, as can be seen in section 2.2.

Bilateral trading, as well as risk management in bilateral contracting and portfolio optimization, have an extensive literature regarding generic sectors of activity, but are not so common in the electricity sector. So, adapting the literature models to the electricity sector, and creating new models that fit with them, is an extension (and contribution) of this thesis, as can be seen in the literature review presented in sections 2.3, 2.4 and 2.5.

Consumers forming alliances to increase their bargaining power in the negotiation of new contracts or even to allow their participation in wholesale markets is one of the extensions of the state of the art (and contributions) of the complementary work performed in this thesis (see section 2.6).

Demand-side management is a well solution considered in EMs, while demand response is more recent and not so developed. These topics have in common an extensive literature, as can be seen in sections 2.7 and 2.8. One of the benefits of using a multi-agent system is the possibility of testing the effects of a methodology on the entire power system, because the applications of DSM measures will

not only affect consumers (that potentially can reduce their costs), and retailers (that have to adapt their bids to consumption changes), but the entire power system and its agents.

The overview of the core contributions (recall section 1.3.1), the core contributions presented in chapters 3,4,5 and 6, and the complementary contributions discussed in section 2.9 represent the aforementioned extensions (and contributions) and are, to some extent, put in context, according to the literature review of the next eight sections.

2.1 Multi-agent Systems for Electricity Markets

Due to increased competitiveness and dynamism, the electricity sector is very exposed to external changes. Thus, it is very important to support all involved players in this complex environment. Presently, exist various simulation systems based on the multi-agent technology that allow modeling competitive EMs. Such systems allow market participants to simulate the negotiation of prices and quantities through bilateral contracts, the trade of energy in spot markets, etc. However, they have limitations, mainly because of the complexity of the power system.

There are several simulators using agent technology for simulating actual and future market designs, like AMES (Agent-based Modelling of Electricity Systems) [57], EMCAS (Electricity Market Complex Adaptive System) [58], GAPEX (Genoa Artificial Power Exchange) [59], MASCEM (Multi-Agent Simulator of Competitive Electricity Markets) [60, 92] and SEPIA (Simulator for Electric Power Industry Agents) [93]. Other simulation tools, which are not agent-based, can also deal with EMs, such as Power Web [94], and SREMS (Short – Medium run Electricity Market Simulator) [95]. AMES is an open source MAS developed with the JAVA language, for the Repast platform, and involves four main components: traders, transmission grids, markets (day-ahead and real-time), and an independent system operator (ISO) with four functions, namely system reliability assessment, day-ahead unit commitment, dispatch, and settlement [57]. Repast is a free and open-source agent-based modelling and simulation toolkit [96]. EMCAS supports negotiation through bilateral contracts and pool markets and includes agents representing producers, intermediaries, consumers and ISOs. The agents are autonomous and perform decisions based on expected prices for pool and bilateral contracts, obtained through history analysis and future predictions [58]. GAPEX is implemented in MATLAB. It models and simulates artificial power exchanges replicating the market clearing techniques of the most important European markets [59]. MASCEM includes agents that can simulate market facilitators, generators, consumers, market operators, traders, and system operators. It features bilateral contracts and a pool market, where accepted agreements must be submitted for verification by the market operator. SEPIA is a tool for developing EM models with the purpose of gaining insights about the behaviour of system participants and their impact on EMs. It only allows bilateral contracting, where agents (composed of diverse layers) are as follows: grid zones, generators, GenCos, generator of last resort, consumers, consumer companies, transmission grid, and system operator. Power Web allows to test and analysis different kinds of energy markets, but only supports fixed demand for pool markets [94]. SREMS is based on game theory and supports scenario analysis in the short-medium term, and to evaluate the transacted power, but was

designed only for the Italian EM [95].

These tools were developed for markets with low levels of renewable generation and, for this reason, this work made use (and extend) MATREM, a new tool, that effectively supports market players in their key decisions related to the power systems of the future (i.e., involving high levels of renewables).

The majority of existing tools focuses on the following types of entities:

- GenCos or generators: represent utility companies or single generators and operate in a wholesale market;
- Traders: promote liberalization and competition, and simplify dealings either between sellers/buyers and the market operator or between sellers and buyers. Some traders can act as speculators in EMs.
- Consumers: represent end-use customers and operate in a retail market;
- System operator: maintains the system security, administers transmission tariffs, and coordinates maintenance scheduling: also, analyses the technical feasibility of all negotiated contracts;
- Market operator: regulates pool negotiations, and thus, is present only in a pool or hybrid market; uses a market-clearing tool, typically a standard uniform auction, to set market prices.

There are, however, others agents that play an important role in electricity markets, but are not modeled by these tools, notably:

- Regulator agents: represent the agents that regulate the transmission, distribution, last resource supply, the management of markets and, in some cases, approves the bilateral contracts negotiated in the non-organized (sub-) markets;
- Aggregators: manage groups of players of the electricity market (currently these agent is commonly used to manage groups of renewable producers);
- Retailer or supplier agents: represent electricity retailers and operate in both a wholesale and a retail market.

Also, there are some players that are emerging and start being modeled in the past few years only, such as:

- Coalition of consumers: represent a set of end-use consumers and, beyond the role of negotiating bilateral contracts in a retail market in favour of them, if they are large enough, they may also trade energy directly in the organized market. In the work performed in this thesis, coalitions only enter in bilateral agreements;
- Virtual power plants: responsible for managing coalitions of producers (including the responsibility of negotiating on behalf of such coalitions);
- Virtual power players (VPPs): responsible for managing a set of different technologies, like power plants, distributed generation, energy storage systems and consumers, considering demand response programs.

MATREM is composed of agents capable of adapting to different market contexts and by various market models, supporting market participants in their complex decisions [61]. The architecture, characteristics and capabilities of these agents can be found in [54].

2.2 Wind Power Integration in EMs

VRE has increased significantly in the past few years and, as noted before, it increases the volatility and uncertainty of the net load, as well as has substantial investment costs, but near-zero production costs (which decrease the results of spot markets) [40, 212]. The potential impacts of VRE on EMs need to be carefully analysed to determine if existing designs are still effective and appropriate for high penetrations of VRE [42–50].

Mills and Wiser (2014) classified the economic value of wind as the sum of four components: the market value of energy, the capacity value, the forecast error and the ancillary services values. It is worth noting that the market value of energy is (usually) positive, but the forecast error and the ancillary services values are (usually) negatives. The balance responsibility for RES may increase the costs associated with the forecast error value, which may be compensated either by strategic bidding to increase the revenue from markets or by participating in BMs, which in turn may increase the revenue of WPPs (typically, BMs prices are more attractive), and reduce the payment of imbalances, resulting in an increase in the wind energy value [213, 214].

The new proposal for regulating the EIME can benefit wind power integration [35]. It encompasses legislation for a gate closure close to real-time operation, balance responsibility for RES, aggregated bidding, reduction of the market time up to 15 minutes, the participation of VRE and demand-response in BMs, among other actions. Changing these elements of market design, and the market rules, as well as developing new market products, are important aspects for wind power integration [276, 300, 301].

The European EMs have a significant variety of designs and products. The different electricity products are traded on the exchanges (clearing houses) or OTC. These include forwards, futures and CfDs, electricity price area differentials, spreads, swaps and options. The characteristics of both the products and the market designs differ considerably within Europe, which was the subject of extensive studies and surveys [302, 303]. The motivation for the need of new market products comes from the imbalances that VRE producers, retailers and consumers originate in power systems [272, 304, 305]. These agents are the main sources of the system imbalances. Those imbalances increase the BMs use and their costs, which consequently increase the penalties that the imbalanced parties have to pay. These costs are reflected in the consumers' tariffs, that even with a reduction in the prices of energy in wholesale markets, have their tariffs increased in retail markets. The current BMs products are not adequate to the participation of VRE producers or even retailers without demand response contracts with consumers. In BMs, the bids for power (not energy) have to be performed for a period of one hour, what makes very difficult for VRE producers to keep a stable operation without curtailments (wasting free-of-cost energy) or deviations. Also, for retailers, it is difficult to keep the scheduled demand (traded in the markets) without direct load control over consumers. WPPs have to bid their expected active power in spot markets

(a fixed value for every hour), based on forecasts that use time horizons between 18h–42h in the DAM, and 7h–2h in each IDM session.

Providing reactive power is a current market product where WPPs can participate [306]. The provision of kinetic energy, also called instantaneous reserve or inertia is not a market product, but an inevitable result of the physical reality of power plants without converters. So a new product associated with VRE is the primary reserve that should be used to compensate the disadvantage of the reduced inertia in a power supply with high shares of VRE [307]. Photovoltaic (PV) systems do not have mass inertia but are entirely converter based, so they can adjust their output within milliseconds. By changing the pitch angle, wind turbines can deliver primary reserve faster than currently required. Wind turbines are also able to deliver synthetic inertia, which can solve the problem of the reduced inertia of the grid due to high shares of VRE [308].

The problem that all these products have in common is that they contribute to increase the wasting energy or curtailments of VRE, by making them participating in non-optimal schedules [309]. These products use the technical capabilities of VRE, instead of considering their optimal use without curtailments (wasting free-of-cost energy), allowing a higher short-run interaction between the market agents that are directly related to system imbalances.

2.3 Bilateral Trading

Negotiation is an important and universal form of social interaction. Traditional negotiation is normally difficult to manage, easy to misunderstanding, and time consuming. Automated negotiation is in constant evolution and has been the focus of artificial intelligence and computer science generally [97].

Normally, negotiation proceeds through several different phases or stages [22]. Preparing and planning for negotiation (pre-negotiation) is normally considered the key to successful negotiations [98]. The process of trying to achieve an agreement (actual negotiation) often involves an iterative exchange of offers and counter-offers, where parties commit to make an agreement [99, 100].

Agreements are usually accepted or rejected based on the utility functions of agents [23, 101, 102]. Utility functions are used to score proposals. The more common utility functions are the additive and multiplicative utility functions. While the additive function only takes into account individual issues (e.g., prices) the multiplicative function considers the interaction between different issues (e.g., prices, quantities, periods, etc.).

The post-negotiation involves the legal procedures related to the signature of contracts. Three different agreement types are often identified in the negotiation literature [103]: a compromise agreement, an integrative agreement and a Pareto optimal agreement. Automated negotiation is in constant evolution and has been focused of artificial intelligence research [104]. A relevant review on automated negotiation for computational agents has been presented in [105]. However, there is a need to improve the selection of the best parties, tactics and strategies to negotiate, although there is an advance in the literature [106–111].

MATREM uses the negotiation model proposed in Lopes et.al [112], with the pre-negotiation, the ac-

tual negotiation and the post-negotiation phases. In relation to the literature, the model addresses a risk management issue that allows to select target parties and strategies to negotiate bilateral agreements [62].

Signing bilateral contracts is a form of risk hedging against spot price volatility. Considering the available time and the traded quantities, buyers and sellers can consider the following options of bilateral trading [1]: customized long-term contracts, trading over the counter (OTC) and electronic trading. MATREM allows the negotiation of several types of standard and non-standard customized long-term and OTC bilateral contracts (forwards, futures and CfDs), between GenCos, producers, retailers, traders, aggregators, consumers and coalitions of consumers. Agreements need to be accepted by the market operator.

Forwards are contracts to purchase and sell a given amount of an asset (financial or otherwise), in a specific future date, at a price set in the present, and negotiated bilaterally (outside the stock exchange). Futures are standardized contracts that can be subject to physical or financial settlement, reversible, to buy and sell a given quantity of an asset, at a future date, with a price fixed in the present. Buyers are bound to pay the agreed price and sellers to deliver the active under the agreed conditions. CfDs are differential contracts between two parties, which state that the seller pays to the buyer the difference (if positive) between the market value of an asset on the closing date of the position taken, and the market value on the opening date of the position taken (the buyer protects itself, due to the possibility of price increases). Otherwise, is the buyer who pays the difference.

2.4 Risk Management in Bilateral Contracting of Electricity

Bilateral contracts are normally used to hedge against the volatility of spot prices [153–155]. However, they have to be carefully negotiated, since if they significantly differ from spot prices they may lead to significant losses for one of the parties [156, 157]. While bilateral contracts are recognized as very important to the operation of competitive EMs, there are several obstacles to long-term contracts. One of them is the risk asymmetry between buyers and sellers [158]: buyers have higher risks than sellers in waiting to trade in spot markets, so sellers can charge a risk premium for bilateral contracts. Sellers prefer to bid in spot markets where they are remunerated by marginal clearing prices, with very low risk, since they will not sell below their bids. Risk-premiums requested by sellers depend on their risk attitude (also known as risk preference or risk appetite). The risk attitude can be characterized as risk-averse, risk-neutral and risk-seeking. Risk-averse agents show typically more flexibility to get a deal, and concede more to avoid that negotiation ends prematurely without agreement. So, if an agreement is reached, these agents will probably make a worse deal when compared to agents that are not averse to risk. On the contrary, risk-seeking agents are more firm, tending to maintain their position, and thus conceding less to get a deal. Notwithstanding, in case of agreement, risk-seeking agents will probably get a better deal than risk-averse agents in similar situations.

A risk management process normally starts with a risk assessment phase where all risk factors are identified and analyzed. This phase is followed by a risk characterization method, where metrics, like

VaR (value-at-risk), are used to measure the risks. Finally, the process ends with a risk hedging phase, where some actions are performed in order to mitigate the risks [159–161].

The literature contains many relevant approaches to deal with the broader issues of negotiation and decision-making under uncertainty [162–165]. In Khatib et al. [166], the authors developed an iterative approach when a generator and a load can negotiate a bilateral contract characterized by the time of delivery, duration, amount, and price. This approach allows the negotiating parties to self-specify their risk measures, calculating the VaR, and through a probability distribution, each party can determine how the uncertain parameters (such as spot price, fuel price and demand), should be modeled.

The approach followed by Caruso et al. [167] is to some extent similar to the previous approach. The main difference is related to the fact that now the focus is placed on the producers, who need to make a decision about the price to bid in the spot market, as well as about the price to sign bilateral contracts.

Ramos et al. [168] developed a model to evaluate the optimal hedging strategy of a generation company that trades electricity in a competitive market, where two possible energy markets are considered: a spot market and a bilateral contracting market.

2.5 Risk Management in Portfolio Optimization

Typically, in retail competition, retailers sign private bilateral contracts with end-use consumers, obtaining a private portfolio to manage. To satisfy the consumption needs of the consumers that compose the portfolio, they enter into wholesale competition, submitting bids to spot markets and signing bilateral contracts with producers.

The main problem associated with retailers is that they usually follow a business as usual strategy, proposing high tariffs, equal to each consumer segment. By not optimizing the portfolios, retailers face significant risks due to the consumption variability of the consumers in their portfolios, requiring an high risk premium, that make the energy part of the tariff significantly higher than the market prices of electricity [62, 169].

Risk-averse retailers may optimize their portfolios, typically obtaining stable portfolios, allowing them to reduce the risk premium, and consequently the tariffs that they charge to consumers. However, profit-seeking retailers may have advantage in retail competition, because high variations in return lead to low variations in risk. Risk-neutral retailers do not care too much with uncertainty and risk, focusing on the expected return of portfolios. Typically, risk-seeking retailers consider large portfolios that bring a significant variability to their revenues.

The majority of the pieces of work on portfolio optimization are about portfolio management [170–176], modeling traders with the goal of maximizing profit [177–180]. There are, however, some work on electricity producers, optimizing their portfolio of (sub-) markets to sell electricity [70, 181–187]. Also, there are a few approaches that take into account the optimization of the portfolios of retailers of electricity [62, 71], as well as work on the optimization of the portfolios of (sub-) markets, where retailers can buy electricity to satisfy a specific amount of load [188–190]. Furthermore, there are some work for the specific case of traders [177, 178], producers [184] and producers of renewable energy [185].

In [188], Hatami et al. developed a decision support model for retailers that need to buy electricity to satisfy their customers. The goals are to determine the tariffs of the customers and the optimal trading options between spot markets, forward contracts, call options and self-generating facilities. The optimization aims at increasing the profit of retailers and reducing the risk of portfolios. The authors consider a fixed number of clients, corresponding to the demand of retailers, and assume an elasticity for that demand. They do not use real consumption data. Hatami et al. [189] extended the previous piece of work by considering interrupted contracts and an elasticity matrix that considers different load elasticities on each TOU block.

The work of Kettenun et al. [190] has the goal of obtaining an optimal portfolio of forward contracts by considering retailers with different risk attitudes, facing the consumption risk of their clients and the price risk of spot markets. The optimization is based on the assumption that there is a strong correlation between spot prices and the demand of retailers, which can be true for large retailers (i.e., depends on the “size” of retailers) or entire markets [169]. The authors presented a case-study that uses demand from the entire Nordpool, so the effectiveness of the methodology was not tested with typical retailers. The authors concluded that risk-neutral retailers are more concerned with price-related uncertainties, while risk-averse retailers consider forward contracts to hedge against spot prices volatility (so they are more concerned with the risk premiums of forwards). Teive et al. [177] proposed a methodology for solving the portfolio optimization problem of contracts using a multi objective genetic algorithm. In [178], the authors proposed a decision support system for solving the problems of portfolio optimization of contracts — choose the best set of market options to sell or buy electricity — by using linear programming, and also to perform a risk analysis of the portfolio performance, using VaR and CVaR metrics. In this piece of work, traders act as speculators, so they do not have clients or a fixed number of end-use consumers in the demand-side, neither fixed generators in the supply-side (they acquire a specific amount of energy and then resell it).

Suksonghong et al. [184] studied the application of several genetic algorithms to the portfolio optimization of a producer agent that wants to choose the best allocation of the produced electricity to spot markets and forward contracts.

Kazagic et al. [185] aimed at solving the problem of designing a power system with the best generators in order to achieve specific targets related to the penetration of renewable energy sources (and decarbonisation).

2.6 Coalitions of consumers

A coalition is a set of self-interested autonomous agents that can negotiate rationally [191]. In Sandholm and Lesser [192], the authors concluded that alliances of agents may save costs compared to agents operating individually. In EMs, a coalition could surpass dimension limitations, allowing agents to directly buy electricity in spot markets, and also increasing their negotiation power to achieve better electricity tariffs.

The literature contains a richness of approaches about aggregation of electricity players [193], giving

special attention to the production issues, with relates to virtual power plants [194, 195], virtual power producers [196], virtual renewable power plants [197, 198], etc. In relation to consumers, the literature has some references about aggregating and managing consumers [199–201], and their impacts [202, 203], with special emphasis to aggregator agents [127] and virtual power players (VPP) [92, 204]. The aggregator is the agent that manages the group of consumers to gather flexibility, and also generates bids to the electricity market, with the objective of maximizing the revenue. Compared to aggregators, coalitions of agent aim at minimizing the tariffs of the members (aggregators normally care with benefit only, by maximizing the profit). VPPs are entities that aggregate different types of technologies, like storage, VRE, consumers with DR contracts, etc. A VPP with a miscellaneous of several clients with different technologies manages the portfolio of clients with the objective of maximizing the revenue (which has a complete different purpose when compared to a coalition of consumers).

In Hämäläinen et al. [205], the authors developed a model where a coalition of cooperative consumers respond to real-time pricing with space-heating control, with the objective of maximizing their benefit. In Hatami et al. [206], the authors demonstrate how cooperative networked consumers considering a single electricity bill and dynamic electricity pricing could minimize their bill by reducing peak hours consumption. This approach focuses on DSM of cooperative consumers that respond to dynamic electricity pricing in order to minimize their electricity cost.

In relation to coalitions in general, there are important pieces of work on coalition formation [191, 196, 198], team strategies [207], team decision and team negotiation models [208–210].

Klusck *et al.* [191], study the impact of dynamic coalition formation (DCF) of autonomous agents, taking into account the environment and information. They designed a DCF scheme based on simulation (DCF-S) that tries to obtain the best solution (coalition) for every agent. Baeyens *et al.* [198] presented a model for coalitions of wind power producers (WPPs) to submit bids to pool and forward markets. They found that alliances of WPPs improve the expected profit. Pinto *et al.* [196] presented a new model for creating and managing virtual power producers, including a facilitator to manage communications between agents and a mechanism to rank possible agents to join coalitions.

Anguix *et al.* [207] studied the impact of the negotiation situation over various intra-team strategies: representative (RE), similarity simple voting (SSV), similarity borda voting (SBV) and full unanimity mediated (FUM). In RE, team members delegate team decision-making to a representative mediator. SSV relies on voting procedures and majority rules in each negotiation round to determine if an opponent offer should be accepted or not, and which offer is submitted to the opponent. SBV is based on rank proposals. This voting procedure has the advantage of choosing largely accepted proposals rather than majority proposals. In FUM, all members have to agree with all team decisions. They concluded that RE is the faster strategy, but FUM is the strategy that brings higher utilities. The team deadline is critical, because when it is shorter than the deadlines of the opponents, their utilities are negatively affected. Otherwise, if it is longer, negotiations may end in failure (in case of selecting tough strategies, as FUM). One interesting result is that an increase in the number of team members negatively affect utilities, so, the environment, the context and the formation of coalitions are very important. The selection of key members is a critical issue to increase utilities.

Ephrati and Rosenschein [208] used the Clark tax mechanism [211] as an economic decision process for having consensus in MAS. These mechanism has very advantages, such as non-manipulability, individual rationality, and maximization of the agents' global utility, but it is difficult to implement.

Anguix *et al.* [209] presented a negotiated model for coalitions negotiating with their opponents and reaching unanimous agreements by using a trusted mediator. They concluded that by achieving unanimous decisions the model can increase the utility of each member in relation to its goals.

Anguix *et al.* [210] presented a negotiation model with the goal of obtaining efficient agreements with low computational costs, concluding that their model can beat similar heuristics with partial information and obtain similar results in case of full information.

Comparing with the literature, in our work, we consider a slightly different interaction process between the mediator and the coalition members. Whenever the mediator receives an offer from the seller agent, at a specific time period, it prepares a new offer and starts a voting process among all members, where both offers are made public. The votes can be positive (acceptance of seller's proposal), and consequent rejection of the coalition proposal) or negative. The decision depends on the utilities that each proposal gives to each member of the coalition Thus, each member receives both proposals, rates them using its own utility function, and votes accordingly. The votes are sent to the mediator, who sums up the number of positive votes and makes a decision based on the selected decision rule. Thus, in case of a majority decision rule, if the number of positive votes is higher than the number of negative votes, then the seller's offer is accepted and negotiation ends successfully in an agreement. Otherwise, if the mediator and the coalition members decide to continue negotiating, the mediator submits a new offer to the seller agent.

2.7 Demand-side Management Measures

Bilateral contracts also have some risks associated with price and quantity. The risk of price is related to market prices and is relevant in case of bad agreements (e.g., negotiated prices distant from future prices of electricity). Other risk is the quantity risk. Retailers usually sign non-standard forward contracts with consumers, consisting in fixed prices but variable quantities, so they have the risk of their acquired energy be different from the requested energy from their customers, paying substantial penalties for deviations. One solution to mitigate this risk is to promote demand-side management (DSM) or sign demand response (DR) programs with consumers.

Customers participating in DSM programs may adopt one or more of the following load shape strategies [113, 114]:

1. *Peak clipping*: reduce the peak demand.
2. *Valley filling*: increase the off-peak demand.
3. *Load shifting*: shift demand to off-peak periods.
4. *Strategic conservation*: reduce demand during almost all hours of the day.
5. *Strategic load building*: increase demand during almost all hours of the day.

6. *Flexible load shape*: establish interruption agreements with consumers to change demand when it is necessary.

While from the point of view of the system as a whole, all measures (except the load building strategy) can be favourable to reduce costs, from the point of view of retailers the conservation strategy can decrease their profit, and the flexible load shape strategy can be hard and costly to implement. Furthermore, the market price volatility is one of the issues that increases the risk of retailers. Thus, these strategies may contribute to a reduction in the load and price volatility, reducing the risk of retailers. A reduction in risk together with an increase in profit may contribute to a reduction of tariffs. A strategic reduction in tariffs should incentivize a change in the behaviour of consumers, avoiding an increase in the peak consumption and encouraging an increase in the off-peak consumption.

In [115], Charles River Associates presented a primer on DSM with a description of the load-shape goals and real examples of price-responsive DSM programs applied in different states of the United States. There is a special focus on describing the outcomes of the time-of-use (TOU) tariffs and the consumers response to critical-peak pricing (CPP) and real-time pricing (RTP) tariffs. The real examples show the success of the DSM programs, with special emphasis to a reduction of 27% in the peak consumption of residential consumers with CPP tariffs, in the state of California.

In [113], the authors presented an overview of the DSM concepts and several real case-studies (by sector of activity) of DSM implementation all over the world, as well as a DSM implementation strategy to the Pacific Islands. Based on the outcomes of the real-world case-studies, they planned to propose dual TOU tariffs for industrial and commercial consumers with the goal of stimulate load shifting from peak to off-peak periods. Their goal with the DSM programs is to improve the system load factor, that range between 45-60%.

In [116], Palensky and Dietrich divided the DSM in different categories: energy efficiency (improving the equipment efficiency and management), TOU, market DR (price signals, incentives, etc.), physical DR (emergency signals and grid management) and spinning reserves (primary and secondary control). They present some demonstrations of DSM measures, and conclude that energy efficiency is the most wanted and used, since it saves energy and emissions at long-term. For short-run DSM, the main issue is the information and communication technology, since it must guarantee the confidentiality, integrity, authenticity, availability and the real-time access-control to data.

In [117], the authors made a review about the demand-side options in electricity markets, namely DSM programs, purchase allocation (in which type of markets they will buy the electricity) and bidding strategy (quantities and prices based on the "price maker" or "price taker" category of the participants). In relation to DSM programs, the authors focuses on the energy efficiency, incentive-based and price-based DR programs, with special attention to the risk/reward of the different price-based programs. RTP tariffs are the riskiest but more economically advantageous, while TOU tariffs are the less risky but also give a lower reward, being the CPP tariffs between them.

In [118] and [119], Jiang et al. compared the industrial and academic DSM approaches in the day-ahead and real-time markets, respectively. While academic approaches are based on the maximization of the social welfare, the industrial approaches give incentives to consumers that decrease their baseline

consumption. Since DSM participants can manipulate their baseline consumption, the authors simulated that the industrial approaches increase the system costs, the imbalances, and the costs with control reserves, and reduces the social welfare, based on the error of the baseline consumptions. An error of 0.05 can increase the system costs in 17.31%, while an error of 0.1 increases the costs in 35.69%. The costs increased mainly because of regulation (control reserves), with a 15% and 31.07% increase in the total operation costs for an error of 0.05 and 0.1, respectively, corresponding to a weight around 87% in the total increase. Thus, the inflated baselines in the industrial DSM approaches can extinguish the possible benefit of DSM, since it contributes to imbalances.

In [120], Strbac discussed the major benefits and challenges of DSM in the UK power system, stating that in UK the load factor of power plants is below 55%. So, the plants with highest fuel costs will only operate a few hours per year. Thus, DSM can reduce the generation margin, serve as alternative to generation capacity, and has a value around \$250-\$400/kW. Strbac states that DSM could decrease the amount of power plants needed to fulfil current demand and if well used, would substantially increase the average load factor of the UK power system [120]. As expected by Strback, from 2012 to 2016, the total installed capacity in UK have been reduced in more than 12%, specially the conventional steam stations (less 46%). Furthermore, the system load factor was maximal in 2013, achieving 70.7%, and vary between 66.3% and 70.7% from 2012 to 2016, significantly higher than the value of 2008 (55%). Also, as predicted by Strback, the demand falls around 5%, from 2012 to 2016, driven by reductions in consumption of the industry and domestic sectors [120].

In [121], Warren presents a review about the global DSM policies, with special emphasis in the UK power system. These type of DSM policies are divided in: regulatory (government obligations), market-based (tariffs), financial (incentives) and voluntary (marketing campaigns). At UK it is possible for consumers participate in the balancing markets through DSM measures (with restrictions) [122]. It was estimated that 1.5 GW of DSM has been contracted in 2012 [123], with values close to \$225/MWh and \$22/kW (average values of 2011) [124]. The DSM policy measures conducted to an estimated reduction in demand between 3-11% in 2012 [123, 124].

In [125] the authors made a review about DSM and propose a DSM strategy based on a price signal controller. The motivation for the work started with the load curve of UK during 2012. The authors verified that during the peak loads (5% of the year) there is a potential to decrease 17% of the load. Accordingly, they developed a controller that responds to RTP tariffs and changes the HVAC system and the water-heater operation (i.e., the heater set-point) taking into account the price signal. A simulation of the controller in 629 houses allows to shift 21% of HVAC's load and 9% of the water heater's load.

As in the previous pieces of work, the majority of the references about DSM [126–130] use load aggregation to achieve target reductions in the consumption of peak periods. So, the studies are normally performed taking into account the power systems goals.

Few articles study the perspective of consumers, as our previous work [83] ([131] is a piece of work similar to our work). Arteconi *et al.* [131] simulated the control of the cooling loads with and without storage, of an industrial building in four different scenarios: i) using the typical dual Italian tariff (peak: 0.164 €/kWh, off peak: 0.149 €/kWh) without storage (baseline), ii) using the typical Italian tariff with

storage, iii) a tariff similar to the Chinese tariff scheme (peak: 0.164 €/kWh, off peak: 0.082 €/kWh) with storage, iv) Using PV and the Italian tariff with storage. The authors concluded that in a typical week only the fourth scenario can bring economic outcomes, while in a hot week only the second scenario does not bring economic outcomes, in relation to the baseline.

Ogunjuyigbe *et al.* [132] developed a load-satisfaction algorithm that maximizes the residential satisfaction of consumers taking into account a target budget. The algorithm receives the power ratings of the devices, their time of use, their consumption, and the satisfaction of the user on each device. Taking into account the target budget, defined by the user, the algorithm selects the devices that should be used to maximize the user's satisfaction.

2.8 Demand Response Programs

DR programs enable customers to manage their consumption of electricity in response to supply conditions taking into account the market prices or incentives. Several basic categories of demand response programs (or options) have been considered, notably incentive-based programs (IBPs) and price-based programs (PBPs). IBPs give incentives to consumers. These incentives are fixed or time variable and have the goal of reducing the demand when the market prices are very high or when the security of the system is at risk. IBPs include DLC programs, interruptible/curtailable load programs (classical programs), emergency DR programs, demand bidding programs, capacity market programs, and ancillary services market programs. In the first three programs (classical programs), consumers are remunerated or receive discounts for their participation, and in the remaining programs (market-based programs), they are remunerated by taking into account their consumption behavior. DR is used in EMs to assure an efficient interaction between demand and supply [133].

PBPs are part of DSM, because the incentives for consumers adjusting their demand derive from dynamic tariffs. The goal of the PBPs is to smooth the demand curve, offering high prices during peak periods, and reduced prices in the off-peak [134–136]. PBPs are related to five types of tariffs: TOU, CPP, extreme day pricing programs (EDP), extreme day CPP (ED-CPP) and RTP [137, 138]. Consumers voluntarily respond to the tariffs based on their economic decision-making process.

IBP and PBP can also be considered as explicit and implicit forms of DR, as defined by the Smart Energy Demand Coalition (SEDC) [139], considering that they are different and irreplaceable, since consumers can participate in IBPs through aggregators and in PBPs through dynamic tariffs.

SEDC performs an overview about the European mapping of DR, verifying that the majority of the countries already adopted PBPs, using TOU rates, and also RTP tariffs. Portugal only allows TOU rates [140], but in Spain RTP tariffs are common and represent the option of 28 million customers [141]. In relation to IBPs, they are also common in Europe, specially to support ancillary services and the balancing mechanism. In Portugal, there is no active IBP [142–144], but in Spain consumers can participate in interruptible contracts, with a threshold of 5 MW [139, 140, 145]. This DR situation in the world is presented [146–149], briefly, in Woo and Greening [150]. Various applications of DR in EMs are also occurring in Europe [139, 151], China [152] and elsewhere [115].

2.9 Complementary Contributions

Figure 2.1: Complementary work that have been published

Figure 2.1 extends Figure 1.1 by considering the contributions complementary to the core contributions (green parts related to bilateral contracts, coalitions and demand response).

2.9.1 Bilateral Contracting in Multi-agent Electricity Markets

In Lopes *et al.* [112], the authors developed a model of negotiation between two agents (bilateral negotiation). This model was adopted for bilateral negotiation in electricity markets.

In [76], a brief overview about electricity markets was made, mainly electricity pools and bilateral contracting. The aforementioned model was described, specifically, for bilateral contracting in multi-agent electricity markets. The characteristic of the software agents were briefly introduced. The main focus of this paper is the development, use and test of negotiation strategies (concession strategies) during the negotiation process between the two parties. The different types of strategies were used in a case-study to analyse the strategies that bring more benefits to each party. Some negotiation strategies were developed to comply with the needs of specific market agents (consumers, retailers, etc.). In [73], this work was illustrated by considering a case-study involving the negotiation of hour-wise tariffs (24h tariffs). And in [75], an analysis of several systems for simulating electricity markets is presented together with an overview of the aforementioned model for bilateral contracting of electricity.

In [80], a procedure for bilateral contracting of electricity is described, paying special attention to the negotiation process, demand response and risk management.

In addition to bilateral contracting, the MATREM supports the simulation of spot markets (day-ahead and intraday markets) and also balancing markets (secondary band and tertiary reserve). It also has specific (exclusive) software agent models for consumers, producers, retailers, coalition of consumers,

TSOs, market operators, wind power aggregators, etc.

2.9.2 Risk Management in Bilateral Contracting

The work presented in [72] focused on the different types of bilateral contracts were described. This paper focus in the risk management process, mainly in forward contracts. I addressed risk in bilateral contracting, discussing the risk attitude of each agent (risk-averse, risk-neutral and risk-seeking) and its influence on the negotiation process. It also introduced specif utility functions that can deal with risk. The risk sharing was also introduced, including a simple concession strategy able to make both parties negotiating the risk sharing of the contract. A case-study was presented where both parties can negotiate the prices and the risk sharing of the forward contracts. The results show that by negotiating the risk sharing, both parties can sign more beneficial contracts.

The work presented in[81] focused on the risk asymmetry between both parties, while negotiating a physical forward contract. Negotiating strategies take into account the risk asymmetry of the contract and the risk attitude of each agent. It was verified that usually sellers face more risks than buyers when signing a forward contract, what makes them requiring a higher risk premium in the contract prices. It was presented a case-study that illustrates the negotiation dynamic between both parties when the seller faces more risks. As both agents were moderate risk-averse agents, they privilege the achievement of an agreement with lower risks, even if the expected returns are lower. As expected, as the seller face more risks, it was the buyer that conceded more in relation to the initial position, to achieve an agreement.

The work presented in [82] focused on on bilateral contracting involving CfDs., presenting the different risk attitudes of agents. A case-study illustrated how the parties can negotiate a CfD and how the compensation scheme works.

2.9.3 Coalitions of end-use consumers

In [86], a strategy for retailers to deal with different consumers and coalitions was introduced. A case-study was presented, where the strategy was used together with the adaptation of existing intra-team strategies, such as the representative and the similarity simple voting (SSV) strategies. The case-study illustrated that by making alliances and forming coalitions, consumers can increase their bargaining power and achieve more beneficial agreements, obtaining more competitive tariffs.

In [87] a slight modification of the interaction process between a trusted coordinator agent and the coalition members was introduced together with a case-study. A representative mediator with individual decision making (RM-IDM) was considered. Using a particular strategy, all members can vote their preferred proposal. The mediator presents to all members the proposal sent by the seller and its own proposal. The members will vote for the acceptation of the seller's proposals or for sending a new proposal (the mediator's proposal). The decision can be made over a majority (where more than fifty percent of the coalition members must agree), a consensus (75% must agree) or an unanimity (100% must agree) rule. The strategy was used in a real world case-study, where real consumers and data were used. The results showed that when all coalition members agree (unanimity rule), it is possible to

achieve better agreements for all coalition members.

[68] extended the previous papers by considering a new case-study with coalitions formed by real schools in United Kingdom with different sizes, which allow to verify that the smaller schools can benefit by making alliances with bigger schools, obtaining more competitive tariffs. This paper also tested the selection of a mediator and its consequences. It was verified that independently of the size of each member, and since the mediator negotiates on behalf on the entire coalitions, it should be chosen to increase the coalition benefit.

2.9.4 Long-term Demand-side Management measures and short-run Demand Response programs

In [84], some strategies (shifting and curtailment strategies) used by consumers to respond to market prices variations were described. Also, the “Price Management” strategy for retailers was introduced, modeling their response (tariff change) to the consumption volatility of consumers. A case-study based on time-of-use (TOU) tariffs was presented.

In [78], the previous work was extended by introducing strategies enabling consumers to deal with consumption variation and DSM measures, related to changes in the price and quantity of energy during the negotiation process.

The work presented in [74] consider both additive functions and multiplicative functions to evaluate proposals and counter-proposal during the negotiation process.

In [83], a real-world case-study was presented. It involved a state library (real consumption and equipment specifications), and the adoption of DSM measures and a DLC program to reduce costs. The results showed a significantly reduction in the electricity total costs. It was introduced a case-study with a model of a public library (real consumption and equipment specifications) where was used specif DSM measures and a DLC program in order to reduce costs. It was verified a significantly reduction in the electricity total costs.

The work presented in [77] described the application of the DR programs to the DAM of the Iberian Market for the period between January 2014 and January 2017. The study considered market prices above 80 €/MWh and reduction in demand of 1%, 3% and 5%. The results showed that the prices were reduced between 0.38% in 2017 and 37.35% in 2014. The benefit varies between 3.44% in case of a reduction of 1% in 2017, and 49.40% in case of a reduction of 5% in 2014.

In [85], the authors continued the previous study by considering the full year of 2017, obtaining similar results.

Chapter 3

Effects of Regulating the European Internal Market on the integration of Variable Renewable Energy¹

3.1 Authors

Hugo Algarvio, Fernando Lopes, António Couto, João Santana and Ana Estanqueiro

3.2 Abstract

The new proposal for regulating the European Internal Market for Electricity (EIME) can motivate the harmonization of the various National markets. The process of harmonizing the day-ahead markets (DAMs) is at an advanced stage, with an efficiency in the use of interconnectors of 86%. However, the harmonization of both intraday (IDMs) and balancing markets (BMs) is still in its infancy, with an efficiency in the use of interconnectors of 50% and 19%, respectively. The new proposal brings new targets to DAMs, and European countries should make efforts to comply with them. The same is true for IDMs and BMs, but involving more ambitious targets, requiring higher efforts to be accomplished. This paper analyses and compares the various National markets according to their compliance with the new proposal for regulating the EIME. It also analyses the advantages of the new proposal for key market participants, particularly consumers, variable renewable generation and conventional generation. The analysis indicates that the proposal contributes to a potential increase of the general welfare of all market participants. However, for both variable renewable generation and conventional generation, some aspects of the proposal can negatively affect the revenue obtained from the National markets.

¹[39], WIREs Energy and Environment 8(6):e346, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1002/wene.346>

3.3 Keywords

European Internal Market, Harmonization of European Markets, Market Participants, New Proposal of Regulation, Variable Renewable Energy Integration.

3.4 Introduction

Electricity markets (EMs) are a complex and continuously evolving reality [2, 53]. Most markets were designed according to the principles proposed in the standard market design, which was set out when the majority of power plants were dispatchable. Variable renewable energy (VRE), with near-zero variable costs, has increased significantly in the past few years. So, the potential impacts of VRE on EMs need to be carefully analysed to determine if existing market designs are still effective [42, 43, 46, 47].

The main European markets are Nord pool [5], EPEX [6] and MIBEL [7]. These markets close at 12:00 PM (CET time), 12–36 hours before physical delivery (or 13–37h in Great Britain, Ireland and Portugal). In terms of structure, these markets typically include day-ahead and intra-day markets, as well as balancing markets for defining prices and schedules in real-time. The day-ahead markets (DAMs) are the largest and most liquid physical markets. The trading occurs through an implicit auction where price and volume are calculated in day d for every hour of day $d + 1$ [10, 11]. Intraday markets (IDMs) may involve auctions (like DAMs, but with several sessions), or operate continuously. Deviations from schedules should be compensated in balancing markets (BMs), and the players that deviate need to pay the imbalance prices or penalties [15, 16].

In 2007, the European Electricity Regulatory Forum (EERF) decided to advance with the European Internal Market for Electricity (EIME) [24]. In 2008, the EERF developed a Target Model that considers the harmonisation of the market rules in all European markets to facilitate the cross-border trading across all horizons, and in 2009 the European Commission (EC) published the first proposal for regulating the EIME, following the Third Energy Package [25]. In 2016, EC presented a new package of measures, called Clean Energy for all Europeans, with the goal of facilitating the clean energy transition and the operation of the EIME. In 2017, it presented a new proposal for regulating the EIME [35]. It includes legislation for a gate closure of EMs closer to real-time operation, balance responsibility for renewable energy sources (RES), aggregated bidding, reduction of the market time unit up to 15 minutes (in 2025), implicit allocation of the cross-border capacity, participation of VRE in BMs, etc.

Arguably, the harmonization of the European DAMs can be considered a “success”, with an area representing more than 85% of the National markets. However, for IDMs and BMs, there are some issues still waiting to be addressed more thoroughly. Also, the new EC proposal aims to adjust the present European markets to new market realities, involving big quantities of electricity generated from VREs in a cost-effective way. Furthermore, the reasons and objectives of the new EC proposal include the global leadership of Europe in renewables, the integration of VRE in EMs and an increase in the general welfare of consumers.

Accordingly, the purpose of this article is twofold:

1. To analyse the European EMs, focusing on their current status and barriers to a complete harmonization, taking into account the measures indicated in the new EC proposal;
2. To analyse the potential benefits of the new EC proposal to VRE, conventional generation, end-use consumers, and power systems generally.

The remainder of this article is structured as follows. The next two sections present an overview of the European EMs, discuss their current status taking into account several key Articles of the new EC proposal, and analyse the advantages and disadvantages of the new proposal to VRE and key market players. Finally, the last section presents some concluding remarks.

3.5 The Internal Market for Electricity: Analysis of Current State

The new proposal for regulating the EIME considers the harmonisation of market rules in all (sub)markets—that is, day-ahead, intra-day, balancing and forward markets—to facilitate cross-border trading across all periods. Rule harmonization brings opportunities—and raise challenges—to accommodate the increasing levels of VRE in Europe [28, 29]. This section analyses the current status of the application of the new proposal, focusing on the main rules and procedures adopted by several key European markets.

3.5.1 Day-ahead Markets

The Multi-Regional Coupling project has been created with the objective of coupling internal electricity markets on the basis of the Single Price Market Coupling for DAMs, with implicit allocation of cross-border capacities. It also aims to ensure an harmonised approach to market organisation and a more efficient use of cross-border transmission capacities [310]. The coupled area is covering twenty-three European countries representing more than 85% of the European power system.² Market coupling mechanisms are founded on the reference prices that emerge from liquid markets [33]. DAMs close at 12:00 PM (CET time), 12-36 hours before physical delivery (or 13-37h in Great Britain, Ireland and Portugal).

Market coupling uses implicit auctions, where players trade energy on exchanges without any allocation of cross-border capacity, using EUPHEMIA, a program based on the system marginal pricing theory. It may consider simple and complex bids from both the supply-side and the demand-side, and may also take into account physical constraints of the cross-zonal capacity. By obtaining the price and volume for each bidding zone, the algorithm also defines the day-ahead flows between bidding zones. Exchanges use the existing transmission capacity to minimize the price differences between two or more areas [5]. Therefore, market coupling maximizes social welfare, avoiding potential errors in the splitting of markets, and sending relevant price signals for investment in more interconnection capacity. The efficiency of this mechanism is indicated by an increase in the price convergence between different market areas.

²Austria, Belgium, the Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Hungary, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, the Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain and Sweden.

Table 3.1: Comparison of several day-ahead European markets according to their compliance with the new proposal for regulating the EIME.

Market	EIME regulation ^a			
	Balance responsibility for RES Art. 4, par. 1 ^d ; Art. 6, pars. 2 a, b	Aggregated bidding Art. 6, pars. 2 a, b; par. 3 ^e	Market time unit ^b Art. 7, par. 2; par. 4 ^f	Price caps ^c Art. 9, par. 1; par. 2 ^g
Belgium	✓	✓	X	X
Czech Republic	✓	✓	X	X
Germany	X(not fully)	✓	X	X
France	X	✓	X	X
Great Britain	✓	✓	X	X
Italy	X(not fully)	X	X	X
Lithuania	X	✓	X	X
Poland	✓	✓	X	X
Portugal	X	X	X	X
Slovenia	X	✓	X	X
Spain	✓	X	X	X
Sweden	✓	✓	X	X
The Netherlands	✓	✓	X	X

^aEither in agreement (✓) or not in agreement (X) with the new proposal for regulating the EIME.

^bMarket time unit equal to 1 hour for all selected countries (except for Great Britain: 1 hour and 30 minutes).

^cFor most countries, price caps range between -500 and 3000 €/MWh. For Portugal and Spain, price caps range between 0 and 180.3 €/MWh

^dArt. 4 has three key paragraphs. The first paragraph defines that all market participants shall be financially responsible for imbalances, with only a few restrictions, specified in the second and third paragraphs.

^eAccording to European Commission [35] the first three points of the second paragraph of Art. 6 considers that “Day-head and intraday markets shall: (a) be organised in such a way as to be non-discriminatory; (b) maximise the ability of market participants to contribute to avoid system imbalances; (c) maximise the opportunities for market participants to participate in cross-border trade as close as possible to real time across all bidding zones.” (p. 42). The third paragraph defines that market operators (MOs) are free to develop new market products to increase the participation of the demand side and VRE (individually or through aggregation).

^fThe second paragraph of Art. 7 refers to a full harmonization between the time intervals of trading and the imbalance settlement period in both day-ahead and intraday markets. The fourth paragraph refers that the imbalance settlement period shall be 15 minutes in all control areas on 1 January 2025.

^gArt. 9 paragraphs 1 and 2, impose no price caps on markets.

In the Nordic region of Europe (12 countries), the convergence of market prices is quite significant (30%), but in remaining European regions the convergence is lower [33]. However, for the particular case of 2011, the price convergence between Belgium and France was around 90%, and the same is true for Germany and the Netherlands, as well as Slovakia and Czech Republic, and Portugal and Spain [14]. The level of harmonization of the European DAMs is large, but most countries are far from complying with the new proposal for regulating the EIME. Table 3.1 shows the main differences between several EU countries according to their compliance with the new proposal.

Table 3.1 shows that almost all analysed countries comply with some Articles of the proposal. However, some countries should make efforts to give balance responsibility for RES in order to be non-discriminatory, and also increase the incentives to minimize imbalances. In addition, Italy, Portugal and Spain should allow aggregated bidding in their DAMs, since flexible aggregated demands and VRE are typically beneficial, namely by reducing forecast errors [249]. All countries should make efforts to decrease the market time unit to 15 minutes to comply with the imbalance settlement period and not impose price caps on markets. The minimum bid size in all selected countries is 0.1 MW, complying with Art. 6, par. 2a and with Art. 7, par. 3.³

³The third paragraph of Art. 7 mentions that the products provided by MOs shall have a minimum bid size of 1 MW in order to allow the effective participation of demand-side response, energy storage and small-scale renewables.

Figure 3.1: Level of efficiency in the use of interconnectors in Europe (% use of available commercial capacity in the ‘right economic direction’) in 2016 (data from ACER [33]).

All selected countries have already market coupling, in accordance with Art. 6, par. 1⁴, and thus also comply with par. 2b [35]. We note that cooperation and market coupling is an important step towards increasing the level of efficiency of power systems, notably the economic welfare of consumers.

Overall, the level of harmonization of the different European DAMs is currently quite satisfactory, despite the changes needed in their design to comply with the new proposal. Also, the level of efficiency in the use of inter-connectors is high (see Figure 3.1).

3.5.2 Intraday Markets

At present, IDMs across Europe present several differences and raise several problems, notably differences related to the type of trading (auction or continuous trade), and problems associated with low liquidity (but see Table 3.2).

Almost all selected countries adopted a gate closure close to real-time, but the market time unit of 15 minutes is only considered in two countries (namely, Germany and the Netherlands). Furthermore, for the various aspects of the new proposal considered in this work, the harmonization of IDMs is at an equal or lower stage of development than that of the DAMs (see Table 3.2). This can also be observed in the level of efficiency in the use of interconnectors, which is 50% for IDMs and 86% for DAMs (recall Figure 3.1). Although the liquidity level of IDMs did not increase in a significant way during the past few years, the level of efficiency in the use of interconnectors increased significantly.

Accordingly, we consider that the new proposal should be complemented with rules related to auctions and exclusive IDMs in order to increase the liquidity and harmonization of markets. Also, European countries should make efforts to integrate all cross-border capacity in their markets and to harmonize IDMs in terms of: type (auction or continuous trade), number of sessions (in case of auctions), gate closure, market time unit and type of products. Furthermore, we note that Neuhoff et al. [311] concluded that the implementation of a 15-minute auction in Germany doubled the liquidity of the IDM, in comparison with a continuous trade.

⁴The first paragraph of Art. 6 incentivises the cooperation between TSOs and MOs of the EU countries. In particular, MOs and TSOs should organise the management of the integrated day-ahead and intraday markets based on market coupling, as set out in Regulation (EU) 2015/1222, in order to maximise the efficiency and effectiveness of the day-ahead and intraday trading of electricity. In relation to trading, MOs and TSOs should be subject to regulation oversight by Regulators and the Agency pursuant to Art. 59 of recast of Directive 2009/72/EC, as proposed by the communication COM (2016) 864/2, and Arts. 4 and 9 of recast of EC Regulation 713/2009, as proposed by COM(2016) 863/2.

Table 3.2: Comparison of intraday European markets according to their compliance with the new proposal for regulating the EIME.

Market	EIME regulation ^a			Other Differences ^b	
	Implicit allocation of cross-border capacity Art. 6, par. 1; par. 2 b	Gate closure close to real-time operation Art. 6, par. 2 c; Art. 7 par 1 ^e	Market time unit ^c Art. 7, par. 2; par. 4	Auctions and exclusivity ^d	Standard and non standard products
Belgium	X(only one border)	✓(5 minutes)	X	X	X
Czech Republic	✓	✓(1 hour)	X	X	X
Germany	X(only one border)	✓(45 minutes)	✓	X	✓
France	X	✓(45 minutes)	X	X	✓
Great Britain	✓	✓(1 hour)	X	X	✓
Italy	✓	X(2-3 hours)	X	✓	✓
Lithuania	X	✓(1 hour)	X	X	X
Poland	✓	X(9h30)	X	X	X
Portugal	✓	X(2-3 hours)	X	✓	✓
Slovenia	X	✓(1 hour)	X	X	✓
Spain	X(only one border)	X(2-3 hours)	X	✓	✓
Sweden	✓	✓(1 hour)	X	X	✓
The Netherlands	X(only some borders)	✓(5 minutes)	✓	X	✓

^aEither in agreement (✓) or not in agreement (X) with the new proposal for regulating the EIME.

^bX- not adequate for IDM liquidity.

^cMarket time unit equal to 1 hour for all selected countries (except for Great Britain: 1 hour and 30 minutes).

^dAlmost all countries analysed do not have auctions nor exclusivity (except Germany that considers auctions of 15 min, and Italy, Portugal and Spain that consider both auctions and exclusivity). Exclusive markets are the only available option to trade electricity in the same time horizon

^eAccording to European Commission [35] the first paragraph of Art. 7 states that “Market operators shall allow market participants to trade energy as close to real time as possible and at least up to the intraday cross-zonal gate closure time determined in accordance with Article 59 of Regulation (EU) 2015/1222.” (p. 42).

The ratio between intraday traded volumes and electricity demand during the period 2011–2016 was nearly 15% for Spain, 10% for Italy and Portugal, 7% for Great Britain, and less than 5% for the other selected countries. Thus, due to the existence of alternatives to IDMs, such as short-run bilateral contracts, the pan-European harmonization of IDMs is still in its infancy, and RES participation is quite reduced [33].

As noted for DAMs, IDMs do not allow aggregated bids nor give balance responsibility for RES, and thus are far from complying with the new EIME regulation.

Spain, Italy and Portugal consider auctions and do not allow aggregated bids, and IDMs are mandatory (i.e., bilateral contracts are no alternative to IDMs), meaning that such markets have high liquidity (see Tables 1 and 2). This can be explained by the fact that IDMs are often considered by market participants to correct the expected deviations from both VRE and the demand-side.

Figure 3.2 shows the prices of DAMs and IDMs (in the first two sessions, i.e., IDM-S1 and IDM-S2) in Spain (ES), Italy (IT) and Germany (DE), during the period 2014–2016. The prices of the DAMs in Spain and Italy were higher than the prices of the IDMs. However, for Germany, the price of the energy traded in the IDM using auctions was lower than the price of continuous trade, and both prices were higher than the price of the DAM. This can be explained, at least in part, by the fact that Spain and Italy allow do not allow aggregated bids (thus increasing imbalances), and also by taking into account that IDMs are mandatory in these countries, increasing the RES penetration and market liquidity [33].

Figure 3.2: Prices of DAMs and IDMs in Spain (ES), Italy (IT) and Germany (DE) during the period 2014–2016 (data from ACER [32, 33]).

3.5.3 Balancing markets

BMs are mandatory and imposed by the European Network of transmission system operators (ENTSO-E). Operationally, each TSO has the responsibility of guaranteeing the power reserve values for BMs within the control zone, based on ENTSO-E requirements (e.g., the reserved capacity for the frequency control reserve is 3000 MW in Continental Europe).⁵ In Europe there are three key types of load-frequency control products negotiated in BMs: frequency control reserve (FCR), automatic-activated frequency restoration reserve (aFRR) and manually-activated FRR (mFRR). During real time operation, primary reserve or FCR is the first to be activated, after grid disturbances, incidents or imbalances between production and consumption, that result in frequency oscillations. It must be activated up to 15 seconds and the disturbances have to be controlled in 30 seconds.

During real-time operation, primary reserve or FCR is the first to be activated, after grid disturbances, incidents or imbalances between production and consumption, that result in frequency oscillations. It must be activated up to 15 seconds and the disturbances have to be controlled in 30 seconds. In some European countries, FCR is a mandatory and non-remunerated system service for all generators connected to the grid, who have technical capability for fast response. They need to reserve 5% of their nominal power to FCR. However, in the Nordic countries, FCR is a non-mandatory remunerated system service. Secondary reserve or aFRR has to be fully activated in 30 seconds, replacing FCR. It can be maintained active for a maximum of 15 minutes. Tertiary reserve or mFRR must be fully activated within 15 minutes, and can continue active for hours, freeing up FCR and aFRR.

Art. 5 of the new proposal for regulating the EIME refers to balancing markets.⁶ This article is complemented with the recent Electricity Balancing Guideline [16], which has the objectives of increasing

⁵The Union for the Coordination of the Transmission of Electricity (UCTE) synchronous area.

⁶Art. 5 has six key paragraphs. The first paragraph states that all market participants shall have access to BMs. The second paragraph states that an effective non-discrimination between participants should be ensured. The third paragraph specifies the need to separate procurement between balancing energy and capacity. The fourth paragraph incentivises the maximum use and efficient allocation of the cross-zonal capacity. The fifth paragraph considers the exclusive use of the marginal pricing methodology. The sixth paragraph specifies that the settlement of imbalance prices has to reflect the real-time price of electricity.

the security of supply, limiting emissions, and diminishing the costs to customers (for instance, allowing the participation of demand response and renewables in BMs). The efficient exchange of balancing services is only observed in Norway, Sweden, Finland and Eastern Denmark, countries that share the same balance system [303]. This is the principal element of the Electricity Balancing Guideline (EBG).

Currently, the major challenges to implement the EBG are related to a full harmonization of pricing mechanisms, techniques for procuring balancing energy and methods for defining imbalance prices. The priority should be given to improving the elements of the design of BMs that inhibit (in some way) a free fluctuation of prices for balancing energy, such as an inefficient procurement of balancing capacity and regulated prices and pricing mechanisms not based on marginal pricing, which reduce the incentives for producers and the demand-side to respond to instantaneous balancing needs.

In EU-28, there are four different methods for procuring balancing energy from aFRR markets:

- pay as bid (adopted by eight countries);
- marginal pricing (eight countries);
- regulated price (three countries);
- hybrid (five countries).

There are also seven different options for procuring balancing energy from mFRR markets:

- mandatory offers (adopted by four countries);
- mandatory provision (two countries);
- pre-contracted offers (four countries);
- pre-contracted offers and mandatory offers (France);
- pre-contracted and free offer (four countries);
- bilateral market (two countries);
- organised market (nine countries).

All such different methods have led to a low harmonization of BMs, including a low efficiency in the use of the cross-border capacity for exchanging balancing services and a large discrepancy between balancing costs and imbalance prices [33]. Also, the method to define imbalance prices is different in several countries [66]. Accordingly, we consider that there is a need to define a general methodology for the different countries participating in the EIME.

3.6 The Internal Market for Electricity: Potential Impact of the New Proposal

The Articles of the new proposal can benefit power systems and consumers, by increasing market efficiency and decreasing market prices, thus contributing to a market harmonization. However, from

the point of view of VRE and conventional generation, some Articles can reduce the remuneration of producers (but see Table 3.3).

Conventional generation units properly equipped to manage their active power output and VRE producers trade the energy required by the demand-side in DAMs and IDMs (as well as through physical bilateral contracts). In these markets, if the energy delivered differs from the scheduling value, the difference is counterbalanced in BMs, which result in the payment of imbalance prices.

Table 3.3: Advantages and disadvantages of the new proposal for regulating the EIME (point of view of different market players).

Players	EC regulation ^a					
	Balance responsibility for RES Art. 4, par. 1; Art. 6, par. 2, a, b	Participation of VRE producers in BMs Art. 5 pars. 1,2; Art. 6, par. 2 a, b	Implicit allocation of cross-border capacity Art. 6, par. 1; par. 2b	Aggregated bidding Art. 6, par. 2 a, b; par. 3	Gate closure close to real-time operation Art. 6, par. 2 c; Art. 7, par.1	Market time unit Art. 7, pars. 2, 4
VRE	×	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Conventional Generation	✓	×	✓	✓	×	×
Power System	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

^a✓- advantageous, X- disadvantageous

Mills and Wiser [312] classified the economic value of wind as the sum of four components: the market value of energy, the capacity value, the forecast error and the ancillary services values. It is worth noting that the market value of energy is (usually) positive, but the forecast error and the ancillary services values are (usually) negatives. The balance responsibility for RES may increase the costs associated with the forecast error value, which may be compensated either by strategic bidding to increase the revenue from markets or by participating in BMs, which in turn may increase the revenue of VRE and reduce the payment of imbalances, resulting in an increase in the wind energy value [213, 214]. Also, the balance responsibility for RES is one of the proposed non-discriminatory actions that can benefit European consumers.

The participation of VRE in BMs can reduce system imbalances, which can increase VRE remuneration in the following ways: i) by reducing penalties, and ii) by being remunerated from BMs. However, the participation of VRE in BMs can contribute to an increase of market prices, particularly when VRE is not aggregated with conventional generation, due to a potential waste of energy when VRE needs to comply with a schedule. In February 2016, Spain has become pioneer in this respect, by considering several WPPs participating in BMs [216, 217]. Germany [219, 220] and Denmark [223, 224] has allowed the participation of WPPs in BMs with some restrictions (only for downward mFRR). Skytte and Bobo [214] performed a study for 2014 where WPPs can participate in the BMs of Denmark, obtaining an increase of 6.5% in the wind energy value. Great Britain (GB) has also allowed WPPs to participate in some balancing services that are different from traditional BMs, specifically “Manage Constraint” and “Rebalance System” (only breakdown of constraint), receiving 40% more to curtail energy than to produce it [225, 226]. And Belgium has studied this aspect in relation to downward aFRR, with a reliability in the service quality above 90% [228]. Furthermore, several studies were performed to investigate the technical capacity of WPPs to provide balancing services, analysing several aspects, notably security,

quality of service and economic outcomes [229].

Overall, the participation of VRE in BMs may increase competition and probably reduce market needs due to a reduction of VRE imbalances, which may decrease market prices, as well as the conventional generation participation and remuneration.

The implicit allocation of the cross-border capacity may increase the efficiency of power systems, improving the harmonization of EMs and increasing the transmission capacity between borders [5, 33]. Also, large interconnected power systems may benefit the integration of VRE, since large geographical dispersion typically reduces the total variability and uncertainty of forecasts. Furthermore, these measures may contribute to the harmonization of market prices and to increase the efficient use of conventional generation, by increasing the participation of the more cost-effective power plants [28, 241]. These actions can also benefit consumers by reducing market prices and decreasing both the use of incentives to VRE and the capacity needs of conventional generation, which can be reflected in tariffs [67, 242].

Aggregated and individually bidding in spot markets (limited due to grid constraints) is already followed by almost all European countries (with the exception of Italy, Portugal and Spain). The spatial aggregation of different VRE sources is typically advantageous to minimize forecast errors [245]. And this is mainly true for the particular case of WPPs, since the aggregation methodologies are related to the reduction of wind power fluctuations, by taking into consideration the spatial variability of wind. From the point of view of the demand-side, aggregated bidding is also advantageous, especially when using demand-side management or demand response programs [2, 83, 249].

Overall, the implicit allocation of the cross-border capacity and the possible aggregation of VRE (and/or other sources) can contribute to the development of regional forecasts of VRE that cover large areas of Europe, which can reduce forecast errors and increase the VRE value to the market.

Apparently, the issue of adjusting the gate closure of the DAM to a time closer to real-time was deferred by EC, despite its importance in markets with increasing levels of VRE [63, 266]. This is mainly due to the forecasts of WPPs, which may have large errors for larger time horizons [64, 258]. A study conducted for the particular case of Spain [28], taking into account the extra dispatchable costs with thermal units, indicated that the adjustment of the gate closure is only advantageous for reductions in forecast errors around 30%, for wind power, and 75%, for solar power. Also, for wind power, only forecasts around 6 hours ahead may reduce the error in more than 30%. Another study, performed for the Finish power system [241], highlighted the advantages of allowing aggregate bidding and postponing the DAM gate closure, for minimizing the forecast errors of WPPs. It also revealed that aggregate solutions are more effective to reduce forecast uncertainty than the forecast horizon, which only begins to be relevant around six hours ahead (or less). Also, Miettinen et al. [245] showed that the mean absolute error of wind power forecasts can be lower than 3% when all Nordic areas are aggregated, while in a smaller area the error can be higher than 10%. Liu et al. [259] tested several clustering techniques to improve wind power forecasts for WPPs. The results showed that some techniques reduced errors in nearly 1.5% (when compared to forecasts based on a single wind speed or power). Giebel et al. [260] showed that the correlation of forecast errors for the DAM decrease exponentially as the distance

between wind parks increases. Also, some authors proposed the aggregation of WPPs in order to submit strategic bids to EMs (see, e.g., [38, 65, 262]).

Overall, in relation to DAMs, a gate closure close to real-time is advantageous to VRE, especially to WPPs. It seems to be, however, disadvantageous to power systems highly dependent of coal power plants that need around 6 to 8 hours (of planning) ahead to schedule their commitments (if not retrofitted for flexibility). But some markets with flexible generation, and not so dependent of coal power plants, such as the Nordic power market, may clearly benefit with this measure.

The standardization of the market time unit to 15 minutes is essentially an issue of uniformity and clarity of operation, since it may not be considered a good procedure to operate with 1-hour bids and imbalance volumes of 15 minutes [35]. This measure may be beneficial to VRE producers, by enabling them to perform more accurate forecasts (VRE is more uncertain and volatile in an 1-hour time period than in a 15-min time period). However, it may be disadvantageous to coal power plants that need to change production every 15 minutes, since their flexibility and ramp rate is limited.

Other aspects of the new proposal for regulating the EIME consider removing barriers to demand response as well as the possibility to strengthen short-term markets by bringing them closer to real-time. The latter, particularly the case of bringing congestion and re-dispatch markets closer to real-time, may be considered an opportunity to meet flexibility needs and increase the effectiveness of BMs [264, 265].

3.7 Conclusion

This paper analysed some key Articles of the new proposal presented by the European Commission for regulating the EIME. The Articles consider the following aspects: balance responsibility for RES, participation of VRE producers in BMs, implicit allocation of cross-border capacity, aggregated and individually bidding, gate closure close to real-time operation, and market time unit of 15 minutes.

The paper analysed the markets of 13 European countries by taking into account their compliance with the proposed regulation. The harmonization of DAMs is already at an advanced stage, with an efficient use of interconnectors. However, there are several issues that should be addressed more thoroughly. Specifically, most countries should make efforts to:

- consider bids for periods of 15 minutes (full harmonization with the imbalance settlement period);
- give balance responsibility for RES (as a non-discriminatory proposal);
- allow aggregated bidding (as an action to reduce the VRE and demand-side imbalances);
- remove (or not impose) price caps.

The harmonization of IDMs is also reasonable, but there are still significant differences between the various markets, reflected on the level of efficiency of the interconnectors (50%). A key problem for IDMs is the lack of liquidity, mainly because most of them are not exclusive. Like DAMs, there are some questions for IDMs that need to be addressed more thoroughly, particularly in relation to the balance responsibility for RES, aggregated bidding, a market time unit of 15 minutes and the removal of price

caps. Currently, almost all IDMs consider a gate closure close to real-time, but should make efforts to allocate all cross-border capacity.

In relation to BMs, the harmonization is at an early stage of development, where only a few countries exchange balancing services, resulting in an efficient use of the interconnectors of only 19%. This occurs because there are significant discrepancies between countries, mainly by considering different methodologies for procuring energy activated from both aFRR and mFRR markets, leading to substantial differences in the overall cost of balancing services, and also in imbalance prices between European countries. Accordingly, it is important to improve (in some way) the elements of the design of BMs that inhibit a free fluctuation of prices for balancing energy, such as an inefficient procurement of balancing capacity, and regulated prices and pricing mechanisms not based on marginal pricing, which reduce the incentives for producers and demand-side to respond to instantaneous balancing needs.

The last part of the paper analysed the advantages and disadvantages of the new proposal for regulating the EIME, from the perspective of VRE, conventional generation and the power system as a whole. Although advantageous for the power system, some proposed Articles affect negatively the remuneration of VRE producers and conventional generation.

The implicit allocation of the cross-border capacity, aggregated bidding and market time unit of 15 minutes are aspects that can improve the effectiveness of power systems, by increasing the use of interconnectors (which, in turn, increase the use of the most cost-effective power plants in Europe), and decreasing forecast errors (and consequently the necessities of BMs, their prices and also the imbalance prices).

Giving balance responsibility for RES and allowing the participation of VRE in BMs, are aspects that can benefit European consumers. So, by start paying penalties (balance responsibility), the remuneration of VRE can decrease. However, the participation of VRE in BMs can reduce system imbalances and increase competition, which can increase VRE remuneration and decrease the use of conventional generation. These aspects can also benefit consumers by reducing the market prices of electricity and decreasing both the use of incentives to VRE and the capacity needs of conventional generation, which can be reflected in tariffs [62].

The adjustment of the gate closure of the DAM to a time closer to real-time seems to be deferred by EC. However, while VRE can be positively affected by this aspect, by increasing forecast accuracy, slower technologies (e.g., coal) that need around 6 to 8 hours of planning (if not retrofitted) can be negatively affected. This aspect can increase the operating costs of the system and is only advantageous for a gate closure six hours ahead or less (with no participation of slower technologies). Changing the market time unit to 15 minutes can also be problematic to slower technologies, since they can have to change their production every 15 minutes, and their slow ramp rates limit their flexibility. These measures can be advantageous for systems with more flexible generation and/or no dependency of slower technologies. However, taking into account the decarbonisation measures, a possible increase in the carbon tax and the retirement of most coal power plants, it is expected a reduced dependency of most countries on coal power plants, and thus such measures may become favourable to all countries of EU-28.

Chapter 4

Changing the Day-Ahead Gate

Closure to Wind Power Integration: A Simulation-Based Study¹

4.1 Authors

Hugo Algarvio, António Couto, Fernando Lopes, and Ana Estanqueiro

4.2 Abstract

Currently, in most European electricity markets, power bids are based on forecasts performed 12 to 36 hours ahead. Actual wind power forecast systems still lead to large errors, which may strongly impact electricity market outcomes. Accordingly, this article analyzes the impact of the wind power forecast uncertainty and the change of the day-ahead market gate closure on both the market-clearing prices and the outcomes of the balancing market. To this end, it presents a simulation-based study conducted with the help of an agent-based tool, called MATREM. The results support the following conclusion: a change in the gate closure to a time closer to real-time operation is beneficial to market participants and the energy system generally.

4.3 Keywords

Day-ahead market, Balancing market, Gate closure, Forecast uncertainty Wind power forecast, Agent-based simulation, The MATREM system.

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4.4 Introduction

Electricity market (EMs) are a complex and continuously evolving reality—new players are emerging and new strategic behaviors are gaining more active roles, meaning that researchers and practitioners did not yet solve the problems associated with this new reality [2, 164]. Chief among these problems are the ones related to the increase in non-dispatchable renewable generation, or variable renewable energy (VRE), such as solar and wind power. VRE is characterized by substantial investment costs, but near-zero marginal costs, and great variability, thus increasing the uncertainty of the net load. VRE is normally the marginal resource, since it is operated at maximum capacity (taking into account the weather conditions). These characteristics have a strong influence on the outcomes of energy markets, reducing market-clearing prices [40]. Accordingly, existing market designs should be analyzed to determine if they are still efficient to deal with high levels of VRE (see, e.g., [17, 40, 47]).

The question of a suitable day ahead market design for a better integration of VRE has been the subject of a great deal of research (see, e.g., [46, 237, 266, 267]). For the particular case of an effective gate closure, the potential solution discussed by the research community involves its adjustment to a time closer to the first hour of delivery. The main reason behind this adjustment is related to the forecast of renewable generation, which typically presents large errors for long time horizons, due to the stochastic nature of the atmosphere. Since the day-ahead market (DAM) closes typically at 12:00 p.m. (CET), the bids of wind power producers need to be performed through power forecasts computed at least 12 to 36 h ahead. Consequently, the adjustment of the gate closure is very important to enable a fair participation of VRE in EMs, since all energy producers (dispatchable and non-dispatchable) participate in the day-ahead market under the same rules. In case the energy production differs from the commitments resulting from the DAM, the differences should be balanced in the intraday market and/or the balancing market.

In 2014, the International Agency of Energy (IEA) presented a report about energy markets and renewable generation [51], scoring key EM features according to eight dimensions: non-VRE dispatch, VRE dispatch, dispatch interval, last schedule update, grid representation, interconnector management and system services definition and market. Half of these dimensions are directly related to the improvement of forecasts, namely dispatch interval, grid representation, interconnector management and last schedule update. IEA considers that all physical transactions should be performed through implicit auctions in a centralized pool without feed-in-tariffs (FiTs) or other incentives to renewable energy sources (RES), with an interval up to 10 min using updates up to 30 min before real-time operation. In addition, the reserve requirements should be computed stochastically, taking into account different scenarios for the share of VRE, and be remunerated through marginal pricing. Furthermore, dispatch intervals should be reduced—that is, should be as short as possible—to enable VRE producers to perform high accurate forecasts. Such market modifications can contribute to a new paradigm—a paradigm of VRE integration without FiTs, where VRE investors do not have a guaranteed return, being remunerated by the market price, and subject to the payment of penalties for their deviations.

In 2016, the European Union (EU) presented the “Clean Energy for all Europeans”, a package of

measures to promote the integration of renewable generation and to harmonize the European markets. In 2017, the EU presented a new proposal for regulating the pan-European market [35]. Article 7 considers that market operators should trade as close as possible to real-time operation, and no later than the gate closure of the intraday cross-zonal market. In [39], we presented an overview of the potential effects of the new EU proposal on the integration of renewable generation. In [63–65], we analyzed the impact of both high levels of renewable generation and significant forecast errors on the outcomes of the DAM. As a preliminary result, we conclude that a gate-closure closer to real time operation is beneficial to wind power producers.

This article builds on our previous work on market design. It considers a specific market design element, namely the gate closure, and investigates how changes in this element can better accommodate the increasing levels of renewable generation. Specifically, this article analyzes the impact of both wind power forecast uncertainty and a change in the gate closure of the DAM, from 12:00 p.m. to 2:00 p.m. (CET), on the day-ahead market prices and also on the outcomes of the balancing market. The proposed gate closure encompasses two perspectives. The first is related to technical requirements. In a power system with a significant number of conventional power plants, there is a need of a certain lead-time to adjust generation levels in a cost efficient manner [242]. The second perspective is related to the most reliable meteorological information to feed the wind power forecast systems.

This article presents a simulation-based study conducted with the help of an agent-based tool. Multi-agent systems (MAS) are a somewhat new area of study (see, e.g., [2, 56]). MAS are fundamentally coupled networks of computational agents that cooperate to resolve issues that are over their individual competence. Theoretically, MAS are an optimal fit for the distributed structure of liberalized energy markets. Accordingly, the work presented here makes use of a multi-agent simulator for competitive energy markets, called MATREM [2, 61] (MATREM stands for Multi-agent Trading in Electricity Markets). The following aspects are examined in the paper, in order to assess the benefits of postponing the gate closure of the day-ahead market:

- The influence of the forecast accuracy on the day-ahead market, namely on the level of prices, and price volatility;
- The influence of the forecast accuracy on the balancing reserve requirements.

In addition, the following questions are addressed in the paper:

- How can forecast improvements possibly reduce the total balancing reserve requirements?
- Which parts of the system cause the need for a balancing demand? In addition, what is the associated energy quantity?

The remainder of the article is structured as follows. Section 4.5 discusses the role of wind power forecasts in energy markets. Section 4.6 presents an overview of the MATREM system, focusing on the day-ahead and the balancing markets. Section 4.7 describes the method considered in the experimental work, highlighting the main tasks and the relationships between them. Section 4.8 presents the case study and discusses the simulation results. Lastly, in Section 4.9, some conclusions are drawn.

4.5 The Role of Wind Power Forecast in Day-Ahead and Balancing Markets

In order to maintain high standards of service quality, in particular in what regards the security of supply and the system robustness, the system operator must be aware of the current and future values of wind power for each area and connection points of the grid [268]. Currently, an efficient and safe operation of power systems [268, 269] requires that wind power production be well forecasted, and, when coupled with a load forecast system, both should enable the reduction of the need to balance the energy in the reserve markets, usually at high costs. During the past few years, numerous approaches have been developed for wind power forecast based on numerical weather prediction (NWP) models. Comprehensive reviews are presented in the literature (see, e.g., [240, 255]). NWP models, as the Fifth-Generation Penn State/NCAR Mesoscale Model (MM5) [270], resolve the formulations that rule the state of the atmosphere using numerical methodologies.

Notwithstanding the advances on NWP, systematic errors still persist due to the inherent chaotic behaviour of the atmosphere, in which minor errors, at an early stage, will increase in the deterministic chaotic system. For a long time horizon, this situation could result in a large deviation of the forecast when compared with the observation [271, 272]. This drawback can be partly explained by the physical formulation and parametrization of the atmosphere processes, the initial and boundary conditions (IC), among others. In fact, as indicated by several authors, one of the main sources of error and uncertainty, when numerical mesoscale models are applied, is derived from the ICs that feed the model, which are essentially atmospheric information provided by analysis/forecast products. Indeed, several authors have shown that these data have a crucial impact on the mesoscale model outcomes [273–275]. ICs are a three-dimensional set of meteorological data to force the boundary conditions of the model, and together with a terrain and roughness database, enable for conducting numerical physical simulations, for the region under analysis, in a time horizon comprising the day-ahead market. The ICs are obtained from global atmospheric models, such as the global forecast model system (GFS), with both a low time (6 h: at 12:00 a.m., 6:00 a.m., 12:00 p.m. and 6:00 p.m. UTC) and low spatial resolutions (e.g., 50 km) [256].

With the increasing levels of VRE generation in EMs, the underlying impact of wind power forecast into the power system has been explored by several authors. For instance, in [272], the authors studied the certainty gain effect of a wind power producer that participates in the day-ahead market, by delaying the forecasts according to NWP data availability. The results obtained demonstrate that NWP data availability determines the wind power forecast accuracy in the day-ahead market. In [17], by using a case study where wind parks are allowed to participate in the Portuguese tertiary reserve, the authors concluded that changing the market time unit from 1 h to 15 min reduces their imbalances about 10%. Thus, schedule updates as close as possible to real-time operation may strongly reduce the effect of forecast errors. However, the majority of the physical transactions of energy are performed in the day-ahead market (around 90% in Europe [33]), meaning that intraday markets (in Europe) and real-time markets (in the United States and Australia) have been less attractive, despite the fact that they allow

Figure 4.1: Global Forecast System (GFS) data availability and DAM design: **(top)**—actual; **(bottom)**—proposed in this work.

schedule updates closer to real-time operation. Balancing markets operate essentially in real time and have attractive prices, when compared to spot markets, but have less liquidity (smaller trading quantities). A study conducted in Denmark [214] concluded that the participation of wind power producers in balancing markets increases the wind energy value [312] only 4.5%. However, some preliminary results (see, e.g., [66]) indicated that a suitable day-ahead market design can contribute to a large increase in the wind energy value, mainly by reducing the penalties paid with deviations.

This article explores the adjustment of the DAM gate-closure considering wind power forecasts according to the typical availability of the IC meteorological data. Currently, the Portuguese wind farm producers may participate in the Iberian day-ahead market by considering forecasts based on meteorological information obtained 18 h before the first trading hour (see Figure 4.1). To accomplish the technical requirements, such as the unit commitment and the time needed to perform all the steps necessary to obtain the wind power forecasts, the proposed new gate closure time is set to 2:00 p.m. (considering the 12:00 p.m. IC conditions). This adjustment can be favourable to deal with the variability of stochastic energy sources [215, 276, 305].

4.6 The MATREM Simulator

The major components of the MATREM system include a day-ahead market, an intra-day market, a futures market, a balancing market, and a marketplace for negotiating the terms and conditions of “tailored” bilateral contracts [2, 61]. The system supports seven types of market entities: generating companies (GenCos), retailers (RetailCos), aggregators of VRE, coalitions of consumers, traditional consumers, market operators and system operators. All entities are modeled as software agents.

GenCo agents may own one power plant or a set of power plants with different technologies. Typically, they sell energy in the day-ahead market and the intra-day market—that is, the centralized markets—as well as in the bilateral market—the futures market. RetailCo agents buy energy from GenCos in the centralized markets as well as in the futures market, and subsequently, re-sell that energy to private

consumers (by signing bilateral contracts with them). Aggregators of VRE allow the participation of wind power producers and other types of VRE producers in the centralized markets. Coalitions of consumers are essentially alliances of end-use consumers with the goal of reducing their energy cost, typically by increasing their bargaining power. Large traditional consumers can trade energy in the centralized markets and the bilateral market, while small traditional consumers may ally into coalitions or establish private bilateral contracts with retailers.

The day-ahead market is cleared one day in advance—that is, in day D for each of the 24 h of the next day ($D + 1$), as illustrated in Figure 4.1. The intraday market is a short-run market involving several auction sessions. Typically, both markets operate according to the system marginal pricing algorithm, although MATREM also supports locational marginal pricing. Supply-side agents compete by submitting offers to sell energy while demand-side agents submit offers to buy energy. The system ranks the selling offers by increasing price and the buying offers by decreasing price, obtaining the supply and demand curves, respectively. Next, the market operator computes the market-clearing prices and sends the results to the system operator, who checks (in a preliminary way) the security constraints.

The stability of the power system is a task associated with the system operator. To this end, this agent needs to take access to reserve capacity for the provision of system services. MATREM considers three different types of reserve capacity: primary reserve (or frequency control reserve), secondary reserve (or fast active disturbance reserve), and tertiary reserve (or slow active disturbance reserve). Tertiary reserve has to be available within 15 min and its activation is carried out manually—this type of reserve is the most important for the work described here.

Tertiary reserve is traded by the system operator in a day-ahead tender. This agent defines the needs for up and downregulation, receives the offers from the balance responsible parties, and computes the market-clearing prices by using a simplified version of the system marginal pricing algorithm. Two different simulations are performed, one for computing the upregulation price, and another for determining the downregulation price. Following the clearing process, the system operator can perform an imbalance settlement process.

The futures market is an organized market for trading standard bilateral contracts. Such contracts are agreements by which the parties take on the obligation to buy or to sell electricity, in a standardized quantity and quality, on a predefined date and place, at a price agreed in the present. The bilateral marketplace allows private parties to negotiate the terms and conditions of tailored (or customized) long-term contracts, specifically forward contracts [81] and contracts for difference [328]. To this end, market participants are equipped with a model that handles two-party and multi-issue negotiation [112, 278].

4.7 Method

This work makes use of a diverse range of models and involves a set of tasks. Figure 4.2 depicts a flowchart of the approach considered, highlighting the main tasks and the relationships between them.

Figure 4.2: Overview of the methodology considered in this work, specifically the method and the main tasks related to the definition of the bids of the wind power producer (green) and the other market participants (light orange), as well as the procedure associated with the operation of the day-ahead market and the imbalance management process (light yellow).

4.7.1 Wind Power Forecast Approach

In the last few years, one of the key scientific research topics is the development of reliable forecasting systems. These systems are being widely employed in different fields, such as the prediction of consumer comfort based on temperature and humidity, electricity demand, wind speed and direction for onshore wind power, and also metocean conditions for offshore wind power, and irradiation for solar power (see, e.g., [279–282]).

For the particular case of wind power forecast systems, several techniques have been proposed in the literature (see, e.g., [283–288]). To support the participation of wind power producers in the DAM, existing wind power forecast systems are generally based on statistical post processing approaches coupled with mesoscale NWP outputs [255]. In this article, a K-nearest neighbour (K-NN) methodology is applied to provide the wind power forecasts. This statistical approach, also known as analogous forecast, has been applied by several authors due to its simplicity, effectiveness and non-parametric features [89, 289].

The K-NN methodology is considered a lazy learning methodology, since there is no need to (previously) build a model or a function. Instead, the methodology uses only similar situations from the historical data to forecast. This characteristic is especially suitable to forecast weather dependent variables, such as wind power. The K-NN methodology considers that atmospheric flow releases the same local impact. Consequently, and taking into account the atmospheric flow characteristics, where the meteorological weather patterns have a tendency to repeat over certain regions, from time to time, the wind power forecast production for a determined hour can be determined from a similar meteorological weather pattern from historical events. The K-NN technique has shown a high efficiency in forecasting phenomena where the synoptic variability is predominant, such as precipitation [290] and wind speed [291]. Currently, this technique has already been explored by several authors for forecasting wind power, showing good performance [254, 292, 293]. To estimate the degree of similarity with each historical

event, the Euclidean distance, with a trajectory matrix providing information regarding the state of the atmosphere on the preceding times, is the most common metric used in the wind forecast sector [293].

Due to a large number of degrees of freedom of the atmosphere, it is usual to apply a principal component analysis (PCA) approach to the input data. This procedure allows to filter atmospheric perturbation that represents only background noise [272]. To assist in this filtering process, the North criterion [294] was applied, allowing to identify the appropriate number of principal components (PCs) to be used in each meteorological parameter input.

Figure 4.3 depicts the flowchart of the K-NN methodology applied in this work. In order to calibrate the forecasting methodology, sensitivity studies were performed, using two years of real wind power data from a set of wind parks located in the central region of Portugal. These sensitive tests comprise the suitable number of K nearest neighbours, the size of the trajectory matrix and the selection of the most adequate meteorological parameters. After some tests, the most adequate configuration of the forecast methodology was to set K to 10 using a trajectory matrix with a lag of 3 h, composed by the first three PCs of the longitudinal component of the wind, wind speed, and atmospheric pressure. Thus, the deterministic wind power forecast is based on the average value of the ten historic events.

The normalized root mean square error (NRMSE) represents the quadratic difference between the estimated value (based on the proposed methodologies), and was normalized by the nominal capacity of wind park: P^{nom} . The correlation r is used in statistics to measure how strong the relationship is between two variables, in this case, the observed power P_t^{obs} and the forecast power P_t^{for} . The F Test is used to verify the statistical significance between the deviations associated with the two different gate-closures considered in this work. Mathematically, the previous parameters are defined by the following equations:

$$NRMSE [\%] = \sqrt{\frac{\sum (P_t^{obs} - P_t^{for})^2}{N}} \times \frac{1}{P^{nom}} \quad (4.1)$$

$$r = \frac{cov(P_t^{obs}, P_t^{for})}{\sqrt{var(P_t^{obs}) var(P_t^{for})}} \quad (4.2)$$

$$F = \frac{var(P_t^{obs} - P_t^{for1})^2}{var(P_t^{obs} - P_t^{for2})^2} \quad (4.3)$$

4.7.2 Selection of Representative Days

The underlying goal of choosing representative days is to statistically detect the most typical wind power daily patterns and, at the same time, clustering together days that exhibit identical patterns. This procedure allows for: (i) feeding the MATREM simulator without resorting to extensively time-consuming simulations, and (ii) assessing, for instance, the typical profiles that can jeopardize the wind power producer revenues enabling for adopting measures to mitigate their risk exposure. The identification of representative days is a suitable approach widely employed to increase the knowledge of a deter-

Figure 4.3: Wind power forecasts methodology based on NWP data coupled with a K-NN approach.

mined parameter allowing the creation of decision support systems (e.g., the classification of the type of profile of electricity customers [295]). A K-medoids clustering algorithm [88] is used in this work to find the representative days based on the daily observed wind power profile for the wind parks considered. This technique allows arranging the input data with similar characteristics into clusters in order to achieve the most representative daily profile. With this step, it is possible to identify (in a statistical way) statistically independent patterns from the data that can be related to physical processes. Clustering algorithms are unsupervised learning processes typically applied to find and split the data according to the similarity among the observations, in a way that is always closer to the elements of the same cluster, and dissimilar among the remaining clusters [88, 246].

The main advantages of the K-medoids algorithm, when compared to others non-hierarchical clustering algorithms (e.g., the K-means algorithm) are: (1) to be more robust to noise and outliers by using the median values, and (2) to allow for selecting data points as centres (medoids) [246]. The K-medoids technique used in this work is classified as a non-hierarchical clustering algorithm, allowing to group the data into K clusters. The suitable K, i.e., the number of clusters, is predetermined through the Calinski–Harabasz (CH) criterion [248].

The wind power input matrix ($X_{d,t}$) for the clustering algorithm is defined as follows:

$$X_{d,t} = \begin{pmatrix} Z_{1,1} & Z_{1,2} & \cdots & Z_{1,t} \\ Z_{2,1} & Z_{2,2} & \cdots & Z_{2,t} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ Z_{d,1} & Z_{d,2} & \cdots & Z_{d,h} \end{pmatrix} \quad (4.4)$$

where t represents the wind power observed during a predetermined hour of day d during the period 2009–2010.

4.7.3 Measures of Economic Results

In this section, the formulation used to compare the results between the 12:00 p.m. scenario (hereafter designated as the *base case*) and 2:00 p.m. scenario (hereafter designated as the *upgraded case*) is presented. The total remuneration (per hour) of the wind power producers is as follows:

$$R_t = \sum_{t=0}^{23} P_t^{bid} C_t^{dayahead} + \begin{cases} (P_t^{obs} - P_t^{bid}) C_t^{updeviation}, & \text{for } P_t^{bid} < P_t^{obs} \\ (P_t^{obs} - P_t^{bid}) C_t^{downdeviation}, & \text{for } P_t^{bid} > P_t^{obs} \end{cases} \quad (4.5)$$

where:

- $C_t^{dayahead}$ is the day-ahead price at hour t ;
- $C_t^{updeviation}$ and $C_t^{downdeviation}$ are the up and down deviation costs, respectively.

It is important to note that $P_t^{bid} C_t^{dayahead}$ is the part consisting of the remuneration obtained from the day-ahead. The other part consists of the remuneration obtained from the deviations. Therefore, the total remuneration R_d and average remuneration \bar{R}_d for a specific day d are as follows:

$$R_d = \sum_{t=0}^{23} R_t \quad (4.6)$$

$$\bar{R}_d = \frac{R_d}{\sum_{t=0}^{23} P_t} \quad (4.7)$$

The average remuneration obtained in the day-ahead market $\bar{R}_d^{dayahead}$ is defined as follows:

$$\bar{R}_d^{dayahead} = \frac{\sum_{t=0}^{23} P_t^{bid} C_t^{dayahead}}{\sum_{t=0}^{23} P_t^{bid}} \quad (4.8)$$

In addition, the average remuneration obtained by considering the deviations $\bar{R}_d^{deviation}$ is as follows:

$$\bar{R}_d^{deviation} = \begin{cases} \frac{\sum_{t=0}^{23} (P_t^{obs} - P_t^{bid}) C_t^{updeviation}}{\sum_{t=0}^{23} (P_t^{obs} - P_t^{bid})}, & \text{for } P_t^{bid} < P_t^{obs} \\ \frac{\sum_{t=0}^{23} (P_t^{obs} - P_t^{bid}) C_t^{downdeviation}}{\sum_{t=0}^{23} (P_t^{obs} - P_t^{bid})}, & \text{for } P_t^{bid} > P_t^{obs} \end{cases} \quad (4.9)$$

With these formulae, it is possible to compute the average wind power value, the energy transacted in the tertiary reserve market, and the tertiary reserve cost for both scenarios. Both the reserve cost and the electric system levelized cost are computed by taking into account the occurrence of each representative day and the traded energy. In order to assess the gain effect regarding the proposed

Table 4.1: KPIs considered in this work.

KPI	Objective	Formulation
Increase in the wind power value to the market	Increase the remuneration of wind power producers in the market	Equation (4.5)
Increase in the forecast accuracy	Reduce the forecast error	Equation (4.4)
Reduction of total control reserve by wind power forecast improvements	Reduce the balance needs of the tertiary reserve	Equations (4.1) and (4.2)
Reduction of the tertiary reserve costs	Reduce the balance costs of the tertiary reserve	Tertiary reserve simulation
Reduction of total operating costs in the electricity system by forecast improvements	Reduce the system costs with the day-ahead market and the tertiary reserve	Day-ahead market and tertiary reserve simulations

adaptation of the gate closure of the day-ahead market, several key performance indicators (KPIs) are defined (see Table 4.1).

4.8 The Case Study

This section describes a case study to analyse the effect of wind power forecasts errors on the outcomes of the DAM. The following two scenarios are considered: (i) a base scenario, where the DAM closes at 12:00 p.m. (the bids of the wind power producers are based on a wind forecast performed 18 to 42 h ahead), and (ii) an updated scenario, where the DAM closes at 2:00 p.m. (the bids of WPPs are based on an updated forecast performed 12 to 36 h ahead).

4.8.1 Software Agents and Wind Power Profiles

This study makes use of data published by the Iberian electricity market (MIBEL) and involves the simulation of the day-ahead market prices as well as the balancing market prices. Market participants are modeled as software agents, defined with the help of the MATREM system. Since the normal operation of the daily market of MIBEL involves a number of bids on the order of thousands for a particular hour, there is a need to make some simplifications related to the number of software agents, in order to avoid a large computational complexity. Accordingly, the main agents considered in the study are as follows: a market operator (S1), a system operator (S2), twelve producers (supply-side agents) and four retailers (demand-side agents). Table 4.2 presents the characteristics of the supply-side agents. The wind aggregator (agent P_1) represents the Portuguese wind farms.

It is important to note that the detection of violations related to the interconnection constraints between Portugal and Spain leads to a process of market splitting, resulting in different price areas for Portugal and Spain. After a careful examination, we concluded that this situation applies for some hours

Figure 4.4: Wind energy typical profile (a) and representability of each wind power profile during the 2-year period of the study (b).

of the days under consideration. In practice, this means two sets of simulation for each hour of operation, one for Portugal and another for Spain. However, for convenience, and in the interests of simplicity, the day-ahead market is cleared for Portugal only.

The forecast methodology is deterministic and uses the following: (i) numerical weather prediction data outputs (see Section 4.7), and (ii) observed data for a set of wind farms during the period 2009–2010. The wind farms have a nominal capacity of 250 MW (10% of the Portuguese installed capacity, in 2010). This value is upscaled to 2500 MW to obtain a meaningful impact on the market results. The observed wind power profiles are depicted in Figure 4.4a. The representability of each wind power profile is also shown in Figure 4.4b.

The analysis of Figure 4.4 supports the consideration that the Portuguese wind farms are located in a mountain region, since several wind power profiles show the typical features of wind speed in such a region (although with different intensity)—that is, due to the thermal stratification and local effects [296], the highest wind speed is associated with the nocturnal period. Moreover, the most common wind power profile shows a reduced production during all day. On the other hand, profile 2 is associated with a high level of wind power production, which occurs during the passage of severe meteorological phenomena,

Table 4.2: Producer agents (software agents) and their key characteristics.

Agent	Country	Technology	Maximum Capacity (MW)	Marginal Cost (€/MWh)
P1	Portugal	Wind	2500	0
P2	Portugal	Renewable mix	2000	0
P3	Portugal	Hydroelectricity	4500	[30; 60]
P4	Portugal	Coal	1800	≈30
P5	Portugal	Combined Cycle Gas	3000	≈55
P6	Portugal	Fuel oil	2000	≈70
P7	Spain	Renewable mix	30,000	0
P8	Spain	Hydroelectricity	16,500	[30; 60]
P9	Spain	Coal	10,000	≈30
P10	Spain	Nuclear	7500	≈30
P11	Spain	Combined Cycle Gas	22,000	≈55
P12	Spain	Fuel oil	4000	≈70

Figure 4.5: Wind power forecast deviations at 12:00 p.m. (base case, **left**) and at 2:00 p.m. (updated case, **right**).

as the cyclone systems [297]. This profile shows the lowest number of occurrences.

4.8.2 Wind Power Forecast Deviations

Figure 4.5 depicts the wind power forecast deviations (forecast minus observed production) for the seven representative days, at 12:00 p.m. (base case, left) and 2:00 p.m. (updated case, right). The figure shows that the wind power forecast deviations at 12:00 p.m. have an absolute value that is almost twice that of the deviations at 2:00 p.m. Moreover, wind power fluctuations are considerably higher in the base scenario. For instance, the uncertainty in profile 2 ranges between -200 and 1700 MW.

Table 4.3 depicts the forecast results regarding both the NRMSE and the correlation values between the two scenarios. The most significant improvement was observed in profile 2. This profile, usually associated to extreme weather conditions, shows a strong improvement in the correlation and the NRMSE values. The link between wind power variability as well as the uncertainty with extreme weather conditions was described by several authors [255, 257, 297–299], who demonstrated that larger errors in the wind power forecast are expected to occur during severe weather conditions with strong dynamics (e.g., storms and cold fronts) when compared with weather conditions associated with stationary systems (e.g., anticyclonic systems). For a 0.05 significance level, the critical value is 2.01, which means that comparing both deviations (see Figure 4.5), exist statistically differences in all profiles, except in profile 6 (see Table 4.3).

Profile 4 also shows a strong improvement in the wind power forecast for the upgrade scenario. Profile 5 shows the lowest NRMSE amelioration that can be explained with the capabilities to obtain a reliable forecast during calm wind speed conditions [298, 299]. Consequently, results from Table 4.3 highlighted the fact that the data considered about the ICs strictly define the wind power forecast errors. Thus, as expected, since the most up-to-date information on the state of the atmosphere is used, postponing the gate closure can strongly reduce the uncertainty of the bids that the wind power producers submit to the day-ahead market.

4.8.3 Simulation Results

Impact of Wind Power Forecast on Market Outcomes

In a preliminary attempt to understand the relation of the aforementioned wind power forecast uncertainty results with the market outcomes, we observed that the deviations are essentially positive in most of the representative days (day seven is the exception), meaning that the forecasts normally underestimate the wind power values. From the point-of-view of wind power producers, this situation (underestimation) can be profitable, since wind power is offered at a price around 0€ in the day-ahead market, and thus an underestimation forecast will increase the market price. On the other hand, an overestimation forecast can decrease the day-ahead market price, decreasing the wind energy value. Therefore, it can be concluded that an underestimation of the wind power production in the day-ahead market (shortage forecast) overestimates the importance of the wind power and also gives an extra amount to the supply-side agents (by increasing the market-clearing price). On the other hand, an overestimation of the wind power production (excess forecast) undervalues the wind power value. Moreover, due to the payment of penalties in the balancing market, the latter situation can lead to a drastic reduction in the revenues of wind power producers. Thus, an underestimation of wind power production can be more profitable for wind power producers.

The results of the simulations for both the base scenario (12:00 p.m.) and the updated scenario (2:00 p.m.) are presented in Tables 4.4 and 4.5, respectively. In both tables, details regarding the outcomes of postponing the market closing time by two hours are also provided. As mentioned previously, the sum of the wind power deviations at 12:00 p.m. is almost twice the deviations associated with 2:00 p.m., and on some days it is more than twice the amount, such as the 3rd and 4th representative days. The results also show that the underestimation of wind power production can increase the market price and, as discussed previously, can overvalue the wind power. This conclusion takes into account the fact that the average day-ahead remuneration is higher at 12:00 p.m., in almost all days, excluding the 7th representative day. In this representative day, the overestimation of wind power production leads to an undervaluation of the wind power value. This behavior can also be observed in the revenue deviations results. In fact, when both day-ahead and revenue deviations are positive, an underestimation of wind power is obtained. Consequently, power producers receive a positive revenue for the extra energy at the real-time operation (normally less than in the day-ahead market, due to penalties). When the

Table 4.3: Correlation and NRMSE between the observed and forecasted wind power and F value of the wind power deviations for each scenario and wind power profile.

Parameter Difference	Simulation	Wind Power Profile						
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Correlation	Base Scenario	0.91	-0.35	0.72	0.54	0.79	0.78	0.47
	Upgrade Scenario	0.95	0.27	0.89	0.86	0.92	0.88	0.71
NRMSE (%)	Base Scenario	4.23	19.46	10.72	12.45	2.73	5.99	8.94
	Upgrade Scenario	2.87	12.85	3.93	5.52	2.10	3.90	5.61
F	Both Scenarios	2.07	3.39	2.61	2.81	2.37	1.94	3.85

Table 4.4: Key results for the base scenario (12:00 p.m. scenario).

Profile	Power Forecast 12 h (Base Scenario)						
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Day-ahead energy bid (GWh)	22.01	25.93	22.18	14.37	10.58	8.06	12.61
Day-ahead Remuneration (k€)	767.21	951.6	885.58	529.22	389.25	317.03	525.92
Average Day-ahead Rem. (€/MWh)	34.85	36.7	39.93	36.82	36.81	39.31	41.72
Real time deviations (MWh)	4.45	21.86	11.61	13.26	2.55	5.5	8.78
Deviations Revenue (k€)	-143.6	460.33	226.29	317.29	9.94	98.66	-527.7
Average Remuneration (€/MWh)	29.94	30.03	32.91	30.63	33.75	31.75	-0.46
Total Remuneration (k€)	623.62	1411.9	111.19	846.51	399.19	415.69	-1.77

revenue deviations are negative, this normally means an overestimation of wind power production when compared with the forecast, so there will be a need to pay a value higher than the day-ahead price.

One of the key parameters that can be used to compare the base scenario with the updated scenario is the average remuneration of the wind power producers. Considering both tables, it can be seen that, in the updated scenario, the wind value (average remuneration of the wind power) is always higher, and the proposed market design element seems even more relevant when a wind power forecast overestimation occurs. For instance, for the 7th representative day, the average remuneration of the wind power producer is negative, in the base case. Therefore, if hypothetically wind power producers are active players in the market, with the current market design, when the day-ahead market prices are lower than the deviation prices, the producers who have an energy shortage (when compared to their energy forecast bids) may have a negative average remuneration.

Now, taking into account the representability of each wind power profile during the two years of data, it is possible to compute the average wind energy value, the energy transacted in the tertiary reserve market, and the tertiary reserve costs, among other key parameters, for both the 12:00 p.m. and the 2:00 p.m. scenarios (see Table 4.6). The results in the Table show that the upgraded case leads to better results in almost all key indicators (the exception is the reserve cost).

Also, the results suggest that a reduction in the day-ahead market prices, due to a reduction in the forecast errors (NRMSE), leads to an increase in the wind power producers revenues, by allowing for reducing their losses associated with the deviation penalties. With a reduction of forecast errors, the quantity of reserve required to compensate the deviations decreases. However, both the reserve

Table 4.5: Key results for the updated scenario (2:00 p.m. scenario).

Profile	Power Forecast 2:00 p.m. (Updated Scenario)						
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Day-ahead energy bid (GWh)	20.62	32.48	30.83	22.59	13.41	10.26	9.83
Day-ahead Remuneration (k€)	699.61	1173.3	1187.7	784.42	488.76	400.31	414.5
Average Day-ahead Rem. (€/MWh)	33.93	36.12	38.53	34.73	36.44	39.03	42.17
Real-time deviations (MWh)	2.76	14.59	3.78	5.2	1.75	3.82	6.01
Deviations Revenue (k€)	-45.3	330.82	48.19	124.78	-81.56	43.28	-355.6
Average Remuneration (€/MWh)	31.42	31.99	36.58	32.9	34.43	33.88	15.41
Total Remuneration (k€)	654.31	1504.1	123.59	909.2	407.2	443.6	58.94

levelized cost and the reserve cost increased. These results are associated with a decrease in the system requirements for down reserve (see the reserve direction parameter). In this way, the system operator receives an inferior remuneration from the down reserve, which leads to an increase of the

Table 4.6: Average values of the key parameters under evaluation per day.

Key Parameters	Simulations	
	12:00 p.m. (Base Scenario)	2:00 p.m. (Updated Scenario)
Wind Energy Value (€/MWh)	28.46	31.69
Forecast NRMSE (%)	8.03	4.52
Reserve Use (GWh)	11.1	6.23
Reserve Direction (GWh)	-7.44	-3.83
Reserve Costs (M€)	-0.1	-0.04
Reserve Levelized Cost (€/MWh)	-7.26	-3.83
Down Reserve Price (€/MWh)	20.07	25.7
Day-ahead Market Cost (M€)	18.75	18.63
Day-ahead Market Prices (€/MWh)	38.6	37.97
Day-ahead Market Energy (GWh)	487.71	491.31
Electric System Cost (M€)	18.65	18.58
Electric System Lev. Cost (€/MWh)	38.84	38.12

Table 4.7: Key performance indicators (KPIs).

KPIs (%)	Changing from 12:00 p.m. to 2:00 p.m.
Increase in the wind power value to the market	11.34
Increase in the forecast accuracy	43.71
Reduction of total control reserve by forecast improvements in wind power	43.87
Reduction of the tertiary reserve costs	-56.25
Reduction of total operating costs in the electricity system by forecast improvements	16.46

down reserve price. This increase, together with a decrease in the down reserve utilization and the day-ahead market prices, will negatively affect the revenue of the power plants that bid at the tertiary reserve market. This behavior is associated with a reduction of the remuneration of wind power producers from the day-ahead market since they need to pay a high price for the down reserve, for a small quantity of energy.

Quantifying the Gain Effect of the Proposed Market Design Change

The KPIs defined in Section 4.7 enable for quantifying the gain effect by setting the gate closure of the day-ahead market to 2:00 p.m., instead of 12:00 p.m. (see Table 4.7). The change of the day-ahead market closing time brings benefits to the system in general, with a reduction around 16.5% in the total costs. As stated before, the wind power producers and the demand-side players benefit from this change. Wind power producers gain from selling the same quantity at a higher net price (market price with fewer penalties). The demand-side players gain from buying a similar quantity of electricity at a lower price. The system operator benefits from using less the reserve market to balance the system (a reduction around 44%) and also receives the lowest revenue (less 56%) from the down reserve market (part of the tertiary reserve market), which means that the agents that deviate will pay higher penalties. Notwithstanding, the power producers that buy energy from the tertiary reserve market (down reserve) decrease their revenues, by having less energy to buy at a higher price.

A comparison of the results shown in Table 4.7 with the main results presented by the literature (see Section 4.5) allows us to conclude that postponing the gate-closure of the day-ahead market only two hours seems to be a change of market design that can bring large benefits to power systems generally.

4.9 Conclusions

The article analyzed a change in the gate closure of the day-ahead market to deal with the uncertainty of variable generation. Specifically, it considered the adjustment of the day-ahead market closing time from 12:00 p.m. (currently in use in most of the European electricity markets) to 2:00 p.m. (CET). To test this adjustment, a case study based on real data from a set of aggregated wind parks in Portugal, and

also data from the supply-side (producers) and demand-side (retailers buying electricity for the end-use consumers) of the Iberian Market (MIBEL), as an approximation of the entire system, was established.

Wind power forecast data were obtained using a K-NN approach based on data from a NWP model. The day-ahead market was simulated using the system marginal pricing algorithm for seven representative days, taking into account two scenarios: gate closure of the day-ahead market set to 12:00 p.m. (base case) and to 2:00 p.m. (updated case). The seven representative wind power production days enable: (i) to simulate only the most common typical wind power production days in the region under study, and (ii) to identify the wind power profiles that can jeopardise the revenues of the wind power producers or can pose serious challenges to transmission system operators.

From a wind power forecast perspective, the results show that some wind power profiles clearly benefit from a change in the market design. Regarding the electricity market perspective, the results show that the change of the day-ahead market closing time to 2:00 p.m. benefits the wind power producers at both a technical and financial level by decreasing the forecast errors and increasing the revenues. The consumers can also potentially take advantage of this change due to a potential reduction in the overall system costs, which may allow a reduction of the electricity tariffs. The system operator benefits from a reduction in the wind park forecast errors, by reducing the requirements to maintain the production/demand balance (technical benefit), requiring less energy from the tertiary reserve market. However, they also receive less money from the downregulation (financial loss), which means that the agents that deviate will need to pay higher penalties to compensate this loss. The power producers that bid at the down reserve market have a loss due to a decrease in the system requirements for this type of reserve, i.e., the system operator requires less down reserve quantity to balance the system, which increases the price of this market.

The results presented in this work highlight that electricity markets with high shares of VRE could benefit from DAMs with a gate closure closer to real-time operation, due to improvements in the forecast accuracy. The full integration of wind power in markets can be possible with substantial changes to the current market designs, especially in power systems with a high share of VRE integration, as expected in the forthcoming years with the society decarbonization.

Chapter 5

Participation of Wind Power Producers in Day-ahead and Balancing Markets: An Overview and a Simulation-based Study¹

5.1 Authors

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5.2 Abstract

At present, a harmonized pan-European electricity market (EM) is a close reality. While in day-ahead markets (DAMs) the harmonization is at an advanced stage, in balancing markets (BMs) still exist some challenging issues, notably the remuneration of imbalances: some countries have simple and clear methods, but others consider complex methods that do not attract the participation of variable renewable energy (VRE). The participation of VRE in BMs is technically feasible, although with some restrictions to guarantee security and stability, and thus the economic attractiveness of these markets should increase in order to enable full integration of VRE without feed-in-tariffs or other incentives. This article presents an overview of EMs, focusing on European BMs, and also investigates the benefits of the participation of wind power producers (WPPs) in BMs at both economic and technical levels. In particular, the article presents a new strategy allowing WPPs to bid in BMs. It also presents a study involving four scenarios, where WPPs participate in: (i) the DAM (baseline scenario), (ii) the DAM and the automatic-activated frequency restoration reserve market, (iii) the DAM and manually-activated FRR (mFRR) market and (iv) the DAM and a 15-minute mFRR market. The simulations are performed with the agent-based system

¹[17], WIREs Energy and Environment 8(5):e343, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1002/wene.343>

MATREM (for Multi-Agent TRading in Electricity Markets). For the last three scenarios, the results indicate an increase around 6% in the wind energy value to the market, a decrease of 12% in the total reserve used, and a decrease around 16% in the costs from the BM.

5.3 Keywords

Agent-based system, Balancing Markets, Simulation-based Study, Strategic Bidding, Wind Power Producers.

5.4 Introduction

The penetration of variable renewable energy (VRE) in power supply systems is progressively increasing, while the penetration of conventional generation is decreasing. To ensure that the power supply continue functioning reliably and in a cost-effective way, electricity markets (EMs) should be adapted to this new paradigm (see, e.g., Lopes:18ba). Contrary to conventional generation, appropriately designed to control the power output, VRE units are non-dispatchable and dependent from stochastic weather conditions. Since these conditions can be forecasted, the possible contributions from VRE can be considered schedulable, although with uncertainties associated with forecast errors. In order to minimize such uncertainties, the input of VRE should be scheduled as soon as possible to the real-time operation.

The current EMs were not designed to receive high penetrations of VRE, and thus should be analysed and adjusted to deal with the variability of stochastic sources, in order to avoid the payment of balancing services, typically at high costs [44]. The harmonization of European EMs, which is already progressing, should be promoted to minimise costs and ensure fair conditions to market participants [30]. In 2017, the European Commission (EC) presented a new proposal for regulating the European Internal Market of Electricity [35].

Regarding the day-ahead markets (DAMs), the next step of the harmonization is probably to shorten the trading periods [313]. Also, sloping schedules (instead of flat) could be used to avoid the need of balancing reserves [309]. And a major challenge for the design of future DAMs is to hedge tail risks, ensuring a power capacity adequacy. Existing or new market products can serve as an example for this purpose. In the intraday markets, there are still some issues to be addressed in order to achieve a full harmonization, namely the time unit (between 15 min and 1 hour), the gate closure (between 5 min and 3 hours), the market coupling (only possible in few countries) and the trading type (continuous or not) [33].

For balancing markets (BMs)², a pan-European harmonization is still in its infancy. Currently, only Norway, Sweden, Finland and Denmark have a common manually-activated frequency restoration reserve (mFRR) market. This lack of harmonization is mainly due to the importance of BMs for a secure and stable operation of the National electricity grids and the necessity of interventions by transmission

²The term "balancing market" is used in a broad sense, refereeing to the automatic-activated and manually activated frequency restoration reserve markets.

system operators (TSOs), and also because of the differences between the adopted schemes for procuring balancing energy in both automatic-activated FRR (aFRR) and mFRR markets in Europe [29]. The European Network of Transmission System Operators for Electricity (ENTSO-E) has already elaborated a definition of product requirements and a set of rules for a cross-border market for BMs. However, it is necessary to uniform some aspects, such as bidding times, tendering and remuneration rules, and minimum bid sizes [15, 16].

There is a growing literature on the participation of VRE in BMs. Such participation may increase the economic value of wind³ and decrease both the market prices and the needs of BMs. In this way, and although with some restrictions, Spain [213], Germany [220] and Denmark [224] have already allowed the participation of wind power producers (WPPs) in the mFRR market.

The remainder of this paper presents an overview of the participation of VRE in BMs, analyses the technical feasibility of the participation of WPPs in BMs, and proposes a new strategy for WPPs bidding in BMs. Additionally, the paper presents a simulation-based study on the participation of WPPs in both the DAM and the BM, discusses the results obtained and compares them with other results presented in the literature.

5.5 European Electricity Markets: Characteristics and Rules

This section describes some of the most important key features of the main European markets and some important aspects related to the evolution of the European EMs towards a pan European market.

5.5.1 Day-ahead and Intraday Markets

With the harmonization, the European DAMs close at 12:00 PM (CET time), 12–37 hours before the scheduled physical delivery. The trading is based on an implicit auction, where price and quantity are calculated during day (d) before the day of operation (d+1), using a hybrid algorithm called Euphemia [11]. The auction is based on simple and complex bids from producers and consumers, and takes into account physical constraints of cross-zonal capacity [10]. By setting prices and quantities for each bidding zone, the auction also defines the schedules between bidding zones. TSOs rely on the market clearing results to plan the day of operation. Intraday markets may involve auctions relatively close (2-3 hours) to real-time, or operate continuously, typically using the pay as bid as the pricing method.

5.5.2 Balancing markets

The deviations from the schedule (resulting from DAMs) need to be compensated in BMs, involving the payment of imbalance prices (or penalties). Clearly, the process for determining imbalance prices differs from market to market, varying from a simple and clear method (in the Nordic countries) to a complex method (in Portugal and Germany) (see, e.g., [66]). To envisage a pan-European BM, with clear rules

³Mills and Wiser [312] classify the economic value of wind as the sum of four variables: the market value of energy, the capacity value, the forecast error and the ancillary services value

for all power producers, where WPPs pay for their deviations, a clear and general method should be adopted [29].⁴

In most European power systems, the frequency reserves are classified as follows [16]:

- Frequency controlled reserve (FCR) or primary control reserve;
- Automatic-activated frequency restoration reserve (aFRR), secondary reserve or fast active disturbance reserve;
- Manually-activated frequency restoration reserve (mFRR), tertiary reserve or slow active disturbance reserve.

The control reserve services are mandatory and imposed by ENTSO-E. Operationally, each TSO has the responsibility of guaranteeing the power reserve values for these services within the control zone, based on ENTSO-E requirements. Table 5.1 summarizes the most important characteristics of the three types of control reserve. Frequency controlled reserve (FCR) is the first to be activated, after grid disturbances, incidents or imbalances between production and consumption, that result in a frequency deviation in relation to the programmed value (50 Hz for the European grid). It should be activated up to 15 seconds (maximum) and the disturbances need to be controlled in seconds (normally 30 seconds). FCR is a mandatory and non-remunerated system service for all generators connected to the grid, or that influence it, and who have technical capability for a fast response. The allocated generators need to provide 5% of their nominal power in stable conditions. Currently, this service is mainly supported by hydropower generation [219].

Automatic-activated frequency restoration reserve should be activated up to 30 seconds (maximum), taking up to 15 minutes (900 seconds) to be finalized, replacing FCR. It also restores the grid frequency to the programmed value. Taking into account the programmed size of aFRR (power band), the TSO defines the band needs for every hour.

Manually-activated frequency restoration reserve is primarily used to free up and/or complement aFRR. The TSO is responsible to activate this reserve, which allows to solve long-term active-power deviations, by implying changes in the following [33]: i) generation or load on a contractual market or regulatory basis (depending on the different schemes used for procuring balancing energy activated from mFRR), and ii) the generation/load schedule. It should be fully activated within 15 minutes and can continue active for a long period of time (hours), freeing up the FCR and aFRR. TSOs define the needs of mFRR (capacity) based on the deviations that both FCR and aFRR cannot deal with.

In the aFRR and mFRR products, TSOs typically define schedules for blocks of 15 minutes. In the corresponding markets, an auction for every hour of the day (or blocks of various hours) is carried out, and the technically capable generators are allowed to make bids. The auction criterion aims to determine

⁴ENTSO-E presents the legislation about the imbalances settlements (ENTSO-E, 2014). In particular, Art. 62 defines that each TSO shall settle all imbalances with each Balance Responsible Party (BRP) pursuant to Art. 60. Furthermore, each TSO shall settle each Imbalance Settlement Period pursuant to Art. 21, against the appropriate imbalance price (pursuant to Art. 61). Art. 60 defines several aspects involved in the determination of imbalances, including the final position, the allocated volumes, and the imbalance adjustment for each BRP and for each imbalance settlement period and area. Art. 21 defines the targets for imbalance settlement. Art. 61 considers that each TSO defines rules to calculate the imbalance price to be paid by the BRP to the TSO.

Table 5.1: Comparison of the most typical types of balancing control options.

Key Characteristics	FCR	aFRR	mFRR
Target	Frequency	Area Control Error and frequency	Current and expected level of aFRR activation
Minimum offer	±1 MW	5 MW	5 MW
Activation	Decentralized via frequency measurement	Centralized (TSO); IT* signal (Automatic gain control)	Centralized (TSO); phone/ IT* signal
Activation speed	15 s	30 s	15 min
Response time	30 s	15 min or less; direct	Hours or less; direct or scheduled
Typical Suppliers	Synchronized generators, (large consumers)	Synchronized generators, stand-by hydro plants , large consumers	Synchronized and fast-starting stand-by generators , large consumers
Reserved capacity	3000 MW (Continental Europe)	Determined by national TSOs	Determined by national TSOs

the lowest capacity price (aFRR market) and the lowest energy price (mFRR market), based on marginal pricing, pay-as bid or other pricing methods.

5.6 Participation of Wind Power in Balancing Markets

5.6.1 Operational Capability: Analysis and discussion

This section discusses the participation of WPPs in BMs, placing emphasis on the operational capabilities to support the frequency support provision.

Currently, WPPs respond to curtailment requests of transmission system operators according to the ramp rates given in the Network Codes of each TSO. As an example, consider the following possibilities of active power curtailment [314]:

- Germany, with a ramp rate of 10% of grid connection capacity per minute.
- Ireland, with a ramp rate of 1-30 MW per minute.
- Nordic Grid Code, with a ramp rate of 10% of the rated power per minute.
- Denmark, with a ramp rate of 10-100% of the rated power per minute.

Accordingly, various control methods can be used to provide very fast responses. Notice that such responses are limited by the rate of changing thresholds of reference power (the electrical torque, which is typically 0.4–0.6 p.u., according to the wind turbine size and type) [315]. Furthermore, as discussed by Attya, Dominguez-Garcia and Anaya-Lara [229], the different time responses from each control method may have a strong impact on the dynamics of the power system frequency.

The technical literature discusses four key approaches involving different control methods to secure a power surge (overpower) from a wind turbine during frequency deviations: (i) the kinetic energy extraction, (ii) the over-speeding, (iii) the balance de-loading, and (iv) the delta-de-loading [229].

Despite the existence of different approaches, the capability of WPPs to provide balancing services is strongly related to the accuracy of wind power forecasts [29]. Also, it is clear that WPPs should meet set-points as precisely as possible, and also react to set-point changes as quickly as possible. Therefore, in the new paradigm of WPPs participating in BMs, WPPs may need to follow a schedule (involving all energy traded in both spot and bilateral markets). They should be able to respond to short run variations of the schedules requested by TSOs. Brauns et al. [309] show that WPPs are capable of accomplishing schedules. The authors performed a test where a particular WPP reduces around 70% of the optimal production to comply with a specific schedule, taking around 15 seconds to accomplish it. This situation leads to a large quantity of wasted energy concerning the available resources. So, to avoid wasting energy, WPPs should perform aggregated bids in BMs, as in Spain [213], or bids aggregated with conventional generation, as in Denmark [222], or even provide a maximum of 70% of their installed capacity for downward regulation, as in Germany [218].

Martín-Martínez et al. [213] indicate that the provision of upward regulation can be possible in case of forecast errors, when the real-time expected production is higher than the performed bids, or also by performing voluntary bids below forecasts. This can also be possible by overloading wind turbines, i.e., by forcing their inertia moment to generate extra energy [316]. However, in case of wind falls, WPPs may not be able to guarantee the security of the system and need to perform aggregated bids with conventional generation [222]. Over the long-term, when VRE and conventional generation follow the same rules, unit commitment and aggregation should be important aspects of VRE, to avoid the payment of penalties.

Hirth and Ziegenhagen [219] indicated that special attention should be given to the capabilities of WPPs to provide balancing reserves. Brauns et al. [309] concluded that the use of the available active power, instead of a schedule, as a reference to determine the balancing reserves of WPPs, lead to less wasted energy and lower prices. Banshwar et al. [317] demonstrated how VRE can participate in BMs in a test system with seven different generators (thermal, hydro, wind and PV), where VRE constitutes 26% of the installed capacity. The authors proposed a sequential clearing of spot markets and BMs, concluding that the integration of VRE results in cost savings and feasible solutions in both markets. Banshwar et al. [318] presented a review about the participation of VRE in ancillary services, concluding that WPPs are technically competitive in providing services like operating reserves, regulation and voltage support, but have difficulties to provide other services, such as “load following” and “black start”.

Hansen, Altin and Iov [319] tested the support of aggregated WPPs to temporary frequency response (inertial response and FCR), and to power oscillation damping (damps of the low-frequency oscillations), concluding that WPPs exhibit technical capabilities to provide such services. However, in situations involving high penetrations of wind power, the frequency is potentially degraded, and WPPs need to be supported by conventional generation.

Regarding the economic and welfare benefits, the participation of VRE in BMs was studied by an

increasing number of researchers. For instance, Kiviluoma et al. [320] studied the benefits for Portugal and Spain, Ireland, and Europe (EU-28⁵ plus Norway and Switzerland), by considering scenarios involving different levels of VRE penetration. For Portugal and Spain, the benefits (decrease in annual costs) range between 1% (for 32% of VRE penetration) and 8% (for 50% of VRE penetration), while for Ireland and Europe the benefits range between 8% and 12% (for 32% of VRE penetration), and also between 1% and 6% (for 50% of VRE penetration). For the particular case of 42% of VRE penetration, the results for Portugal and Spain indicate the following penetrations of VRE: 5.4% in upward FCR, 90% in downward FCR, and 12.5% in aFRR. For Europe, the penetrations of VRE are as follows: 4% in upward FCR, 34% in downward FCR, and 12% in aFRR. Accordingly, for Portugal and Spain, 42% of VRE penetration can be considered appropriate (to a certain extent) to surpass the downward needs of FCR, while in Europe such penetration can be considered insufficient. European Commission [264] also analysed the reduction of the total reserve costs in the European Union (EU-28), considering solar and other renewable energy sources, and reaching a reduction of 6% in the cost of BMs.

Now, a careful analysis of the literature suggests that most researchers are addressing important issues associated with the participation of VRE in BMs (see, e.g., [217]). However, the majority of them focused on the reduction of the costs of the system and the penetration of VRE in BMs. In this work, we also focus on the following four key dependent variables: the value of wind energy to the market, the system imbalances, the costs associated with BMs, and the total cost of the system.

5.6.2 Current Status of Key European Countries

In 2016, Spain has become pioneer in relation to the participation of WPPs in BMs, by allowing the participation of aggregated WPPs in both the mFRR market and the imbalance management (IM) [217]. In 2017, more than 50% of the Spanish WPPs may participate in these two markets, with a penetration of 6.1% for downward regulation, 2.55% for upward regulation, and 0.7% for the IM [213].

In Germany, two wind farms (86 MW) were pre-qualified to provide up to 70% of their installed capacity to the downward mFRR market [218]. Hirth and Ziegenhagen [219] estimated that WPPs may surpass 90% of the German downward regulation needs, in case they participate in BMs only. However, this result is reduced to 10%, in case WPPs participate in both the DAM and BMs. Papaefthymiou et al. [321] studied the impact of alternative market designs in cost savings, using real data from 2013, and considering that German offshore WPPs may participate in the downward mFRR market. In a reference scenario (corresponding to 0.6 GW of installed capacity), such participation can bring cost savings of 0.7%. In other two scenarios, specifically a scenario of 11 GW (approved capacity) and a scenario of 30 GW (capacity to be approved), the cost savings were 20% and 18%, respectively. The improvements (in relation to the reference scenario) are as follows: (i) a cost saving around 49%, in case of no reaction of markets to the new offshore WPPs, and (ii) a cost saving of 33% (30 GW scenario), in case of the implementation of weekend tenders of offshore wind. A change of the product time, from 4 hours to 1 hour, is only beneficial for large penetrations of offshore wind power. In relation to the reference scenario, higher feed-in-tariffs are not beneficial for a very high installed capacity of offshore WPPs (30

⁵The European Union before Brexit (i.e., including the United Kingdom).

GW). Also, an increase in the capacity procurement brings lower benefits. Lorenz and Gerbaulet [322] simulated the participation of WPPs in the aFRR and mFRR markets in the German electricity system of 2025. The authors concluded that the costs of BMs can be reduced in 40% (in case of a wind power penetration of 10% in both the aFRR and the downward mFRR).

Denmark has also allowed the participation of WPPs in the downward mFRR market. However, WPPs need to submit bids together with conventional generation to guarantee the supply, in cases where wind turbines are unable to deliver the required performance, due to failing wind [221, 224]. EMD [221] and Sorknaes et al. [224] performed tests where WPPs (21 MW) can make bids for downward regulation in Denmark (on 14 February 2012, at 0:00 p.m.). The results of the former study indicated an increase in the wind energy value of 173%, while for the latter study such increase was 196%. Also, the latter study involved the offer of downward regulation by WPPs during the first 9 months of 2010, resulting in an increase of 8.5% in the wind energy value. Skytte and Bobo [214] studied the different degrees of active participation of a WPP with 15 MW in both the Danish day-ahead and balancing markets, during the year 2014, by considering four scenarios: i) a single-stage offering strategy (reference scenario, where the participation in the DAM is based on wind power forecasts only), ii) a single-stage offering strategy (bids based on both wind power forecasts and prices of BMs), iii) a two-stage offering strategy (strategic bidding on both the DAM and BMs), and iv) a deterministic two-stage offering strategy (bids based on both perfect information of production and market prices). The authors concluded that the strategic bidding of WPPs increases the wind power imbalances in relation to the bids in the DAM, but also increases the wind energy value in relation to the reference scenario, namely 1.5% (second scenario), 4.5% (third scenario) and 7.5% (fourth scenario).

Great Britain allowed WPPs to participate in two curtailment products (a balancing service different from BMs): “Manage Constraint” and “Rebalance System”, receiving 40% more money to cut energy than to produce it [225]. In Ireland, WPPs can participate in similar products: “Constraints” and “Curtailments”. In Denmark, Germany, Italy, Portugal and Spain, WPPs can also be compensated for curtailments [323]. In Belgium, a study for the specific case of the downward aFRR market obtained a reliability above 90% [228].

5.7 Strategic Bidding in Balancing Markets

WPPs can adopt a bidding strategy that optimizes the use of wind power, increasing their revenue and avoiding large quantities of wasted energy. Bidding the deviations from the DAM commitment in the mFRR market at 0 €/MWh (for “upward regulation”), and the DAM price (for “downward regulation”), receiving/paying the clearing price, may represent an adequate solution to avoid the payment of penalties. However, WPPs can probably get a better remuneration by considering the aFRR market, namely by bidding their short-run capacity at 0 €/MW and receiving the market price, despite a higher probability to waste more energy or even to slightly decrease imbalances.

The resulting strategy is based on the optimal use of the resources of WPPs, with the goal of being the first to buy or sell in a market base (as in the DAM). So, in the case of large deviations from the

Figure 5.1: Strategic bidding of wind power producers: blue corresponds to task associated with the DAM and green to tasks related to the participation of WPPs in BMs.

DAM schedule, it can be favourable to bid deviations in the mFRR market. This behaviour consists in a non-strategic provision of regulating power (WPPs only benefit from better production forecasts, not from market price forecasts), the second degree of the active participation of WPPs in the markets (see, e.g., Skytte:18). WPPs can only make bids in BMs if they maintain a stable operation (i.e., keep a stable power requested by TSOs). In other words, WPPs can only make bids if they deviate in a specific direction during a particular hour, for the specific case of the mFRR market (and in case of up deviations, for the aFRR market as well). Furthermore, they may bid either the lowest 15 minutes deviation (for the case of up deviations) or a higher deviation (for the mFRR market only). This option is similar to the German case, where WPPs are limited to offer a maximum of 70% of their installed capacity to downward regulation [218]. For a possible 15-minute mFRR market, WPPs do not need to address such issues, since their production uncertainty decreases with a reduction of the market time unit, increasing their potential to support BMs (see Figure 5.1).

5.8 Wind Power Participation in Balancing Markets: a Simulation-based Study

This section begins by presenting an overview of the MATREM simulator. Next, it describes a study aiming at investigating the operation of WPPs to satisfy the needs of BMs. The simulations involve the DAM as well as the aFRR and mFRR markets. The section closes by presenting and discussing the experimental results in detail.

5.8.1 MATREM: An Agent-Based Simulation Tool for Electricity Markets

MATREM (for Multi-Agent TRading in Electricity Markets) allows the user to conduct a wide range of simulations regarding the behaviour of EMs under a variety of conditions [2, 54]. In each simulation, different

agents are used to capture the heterogeneity of restructured markets, notably generating companies, retailers, aggregators, large and small consumers, market operators, and system operators (see, e.g., [64, 82]). The agents are essentially computer systems capable of flexible action and able to interact with other agents to meet their design objectives. A graphical interface allows the user to specify and monitor all simulations.

MATREM supports a day-ahead market and a shorter-term market known as intraday market. Supply bids and demand offers are aggregated to find a clearing price at which supply and demand are equal (see, e.g., [61, 77]). MATREM is also able to simulate BMs. The system operator defines the needs of these markets and the agents may submit bids to buy or sell energy.

5.8.2 Methodology and Data

The study involves the simulation of both the daily Iberian market prices and the BM prices during the period 2009–2010. In this period, 31 representative days are statistically selected based on a K-medoids clustering algorithm [88]. Specifically, the clustering algorithm is used to identify the representative wind power daily profiles based on the observed data. For each representative day, the algorithm is then applied to identify typical daily forecast errors from the bids of the DAM [295].

The average wind power penetration in Portugal was 16.18% during the period of the study. The following sources of data are considered in the analysis: (i) hourly prices and quantities submitted to the daily Iberian market [7], (ii) hourly prices and quantities submitted to the Portuguese BM (data reported by REN, the Portuguese electrical grid), (iii) hourly requirements of aFRR and mFRR, and (iv) hourly imbalances and prices of the imbalances [324].

The analysis is carried out using the MATREM system. The agents are twenty producers (representing the supply-side) and four retailers (representing the demand-side).⁶ Several key features of the producer agents are shown in Table 5.2, including the maximum capacity of producer P1, the wind aggregator (WA) of WPPs, and its bid price (to submit to the simulated DAM). The wind power generation data was achieved from a set of eight distributed WPPs situated in Portugal (involving the installed capacity of 249 MW, around 10% of the Portuguese installed capacity).⁷ To get meaningful results, the data is scaled to 2490 MW (of installed capacity), by multiplying all values by a constant factor. The forecasts (time horizon from 18h to 42h) are obtained by using the K-nearest neighbour methodology [272]. The normalised root mean square error of the forecasts is around 17%.

The study accounts for the statistical distribution of seven typical power profiles:

- Profile 1: 68 occurrences (9.51%).
- Profile 2: 93 occurrences (13.07%).

⁶To simulate the daily Iberian market prices, there is a need to define the software agents that participate in the (simulated) day-ahead market incorporated into the MATREM system. For simplicity, and after a careful examination of the operation of MIBEL, we consider that the electricity supply industry is represented by 20 software agents and the demand for electrical energy involves 4 agents. This simplification allows us to perform computer simulations as close to the reality as possible, while overcoming the computational complexity resulting from considering a larger number of agents.

⁷Agent P_1 results from the aggregation of eight WPPs (agents P_2 to P_9) situated in the center of Portugal (henceforth, each WPP is referred to as WPP_j , $j = 1, \dots, 8$)

Table 5.2: Key features of the producer agents.

Agent	Country	Type	Maximum Capacity (MW)	Marginal Cost (€/MWh)
P_1	Portugal	Wind Aggregator	2490	0
P_2 to P_9	Portugal	Wind Power Producers	2490	0
P_{10}	Portugal	Renewable mix	2000	0
P_{11}	Portugal	Hydroelectricity	4500	[30; 60]
P_{12}	Portugal	Coal	1800	≈ 30
P_{13}	Portugal	Combined Cycled Gas	3000	≈ 100
P_{14}	Portugal	Fuel oil	2000	≈ 170
P_{15}	Spain	Renewable mix	30000	0
P_{16}	Spain	Hydroelectricity	16500	[30; 60]
P_{17}	Spain	Coal	10000	≈ 30
P_{18}	Spain	Nuclear	7500	≈ 30
P_{19}	Spain	Combined Cycled Gas	22000	≈ 100
P_{20}	Spain	Fuel oil	4000	≈ 170

- Profile 3: 63 occurrences (8.81%).
- Profile 4: 74 occurrences (10.35%).
- Profile 5: 165 occurrences (23.08%).
- Profile 6: 124 occurrences (17.34%).
- Profile 7: 128 occurrences (17.90%).

Each profile involves 3 to 6 typical deviation patterns (forecast errors) in relation to the bids submitted to the DAM, resulting in 31 representative days (see Figure 5.2).

The daily Iberian market and the Portuguese BM are simulated by using the MATREM system. Due to interconnection constraints observed in the electricity transactions between Portugal and Spain, in the hours that the clearing point results in a violation of such constraints, a market splitting mechanism is considered, meaning that the DAM is simulated for Portugal only.

Due to technical reasons in the Portuguese aFRR market, every producer needs to bid half of their upward capacity as downward capacity. Since aFRR is more requested for upward regulation, the system requirements for upward capacity are twice the requirements for downward capacity. Also, we consider that agents P_1 , and P_{10} to P_{14} submit bids to the BM.⁸ The bidding process of agent P_1 involves basically the following three steps (see also Figure 5.1):⁹

1. Submission of (forecast) bids to the DAM, individually for each WPP_j .
2. Determination of the expected 15-minute deviations of each WPP_j .
3. Submission of bids to the BM for each WPP_j (only for WPPs that maintain a stable power).

Figures 5.3 and 5.4 present an illustrative example for a particular day of operation (April 8th, 2010), placing emphasis on WPP1. In particular, Figure 5.3 depicts the bids submitted to the DAM and the sum

⁸Notice that the submission of aggregated bids to the Iberian DAM and to the Portuguese balancing market is currently not allowed.

⁹For clarity of exposition, and since the agent P_1 is the most import for this work, we describe only its bidding process.

Figure 5.2: (a) Typical power profiles of agent P1 and (b) day-ahead forecast errors for power profile 6.

Figure 5.3: Bidding in the DAM (solid blue line), corresponding to step 1 (above), and aggregated wind power forecast deviations (orange line), corresponding to step 2 (above).

Figure 5.4: Step 3: 15-min deviations for WPP1: (a) deviations are not in the same direction, (b) stable up (blue bars) deviations (the lower green deviation defines the bid to aFRR and mFRR markets) and (c) stable down (red bars) deviations (the higher deviation defines the bid to mFRR market). The 15 min deviations define the bids to the 15-min mFRR market.

of the expected individual deviations. Figure 5.4 depicts the 15-min deviations of WPP1. In Figure 5.4(a), there are no bids for the aFRR and mFRR markets, while for the 15-min mFRR market the four pairs of the type (power, price) are as follows: (-7.1, 35), (8.3, 0), (21.3, 0), (124.1, 0). In Figure 5.4(b), the bids are the lowest deviation (99.9 MW) for the mFRR market and a power band between -49.9 and 99.9 MW for the aFRR market, with a price equal to 0 €/MWh, while for the 15-min mFRR market the quantity submitted is exactly the 15-min deviations of each 15-min block with a price equal to 0 €/MWh. In Figure 5.4(c), the bids are the highest deviation (-67.2 MW) for the mFRR market with a price equal to the DAM price (43.0 €/MWh). There is no bid to the aFRR market and the power bids for the 15-min mFRR market are the 15-min deviations with a price of 43.0 €/MWh (the DAM Price).

5.8.3 Iberian Market Simulations – Results and Discussion

Table 5.3 presents the simulation results from the point of view of WPPs, i.e., by taking into account the following variables: i) the wind energy value, ii) imbalances and iii) penalties and costs with imbalances.

Table 5.3: Simulation results from the point of view of the wind power producers: average values of the key variables under evaluation (per day) considering both the DAM and the BM.

Variables	Scenario			
	Baseline	A	B	C
Wind Energy Value (€/MWh)	29.48	30.93	30.12	31.18
Total Imbalances of WPPs (GWh/day)	8.70	8.37	8.26	7.45
Losses due to Imbalances of WPPs (k€/day)	133.15	127.19	127.35	113.62
WPPs Levelized Costs of Penalties (€/MWh)	7.24	6.95	6.87	5.93
Penalties Paid by WPPs (€/MWh)	13.43	13.35	13.37	12.97

The DAM results are similar for all simulations performed. For each scenario, the main differences are related with the following: i) BM results in terms of costs and quantity, ii) the remuneration of wind power producers from the market, iii) costs with deviations of wind power producers, and iv) deviations of wind power producers.

Table 5.3 shows that bidding in a 15-min mFRR market leads to better results for WPPs, which indicates that reducing the market time unit (from 1-hour to 15-minute) and the bidding horizon (to a

time closer to real-time) is beneficial. In particular, allowing WPP agents to bid in the BM leads to an increase of the wind energy value between 2.18% and 5.76% (for scenarios B and C, respectively). Also, the wind power deviations decrease between 3.8% and 14.4% (in scenarios A and C, respectively).

Table 5.4: Average values of the key variables under evaluation (per day) considering both the DAM and the BM – point of view of the balancing market.

Variables	Scenario			
	Baseline	A	B	C
mFRR Reserve Quantity (GWh/day)	9.94	9.59	9.50	8.77
mFRR Reserve Direction (GWh/day)	-2.24	-2.60	-2.18	-1.72
Wind Energy Penetration in Upward Regulation (%)	0	14.96	4.74	23.26
Wind Energy Penetration in Downward Regulation (%)	0	0	6.50	18.17
aFRR Band Needs Satisfied by WPPs (%)	0	24.83	0	0
mFRR Reserve Costs (k€/day)	88.19	88.19	75.14	45.03
aFRR Band Cost (k€/day)	164.30	139.99	164.30	164.30
mFRR Levelized Cost (€/MWh)	8.60	8.60	7.93	4.06
Total Reserve Costs (k€/day)	252.50	228.11	239.44	212.34

Table 5.4 presents the simulation results from the point of view of the BM, i.e., by taking into account the following variables: i) the quantity exchanged, ii) the reserve direction, iii) costs, iv) balancing needs, and v) the penetration of wind power. The reduction of the imbalances of WPPs leads to a reduction of the costs of the BM up to 15.9% (in scenario C). The percentage of wind power that satisfies the band needs of aFRR is 24.83%, resulting in a reduction in the cost of the aFRR band around 15%. The use of 15 minute bids (considered in Scenario C) leads to an increase of the wind energy value in the market, due to a reduction in the deviations of WPPs and also in the penalties, as well as a decrease of the clearing-prices of BMs. A reasonable penetration of wind power in the mFRR (less than 18% for upward regulation, and 16% for downward regulation), and also a moderate penetration in the aFRR band (24.83%), lead to a reduction of the costs of these markets.

The results also highlight that a wind power penetration of 16.18% in the power system is still far from satisfying the needs of the BM (a maximum of 24.83% penetration in the aFRR band). However, the remuneration is lower when compared with the remuneration from a case involving no deviations of WPPs [65]. At this stage, It should be taken into account that the results obtained are for Portugal, which is currently not allowing aggregation of bids into the daily market, leading to an increase in the deviations of WPPs. We also note that in the Danish studies the wind power penetration is smaller and the bids of WPPs can be aggregated, thus not affecting the prices of the mFRR market. Overall, Table 4 shows that bidding in a 15 min mFRR market leads to better results.

From the point of view of the transmission system operator, the participation of WPPs in BMs can bring the following positive impacts: i) a reduction in the use of reserves due to a decrease in the wind power deviations, ii) a reduction in the costs of the BM due to the bids of WPPs at zero euros (for upward regulation) and the DAM price (for downward regulation), which leads to a decrease in the clearing prices of upward regulation (and also an increase in the prices of downward regulation), and iii) a short-run upgrade information about WPPs real-time (expected) schedules.

5.9 Conclusions

This article analysed the participation of WPPs in BMs. Specifically, the article presented a simulation based study to evaluate the participation of WPPs in both the DAM and the BM. The study involves four scenarios: a baseline scenario (participation of wind power in the DAM only), scenario A (participation of WPPs in both the DAM and the aFRR market), scenario B (participation of WPPs in both the DAM and the mFRR market), and scenario C (participation of WPPs in both the DAM and the mFRR market, with a reduction of the time unit of the mFRR market from 1 hour to 15 minutes). The main results indicate that scenario C is the best one. We highlight the following (for scenario C in relation to the baseline scenario):

- An increase of 5.76% in the wind energy value to the market.
- A reduction of 14.4% in the imbalances.
- A decrease around 16% in the costs of the BM.

Overall, the results highlight that the participation of WPPs in the BM benefit the power system at both technical and economic levels, by increasing the wind energy value to the market and reducing imbalances. Such participation can contribute to a possible new paradigm, where WPPs may be active players in EMs, without needing FITs or other incentives to be economically viable. In such a paradigm, VRE will take more responsibility, by being able to provide a full range of grid support services (e.g., BMs). However, to obtain all the possible benefits from the participation of VRE in EMs, and as indicated by other authors (e.g., [44, 61, 305], new market designs elements may be needed (e.g., a market time unit of 15 minutes, instead of 1 hour).

Finally, we note that the approach discussed in this work, as well as other existing approaches (such as aggregation or postponing the day-ahead gate closure), may result in a power system more attractive for investment in VRE without FITs (or others incentives). Since wind power has zero or near-zero marginal cost, its participation in BMs is important at an economic level (to reduce the costs of BMs), and also at a technical level (to control the production of WPPs and to reduce the imbalances of the system).

5.10 Future Work: Analysis of Key Aspects

The new proposal of the European Community [35] includes legislation for a gate closure of EMs closer to real-time operation, balance responsibility for renewable energy sources, portfolio/aggregation bidding, reduction of the market time unit to 15 minutes, and the participation of VRE in BMs.

This article considered individual bids of WPPs in BMs, a situation similar to the German case, with non strategic provision of regulating power. It also considered a gate closure of 15 minutes ahead and bids performed for products of either one hour and 15 minutes. Accordingly, some important aspects for future work are as follows:

1. Strategic bidding in DAMs, intra-day markets and BMs.
2. The possibility of aggregated bids in BMs.
3. A gate-closure of BMs between one hour and five minutes ahead of real-time operation.
4. A 15-minute market time unit for bidding in BMs.
5. New BM products adapted to wind power.

Some notes about these five aspects follows. Skytte and Bobo [214] verified that a gradual increase in the active participation of WPPs in markets, results in high wind energy values. WPPs can perform strategic bids in spot and balancing markets taking into account wind power forecasts and expected values of market prices. An increase in the wind energy value is important to have profitable investments (e.g., in new wind turbines).

Bids of aggregated WPPs are typically advantageous to minimize forecast errors. As noted earlier, this is the solution adopted in Spain for the participation of WPPs in the mFRR market [213]. It can also be considered a good solution to increase the efficiency of the participation of WPPs in BMs, namely by reducing imbalances (and consequently the penalties to pay) and the wasted energy (in case of meeting set-points). However, a potential better solution consists of allowing aggregated bids of WPPs and conventional generation in BMs (as performed in Denmark, for the downward mFRR market only).

A gate closure of BMs close to real-time operation is an important element of market design to accommodate the participation of WPPs in BMs (see, e.g., [63, 66]. Also, Papaefthymiou et al. [321] verified that shortening the length of the downward mFRR product from four hours to one hour in Germany, for large penetration levels of wind power, may contribute to a cost saving of 18%. Clearly, a gate closure close to real-time operation and short products are important elements of market design that can improve wind power forecasts and the value of wind energy.

A market time unit of 15 minutes to BMs (instead of 1 hour) may also be considered an important element of market design. In fact, balance products need to be fully activated in 15 minutes and imbalance costs are also calculated for periods of 15 minutes [16, 35]. This measure also benefit WPPs, since they have less volatility in shorter time periods, which can be verified by the difference of almost three times in the reduction of imbalances in scenarios B (5.06%) and C (14.37%) of our study.

Overall, we are confident that the participation of WPPs in BMs is (and will be) an important feature of future markets, which can be largely improved by considering the five aspects just outlined.

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Chapter 6

Multi-Agent Electricity Markets: Retailer Portfolio Optimization Using Markowitz Theory¹

6.1 Authors

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6.2 Abstract

The major electricity market models include: pools, bilateral contracts and hybrid models. Pool prices tend to change quickly and variations are usually highly unpredictable. In this way, market participants can enter into bilateral contracts to hedge against pool price volatility. In bilateral contracts, market participants can set the terms and conditions of agreements independent of the market operator. The hybrid model combines features of both pools and bilateral contracts.

This paper is devoted to risk management and the optimization of the portfolios of retailers operating in liberalized electricity markets. It introduces a model for optimizing portfolios composed by end-use consumers using the Markowitz theory. It also presents an overview of a multi-agent system for electricity markets. The system simulates the behavior of various markets entities, including generating companies, retailers and consumers. The final part of the paper presents three case studies on portfolio optimization involving risk management: a retailer (a software agent) optimizes its portfolio by taking into account the attitude towards risk and the offer of a 3-rate tariff to five different types of consumers: industrial, large and small commercial, residential and street lightning. The results show that the retailer, by being more realistic in choosing consumers to its portfolio, can offer more competitive tariffs to key consumers and keep the portfolio optimal and stable in relation to the risk-return ratio.

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6.3 Keywords

Electricity Retailers, Forward bilateral contracts, Markowitz theory, Multi-agent electricity markets, Portfolio of customers, Risk attitude.

6.4 Introduction

Hunt and Shuttleworth [326] propose four models to chart the evolution of the electricity supply industry towards full competition: regulated monopoly, purchasing agency, wholesale competition, and retail competition (see also [1]). Three major market models have been considered to achieve the key objectives of ensuring a secure system and facilitating an economical operation [1, 3]: electricity pools (day-ahead and intraday markets), bilateral transactions (forwards, futures, options and contracts for difference) and hybrid markets. The negotiation of bilateral contracts will only converge to agreement if both sides can find a pool/bilateral mix that provides an acceptable compromise between risk and benefit [21–23]. This is one of the problems that retailers face when defining their portfolios of consumers.

Typically, electricity retailers buy energy in spot markets and sign bilateral contracts (e.g, forwards) with producers in order to satisfy customers. Retailers often follow a business as usual strategy with the objective of maximizing revenue, i.e., they give small discounts to consumers to attract them. The discounts depend on the consumption profile of each customer (residential, commercial, industrial, etc.), but normally are similar for customers with similar consumption profiles. Hence, there is no “discrimination” between consumers with a particular consumption profile. However, the discounts are mainly made in promotional campaigns to obtain new customers, i.e, old customers do not normally have additional benefits with new campaigns. This business as usual strategy may lead to some problems regarding the loyalty of customers, specially customers that care more about the electricity cost than with the energy provider or the relation between the two. Other problem is the customers’ risk, namely retailers do not usually differentiate between customers with similar consumption profiles, and by pursuing the objective of increasing the number of clients to increase the revenue (absolute values), they use a strategy that maximizes the revenue, instead of maximizing the return and minimizing the risk associated with the customers in the portfolio (relative values). Accordingly, retailers consider large portfolios that can potentially lead to high revenues, but may involve high risks, and frequently require large investments (due to their dimension). Simply put, retailers consider large portfolios that bring a significant volatility to their revenues.

In this paper, we focus on the dual objective of maximizing the return and minimizing the risk associated with portfolios composed of end-use customers. This can be done by differentiating between similar customers and selecting specific customers. In particular, differentiating between customers by proposing different tariffs to consumers of a specific type, but with different consumption patterns. Selecting customers by proposing better tariffs to customers that can benefit retailers (and rejecting or proposing worse tariffs to customers that can impair the portfolio, instead of accepting all customers). Proposing better tariffs to key customers, in relation to other competitive retailers, and having a special

care to update these tariffs by taking into account market prices, consumption patterns and promotional campaigns, can be important to increase key customers' loyalty, keeping the portfolio more stable in terms of risk-return.

Thus, this paper is devoted to both risk management (in bilateral contracting) and optimization of retailers' portfolios. It presents several key features of software agents able to compute an optimized portfolio composed by end-used customers, paying special attention to risk management, notably pricing strategies, a dual-objective optimization model for dealing with risk and return (maximizing the return and minimizing the risk), and also the influence of the risk attitude in the composition of the portfolio. The risk attitude (also known as risk preference or risk appetite) of agents plays an important role in their negotiation behavior, imposing limits to the trading margin and thus influencing the negotiation offers. The risk attitude can be classified as risk-averse, risk-neutral and risk-seeking. As expected, higher risk attitudes influence more the negotiation behavior of the agents.

There are several approaches to deal with portfolio management [173, 174], but they mainly refer to the optimization of assets, especially in the stock exchange, which was the initial purpose of the Markowitz theory [327]. In relation to electricity markets (EMs), the most important pieces of work about portfolio optimization focus on strategic bidding [186, 188], where the authors try to obtain the optimal quantity of electricity to buy or sell in different market types. In Ponsich et al. [175], the authors provide a survey of algorithms to solve the portfolio optimization problem for other real-world applications (i.e., applications different of the EM). In Rockafellar et al. [176], the authors consider a new approach for simultaneous calculation of the VaR (value-at-risk) and the optimization of the CVaR (conditional VaR) for a broad class of problems.

The electricity market has several players with the objective of trading electricity. The aggregators [182, 183] and the traders [177, 178] are the players that play a role similar to that of the retailers [189]. However, their inherent market behavior is different, so these two types of agents will not receive our preponderance in this work. Now, there are other approaches related to the electricity sector similar to ours [177, 178, 184, 185, 189]. Teive et al. [177] proposed an approach for solving the contract portfolio optimization problem by using a multi objective genetic algorithm. In [178], the authors proposed a decision support system for solving the problem of contract portfolio optimization — choose the best set of market options to sell or buy electricity — by using linear programming, and also to perform a risk analysis of the portfolio performance, using VaR and CVaR metrics. In this piece of work, traders act as speculators, so they do not have fixed end-use consumers in the demand-side neither fixed generators in the supply-side. Basically, they aim at optimizing the revenue by trying to buy electricity at low prices and selling it at higher prices. The authors developed a case-study where a trader have: (i) to buy 1000 MWh of energy both in the spot market (500 MWh), and by signing forward contracts (500 MWh) and then (ii) sell this energy quantity by considering forward and option (call or put) contracts. The optimization problem consists in choosing the quantity of electricity to sell through these types of contracts. Our major objectives are different from that of the previous two publications [177, 178]. In particular, we have the goal of obtaining an optimized portfolio of end-use consumers by introducing a multi-agent system (MAS), pricing strategies for defining tariffs, and a decision making process taking into account the

Markowitz theory.

Suksonghong et al. [184] studied the application of several genetic algorithms to the portfolio optimization problem of a GenCo (generating company). The optimization of the GenCo's portfolio consists in choosing the best allocation of the produced electricity to the spot market and forward bilateral contracts. The authors aim at analyzing the performance of different genetic algorithms to solve this problem. Hatami et al. [189] developed a decision support framework for electricity retailers that need to purchase electricity to satisfy their clients. The objective is to optimize the electricity purchasing options between the spot market, forward contracts, call options, interrupted contracts and self-generating facilities. This approach is different from ours, because the authors consider a fixed number of clients and optimize the portfolio of markets options to purchase electricity. Here, we take into account the spot market prices to choose the best group of clients (portfolio optimization) with whom each retailer wants to sign forward contracts.

Kazagic et al. [185] aimed at defining the best power generators in order to achieve specific targets related to renewable energy sources penetration and decarbonization. They try to solve the problem of designing a power system with several generators (the portfolio). They optimize the share of each generator in the electricity production in order to achieve specific environmental targets.

After performing an analysis of the bibliography related to retailers and portfolios optimization, we concluded that there is a small number of pieces of work that address the problem of defining optimized portfolios of end-use customers. The majority of studies consider the supply-side point of view, consisting in defining the best markets for power producers selling their electricity. From the demand-side point of view, the existing studies consist mainly in optimizing the quantity of electricity (a fixed number of contracts with consumers) that must be bought in different markets (day-ahead, forward, etc.) in order to satisfy the electricity required by consumers. Teive et al. [177] performed some work similar to ours, but as explained before, they only consider the optimized electricity quantity (fixed) that a trader wants to sell in a bilateral transaction, i.e., they do not characterize consumers neither take into account their load profiles (variable consumption).

In this work we pursue a different objective, since we try to define efficient groups of consumers with different load profiles by optimizing the risk-return output. Basically, we consider that retailers sign forward contracts with several end-use consumers (industrial, commercial, residential and street lightning) and buy electricity from the day-ahead market. Then, we compute the Markowitz frontier by both using several pricing strategies (i.e., strategies for offering tariffs to consumers) and taking into account the retailers risk attitude. Following this, we define efficient portfolios by considering the Markowitz frontier (see section 6.6 for more details).

The work presented here refines and extends our previous work on the day-ahead electricity market [12, 63], and mainly in the area of automated negotiation between different parties based on a generic negotiation model [112, 325], which was adapted to the negotiation of bilateral contracts between sellers and buyers of electricity [73], and extended with strategies to hedge against spot prices volatility [72, 328]. In [71], we present a deterministic approach to the trader problem, i.e., we introduce a model for optimizing a retailer's portfolio of consumers. The work described in this article is the most similar to

the work presented here. Both pieces of work try to obtain an optimized portfolio of consumers, but the approach adopted in [71] is limited, by considering the past only, i.e., we know the past market prices and the consumers' consumptions and by using a deterministic algorithm we obtain the optimized portfolio for a specific period of time (e.g., one week). In this paper, we aim at obtaining the optimized portfolio of consumers for the future, by taking into account the market price volatility and the consumption variability of end-use consumers along time.

Specifically, the purpose of this article is threefold:

1. To develop a model for optimizing the portfolios of retailer agents (composed by end-use customers), using risk management and the Markowitz theory;
2. To extend a multi-agent system to simulate EMs, by modelling retailer agents (equipped with the above model) and different consumer agents, namely residential, commercial, industrial and street lightning (see [71] for more details about the different types of consumers).
3. To develop three case-studies to illustrate (and test) the model. The case studies involve a retailer (software agent) that wants to optimize its portfolio of clients using real data from the Iberian Market (MIBEL). The retailer is a moderate risk-averse agent.

In the three aforementioned case-studies, we perform three simulations, using the following pricing strategies:

- Simulation 1 - "Equal Tariff" strategy;
- Simulation 2 - "Equal Tariff" and "Minimize the VaR of a tariff at a minimum return" strategies;
- Simulation 3 - "Equal Tariff" and "Minimize the VaR of a tariff at a minimum return" strategies, with a market price forecast.

Table 6.1: Main results of the case studies: energy division by each client type using different strategies

Simulation	Energy share (%)			Return	VaR
	SCom	SL	Ind	%	%
1	[25.54; 41.65]	[74.46; 50.27]	[0.00; 8.10]	[1.12; 13.40]	[8.86; 9.78]
2	[10.65; 42.48]	[89.35; 57.52]	[0.00; 0.00]	[1.11; 13.39]	[8.39; 9.39]
3	[7.16; 15.97]	[92.94; 84.03]	[0.00; 0.00]	[10.02; 12.98]	[9.04; 9.33]

The main results of the article are summarized in Table 6.2. For moderate risk-averse retailers, we can conclude that they will only want consumers of the following types: SCom (small commercial), SL (street lightning) and Ind (industrial). This occurs because SCom consumers lead to higher returns (relative values), SL consumers mitigate risk (lower VaR) and Ind consumers lead to higher absolute returns (they are favorable when retailers desire a portfolio with high revenues). LCom (large commercial)

consumers have a consumption pattern similar to SCom consumers, but give a lower relative return. So, when both types of consumers (SCom and LCom) are considered, they increase the risk of the portfolio. Thus, for risk-averse retailers, LCom consumers are not favorable in portfolios with a substantial share of SCom consumers. Res (residential) consumers have a consumption pattern with high volatility, so they increase the risk of the portfolio. Res consumers are only favorable in cases where they give high returns to retailers (risk seeking agents). For risk-averse retailers, they can be favorable when risk mitigation measures are applied, such as risk sharing [72].

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. Section 6.5 describes some aspects of bilateral contracting and risk management. Section 6.6 introduces a model for the optimization of a retailer's portfolio of clients. Section 6.7 presents an overview of the multi-agent system (MAS) and illustrates graphically the main steps of the simulations performed. Section 6.8 presents three case studies on portfolio optimization and risk management. Finally, concluding remarks are presented in section 6.9.

6.5 Bilateral Contracting and Risk Management

Either physical or financial, a bilateral contract is typically negotiated weeks or months prior to its delivery and can include the following specifications [1]: 1) starting date and time, 2) ending date and time, 3) price per hour (€/MWh) over the length of the contract, 4) variable power (MW) amount over the length of the contract, and 5) range of hours when the contract is to be delivered. In a more general form, the MW amount, contract length and price could be time-varying. This generalization is, however, not followed in this work, where we consider a 3-rate tariff, equal over the whole contract duration.

A bilateral transaction involves only two parties: a buyer and a seller. Depending on the amount of time available and the quantities to be traded, buyers and sellers can resort to the following forms of bilateral trading [1]: customized long-term contracts, trading "over the counter" and electronic trading.

The contracts considered in this work are customized long-term forward contracts, i.e., contracts to purchase and sale a given amount and quality of energy, in a specific future date, at a price set in the present. The buyer is bound to pay the agreed price and the seller commits with the agreed conditions. These contracts may be subject to physical settlement (where the seller delivers the energy sold) or financial settlement (in which there is no physical delivery of energy, but only a reckoning due to the market price on the settlement date).

Forward bilateral contracts can be considered a form of hedging. Now, in order to effectively manage risk, it is important to understand several factors and processes associated with the potential risks that each stakeholder may be exposed in a transaction. The way agents deal with risk depends on their risk attitude, which is modeled by risk preference functions, as will be described next.

6.5.1 Agent Decision Functions

The agents' risk preferences are broadly classified into risk-averse (for seller $\lambda < 0$ and for buyer $\lambda > 0$), risk neutral ($\lambda = 0$), and risk-seeking (for seller $\lambda > 0$ and for buyer $\lambda < 0$), where λ is a risk preference

Figure 6.1: Main phases of the risk management process

constant (see [328] for more details about the risk preference or attitude). For illustrative purposes, a simple example describing how a seller agent can trade energy in a liberalized market can be found in [72].

The agents can use different utility functions [23], notably the well-known additive function, the Von Neumann utility function [329] and a risk management marginal utility function (see [72] for more details). However, the utility functions (a way to evaluate proposals) are not fundamental to this work, since the negotiation between agents is not in its scope.

In a systematic way, risk management can be divided into the three phases illustrated in Figure 6.1 [159, 160]:

1. Risk assessment: identification of risk factors. Involves mainly the identification of deterministic and stochastic variables.
2. Risk characterization: measuring or assessing risk. Several different methods can be used. The most common, and accepted in financial markets, is the value at risk (VaR), also used in electricity markets. Another complementary concept, not so used in financial markets, is the conditional value at risk (CVaR).
3. Risk mitigation: mitigation or hedging, which is the application of the market product in the portfolio that allows to reduce the risk to which retailers are subject to, such as forwards, futures or CfDs (contracts for differences), under the customers' consumption patterns that are assumed as random or stochastic variables in the input of the system.

By following these phases, retailers are able to decide if they will invest in the electricity market, and which type of customers they will persuade to become their clients (decision making).

6.6 Optimization of the Portfolio of Clients

6.6.1 The problem

Consider a retailer operating in an electricity market constituted by several consumers with different load profiles. The retailer wants to sign a forward contract with a set of consumers, and then to satisfy their energy needs, submits bids to buy energy at the pool market (day-ahead market). Taking into account the aforementioned phases of the risk management process, the following risk factors can be considered: day-ahead market price volatility, variability of electricity consumption of end-use customers, duration and prices of the forward contracts tariffs. Thus, more formally, we consider a retailer *Ret* and j consumers c_1, \dots, c_j . The retailer wants to maximize the risk-return output by selecting the optimal set of consumers.

The VaR method is adopted in this work to measure the risk factors. VaR measures the potential losses of a retailer to a certain degree of confidence in a given time interval. A limitation of this method is the failure to know the potential losses that may exist above the value of VaR. To deal with this limitation, the CVaR method was also considered. The CVaR is based on the weighted average of losses with a probability higher than that of VaR. If the VaR and CVaR account for possible losses, methods based on variance account for the scatter of values, not only losses but also possible gains. The mitigation phase is conducted by our optimization model. By dealing with the risk factors, and taking into account their measurement and the specific retailer's risk attitude, we can obtain the optimized portfolio that follows the interests of the retailer, based on a risk-return analysis.

6.6.2 Tariff Definition

The electricity tariff is a non-linear or multi-part tariff. More precisely, a two-part tariff that consists of a fixed payment for power or fee (contracted capacity), regardless of consumption, where the fee increases with the required contracted capacity, plus a price per unit of electricity (variable fee). Both fees are divided into several parts. The fixed fee is divided into the grid access, global use of the system (costs arising from energy or environmental policy measures, or measures with a general economic interest, and costs from the maintenance of the contractual balance), and others. The variable fee includes the grid access, the global use of the system, and the commercialization part as well as the energy part (the only one that reflects the market prices) [144, 330].

At regulated markets, the fixed and variable fees could be discriminatory, depending on the type of grid connection of each consumer, i.e., very high voltage consumers pay less than high voltage customers, high voltage pay less than medium voltage, and so on. To supply a low voltage consumer, the major part of the electricity comes from large power plants connected to the high voltage grid (transmission grid), pass by substations in order to decrease voltage, and then reach the distribution grid that

supply the energy at medium and low voltages at the distributed network.

At liberalized markets, the energy part of the variable fee could also be discriminatory, and normally depends on several factors: the type of consumers, i.e., large (industrial) or small (domestic), the degree of risk of consumers (low or high), and also the return of consumers (short or large). Taking into account the different types of consumers, retailers could establish a return tax (r) for each consumer, according to the following:

$$r = R_F + R_P \quad (6.1)$$

where R_F is the risk-free of the global markets (e.g., treasury bonds or deposits) and R_P is the risk-premium, that depends on several factors, such as the risk associated with EMs and consumers.

Retailers can have several strategies to persuade consumers at the liberalized market. Currently in Portugal, in the domestic sector, retailers are making discounts at the fixed rate, keeping unchanged the variable rate. In the future, a different strategy could consider a discount equal to the fixed cost, i.e., eliminate the fixed cost and increase the variable cost (which could be favorable for residential consumers with more than one house), making the electricity tariff linear. Some researchers could question if the power guarantee (contracted capacity) will be an issue, but we believe it is not, since consumers that have low or null fixed costs in their tariff will pay more for the variable costs.

Now, an obvious thing to do in order to persuade more consumers, is to charge different fixed fees to different consumers or classes of consumers. In short, to consider “discriminatory” two-part tariffs (including quantity discounts and self-selection tariffs), tailoring the fixed fee to the consumers’ willingness to pay, where the sum of the fixed parts should add up to the fixed value that retailers have to pay, ensuring their return in relation to the variable fee.

In this paper, we place the focus on the energy term of the variable fee, considering the other terms fixed (and also a fixed fee equal for all consumers, not given any return to the retailer). Several types of tariffs can be offered. For domestic consumers, the most common are the following: single tariff (equal during all day), two-rate tariff (peak during the day and off-peak at night), three-rate (peak, intermediate and off-peak), and a four-rate tariff (peak, intermediate, off-peak and super off-peak). Commercial and industrial consumers connected to the high voltage or very-high voltage grid can also have a 24-rate tariff.

6.6.3 Pricing Strategies

This subsection presents some pricing strategies that could be adopted by a retailer while negotiating with consumers. These strategies are differentiated by the type of tariff (single, dual, 3-rate, etc.), equality of tariff (“discriminatory” or not), equality of return (if every consumer gives a similar return to retailer), etc.

1. Equal return optimization strategy.

This strategy calculates the different tariffs that a retailer *Ret* can offer to clients in order to receive an equal return from each:

$$T_{j,h} = \frac{r \cdot \bar{C} \sum_{j=1}^J \sum_{h=1}^H q_{j,h} + \sum_{j=1}^J \sum_{h=1}^H q_{j,h} C_h}{\sum_{h=1}^H q_{j,h} K_h} \quad (6.2)$$

where:

- (i) $T_{j,h}$ is the prices of the tariff charged for consumer j at period h ;
- (ii) r is the retailer's intended return (in percentage);
- (iii) \bar{C} is the mean of the retailer's cost with the purchase of electricity;
- (iv) C_h is the Retailer's cost per period h ;
- (v) $q_{j,h}$ is the electricity consumption of the consumer j in period h ;
- (vi) K_h is the period discriminator, in case of existing several periods (i.e., when the retailer wants to give more value to peak periods); otherwise, it is equal to one for all periods.

2. Equal tariff optimization strategy at a minimum return.

This strategy calculates the minimum prices of the tariff that a retailer *Ret* can offer to every client in order to guarantee that *Ret* receives a specific target return:

$$[T_h] = \begin{bmatrix} T_{1,h} \\ \dots \\ T_{j,h} \end{bmatrix} \quad (6.3)$$

$$T_h = \max [T_{j,h}] \quad (6.4)$$

where:

- (i) $[T_h]$ is a matrix containing all the tariffs charged for every consumer at period h ;
- (ii) T_h is the minimum prices of each tariff that *Ret* needs to charge in order to receive the intended return;

3. Equal tariff optimization at a maximum return.

This strategy is similar to the previous one. The main difference is that it calculates the tariff that, at best, gives to a retailer *Ret* the intended return:

$$T_h = \min [T_{j,h}] \quad (6.5)$$

4. Minimize the VaR of a tariff at a minimum return.

This pricing strategy analysis the dynamic of every consumption profile and tries to adapt the tariff to them by solving an optimization problem that has the objective of minimizing the VaR at a given return.

5. Random tariffs statistically distributed.

This strategy follows a distribution (such as normal or uniform), and by defining the price limits for every consumer period, as well as the average price of the tariff, it randomly chooses every consumer tariff.

6.6.4 The Optimization Problem

The dual-objective (multi-criteria) optimization aims at computing the point that optimizes (risk-return analysis) the retailers' portfolio of clients taking into account the tariff and the risk attitude (λ). The problem is formulated as follows:

$$[w] = \max_{w_j \geq 0} \left([w]^T [\gamma] [r] - \left(\frac{\lambda}{2} \right) [w]^T [Cov] [w] \right) \quad (6.6)$$

Subject to

$$\sum_{j=1}^J w_j = 1 \quad (6.7)$$

where:

- (i) $[w]$ is the matrix containing the weight w_j of each consumer j in the retailer's portfolio of clients;
- (ii) $[\gamma]$ is the matrix containing the relative difference between the arithmetic cost of electricity of the used data and a future prediction of the arithmetic cost of electricity for each consumer j ;
- (iii) $[r]$ is the matrix of the expected return of each consumer j ;
- (iv) $[Cov]$ is the covariance matrix that relates the consumption between every consumer j .

The constraint (6.7) guarantees that the sum of the weights of each client in the portfolio does not exceed 100%. The risk attitude (λ) of each retailer agent is very important to solve this dual-objective optimization problem, because it unbalances the importance of risk and return for each agent. Specifically, risk-averse agents give more importance to risk minimization and risk-seeking agents want to maximize the expected return. In order to obtain the $[\gamma]$ matrix, we use a forecasting method to predict the arithmetic cost of each consumer j in the future contract.

6.6.5 Forecasting of Electricity Prices

In this section, we slightly describe a forecast method for obtaining a prediction of future long-term electricity prices, regarding the following variables:

- Market price (P);

- Electricity consumption (E);
- Renewable energy share associated with electricity production (RES%).

Other variables, such as GDP (Gross domestic product) and the Population, can be used, but they are already reflected in the electricity consumption (which is commonly forecasted taking into account these variables). Different forecasting methods can be used: Historical Trends (growth rate forecast), Univariate Time series (UTS) and Multivariate Time series (MTS). In this work, we use the following MTS method:

$$P_t = \sum_{i=1}^L \chi_i P_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^M \beta_i E_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^K \delta_i RES\%_{t-1} + \epsilon_t \quad (6.8)$$

where:

- (i) P_t is the forecasting result for electricity price for year t ;
- (ii) L , M and K are the lags (number of previous periods);
- (iii) χ_i , β_i and δ_i are regression variables.
- (iv) ϵ_t is the error from random events.

6.6.6 The Markowitz Efficient Frontier

In order to obtain the Markowitz efficient frontier [327] that optimizes the retailer's portfolio of clients, we present next an optimization model (see Figure 6.2).

The process follows the three-phase risk management procedure described in Figure 6.1. In the first phase, it is important to analyze the different types of markets to buy electricity, in terms of both dynamics and risk. At this stage, it is also important to check all types of consumers, analyzing their load profiles, and verifying their types of tariffs (prices and duration).

The Markowitz theory was created to optimize the portfolio of assets. For specific target assets of the stock exchange, taking into account the value of each asset and its historical volatility, we can obtain a single frontier with several optimized points (each point consists in a different share of assets in the portfolio). This task involves a risk-return optimization taking into account the risk attitude of each investor. Risk-averse investors tend to prefer portfolios involving lower risk. On the other hand, risk-seeking investors tend to prefer portfolios with high expected returns.

In this work, we adapt this theory to our optimization process. The objective is to obtain an efficient frontier with several points, each corresponding to a group (or share) of end-use electricity consumers of a retailer's portfolio (see Figure 6.2). As a retailer Ret is negotiating contracts for the future, and has an infinite number of options to define tariffs, the degree of uncertainty and complexity increases when compared to a portfolio of assets. In the beginning of the process, all variables are uncertain (tariff, day-ahead market prices and quantities), but by using the pricing strategies, Ret can define competitive tariffs to offer to consumers. We note that in the assets portfolio optimization, the price of acquisition

Figure 6.2: Main steps of the portfolio optimization model

(fixed) of each asset is known, while in our model we only can know (compute) the tariffs to offer to each consumer, obtaining an infinite number. Accordingly, we obtain multiple Markowitz curves (but see the first case-study, in section 6.8.1). The efficient frontier is then obtained by identifying the points of each curve (again, see the first case-study). Also, the complexity of both processes is different. While in the portfolio of assets only the future price of the asset (selling price) is unknown, in this work the selling price (tariff) is the only known variable (the acquisition price and the quantity of electricity to buy are uncertain).

In the second phase, we verify how the previous variables interact. There are several ways of doing this, like correlation and regression, but VaR is one of the most used. The VaR can be calculated in a non-parametric form (historical data and Monte Carlo simulations) or in a parametric way (using variance and covariance). In this work, we use a parametric way for computing the VaR. Specifically, the VaR is computed using the following formula [331]:

$$VaR = -I \cdot r^* = I(\alpha\sigma\sqrt{\Delta t} - \mu\Delta t) \quad (6.9)$$

where:

- (i) I is the investment made by the retailer (necessary money to buy the energy);
- (ii) r^* is the cutoff return (the percentage of the investment that is at risk);
- (iii) α , σ and μ are the confidence level, the standard deviation and the average of the expected return, respectively;

(iv) Δt is the time interval considered (duration of the contract).

At the third phase, the retailer *Ret* should define the intended return, the risk attitude and the tariff strategy. Next, *Ret* proceeds to the iterative process, where analyzes the optimized points of all the tariffs obtained in terms of risk-return. At the end, *Ret* defines the efficient frontier, from the different efficient points. A point is considered efficient if no other point can surpass its result in terms of risk and return.

The efficient frontier is obtained by considering the conditions of the market defined in the first phase, the risk analysis carried out in the second phase, and the risk attitude and pricing strategies defined in the third stage. A small variation in the assumptions made in this phase could conduct to relevant changes in the final result.

Figure 6.3 shows an example of a Markowitz frontier. Several tariffs were analysed, each one represented by a square. The efficient points are represented by dark black squares. The trend line of the Markowitz efficient frontier was obtained by a regression. For every tariff, was obtained the optimal share (weight) of customers of the retailer's portfolio. So, each square represents a tariff computed by the pricing strategies of section 6.6.3 and an optimal division of customers obtained by the optimization problem of section 6.6.4.

To summarize, as shown in Figure 6.2, the process has several steps. First (top box), there is a need to make choices and single computations (covariance matrix), and at the repetitive part (grey box), to perform various computations. The number of iterations depends on the number of tariffs, obtained using the pricing strategies. Taking into account every input tariff, we compute the return and gamma matrices and then the optimal consumers' weight at the portfolio, the expected return and the VaR of the portfolio. At the end of the process, for every tariff, we check if the point obtained (given by the expected return and VaR) is efficient (better VaR and/or expected return when compared to other points), eliminating the inefficient points. The several efficient points are isolated and the efficient curve that connects them is defined, i.e., we obtain the Markowitz frontier (see Figure 6.3).

In order to speed up the process, it will be interesting to consider the case of a retailer with specific objectives in terms of the risk-return relation. In Figure 6.4, by imposing limits, we can verify that a retailer can *a priori* reject a relevant number of optimized points, ensuring that the process of obtaining the efficient frontier will be faster.

A retailer can adopt a strategy with multi-criteria in order to obtain the maximum benefit of the optimization process and achieve its objectives.

6.7 Multi-agent system

The principal components of the multi-agent system under development include a graphical user interface (GUI), a simulation mechanism, and a number of domain-specific agents. The graphical user interface allows users to set agent-specific parameters, specify and monitor trading simulations, and perform a variety of administrative tasks such as saving simulations (see Figure 6.5). The simulation mechanism does not depend on any domain-specific knowledge and controls all trading simulations.

Figure 6.3: Markowitz frontier

The agents represent typical market players, including generating companies (GenCos), retailers (RetailCos), aggregators, large and small consumers, coalitions (where two or more consumers make an alliance), the market operator and the system operator. GenCos may own a single power plant or a portfolio of plants of different technologies. RetailCos buy electricity in a wholesale market and re-sell it to consumers in a retail market. Large consumers can take an active role in the market by buying electricity in the pool or by signing bilateral contracts. Small consumers buy electricity from retailers and possibly other market participants. Consumer coalitions are entities that support alliances of end-use customers with the objective of trading electricity. The market operator collects the bids to buy energy and the offers to sell energy and determines the market clearing price. The system operator receives the accepted bids and offers and checks for their feasibility, informing the market operator of the results. The agents are currently being developed using the JAVA programming language and the JADE platform [55].

The current version of the system supports pool trading (a day-ahead market and an intra-day market), bilateral contracting of electrical energy (notably, forward contracts and CfDs) and balancing markets (secondary band and tertiary reserve). In the day-ahead market, RetailCos make offers to buy electricity and GenCos make bids to sell electricity in advance of time when the electricity is produced and consumed. The market operator can use the SMP (system marginal pricing) or LMP (locational marginal pricing) algorithms to obtain the market clearing price [12, 63]. Bilateral contracts can be either physical or financial. Buyer and seller agents are equipped with a negotiation framework [112, 325] and are able to negotiate the terms and conditions of bilateral contracts [72, 73]. At the secondary band, the system operator computes the required quantity of power band required to guarantee the security of the system and makes offers for it. At the tertiary reserve market, the system operator computes the required quantity of energy to be balanced and makes offers for it. In order to demonstrate how the simulations were performed, a description of the main steps required to optimize the portfolio of clients

Figure 6.4: Risk-return limits

of a new retailer agent follows (see also Figure 6.5):

1. Start the multi-agent system.
2. Create a new retailer agent: go to menu “New → Retailers”. Choose a name for the retailer. Check the agent’s information and select “Next” to input data in the third pane. The agent is created in the Jade platform and introduced to the system GUI (parts 3, 4 and 5 of Figure 6.5).
3. The portfolio’s pane (part 6 of Figure 6.5): in this pane the user can:
 - (a) Select the consumers and add them to the portfolio. We consider clusters of five different types of consumers (industrial, large and small commercial, residential and street lighting). We have data for one year of consumption, normalized in pu (per unit). By taking into account the consumption amplitude (maximum and minimum power), we adapt our clusters to real consumption patterns.
 - (b) Select the “Markowitz” button: perform the optimization of a portfolio of clients using the Markowitz theory. In order to perform this optimization, we consider a database with the day-ahead Iberian Market prices (see Figure 6.5).
4. Add consumers to perform a portfolio optimization: in this panel (part 8 of Figure 6.5), there is the possibility to choose the characteristics (standard or adapted demand) and the types of consumers to consider in the portfolio.
5. Choose Markowitz optimization options: the user may choose the type of pricing strategy to use, the number of periods of the tariffs, and the optimization objectives. For the particular case of the optimization objectives, the user has the possibility to choose the minimum expected return, the maximum expected VaR, the risk attitude and the frontier that he/she does not want to transpose. In relation to this optimization, the user has two options:

Figure 6.5: Multi-agent system: steps for determining the portfolio of clients of a new retailer

- (a) Frontier optimization: obtain a frontier (linear, exponential or logarithmic, taking into account the square root error of the performed regressions) with one or more optimal points, and then select one.
 - (b) Point optimization: perform the optimization problem that automatically selects the optimal risk-return point (optimal portfolio) taking into account the optimization objectives (the options chosen).
6. Check the optimization results: this panel (part 10 of Figure 6.5) gives information about the optimization results (expected return and variance, such as the tariffs and the number and share of consumers in the portfolio).
 7. Select portfolio: by saving the optimization results, the user returns to a panel (part 12 of Figure 6.5) where he/she can add more consumers, perform new “Markowitz” simulations or simply save the portfolio.

After a simulation, the user can start negotiating with consumers. What he/she can also do, by using the optimization model and the MAS, is to “load” a retailer with a portfolio of clients and check if the portfolio can be improved by adding new consumers. Also he/she can check the effects (risk-return analysis) of adding new consumers to the portfolio. Whether the effects are positive or negative, the user can change the retailer’s behavior during the negotiation, either to a more cooperative or more competitive attitude [22]. However, as stated earlier, these aspects are not in the scope of this work.

6.8 Case Studies on Portfolio Optimization

The following three case studies illustrate how retailers can choose optimal portfolios of clients depending on their risk attitude and pricing strategies (i.e., the tariffs offered to consumers). Each case-study involves a specific retailer agent, namely James Owen (a software agent), CEO of Retail Energy Service, an experienced electricity retailer in Europe that is studying the Portuguese electricity market in order to start operating on it. James Owen buys energy in the electricity pool, more specifically in the MIBEL’s day-ahead market, and sells it through bilateral contracts to several consumers. The contract duration is set to one year. The risk factors are the dynamics of the day-ahead market (how prices fluctuate every day, from work days to weekends and holidays, and from winter to summer time), the consumption patterns in Portugal, and the types of tariffs offered. Also, some values considered in the case studies were selected by looking up to real trading prices associated with the pool market in an attempt to approximate them to the real-world. The day-ahead market prices and the consumption data are from 2011 (real data from the Iberian Market). Specifically, the retailer’s energy cost per hour is equal to the market reference price per hour. The market reference price was obtained through an analysis of MIBEL’s day-ahead prices. The case studies involve a one-year optimization problem, i.e., James Owen studies the load profile of each client and the hourly market prices for 2012.

We consider five types of consumption profiles: residential (Res), small commercial (SCom), large commercial (LCom), industrial (Ind) and street lighting (SL). Residential consumers are essentially do-

Table 6.2: Regulated tariff (energy part of the variable term) for electricity in Portugal in 2012 [330]

Voltage Level	Tariff (€/MWh)		
	base	intermediate	peak
High voltage (HV)	46.75	65.10	76.40
Medium voltage (MV)	48.85	67.90	80.10
Low voltage commercial (LVC)	55.00	73.00	83.60
Low voltage residential (LVR)	58.20	73.00	84.10

mestic consumers with a consumption peak outside the common working hours and weekends. Small commercials are local traders, small offices and shops of the service sector that usually have their peak consumption at working time. Large commercial consumers consist of office buildings, shopping centers and large commercial shops in the service sector. Industrial players consist of factories from industrial and other sectors. Street lighting consumers are only lit during the evening and overnight (see [71] for more details).

In Portugal, the liberalization of the electricity sector will be totally finished in 2018 (only the domestic sector is not completely liberalized yet, but consumers will be required to change until 2018). Table 6.2 shows the energy part of the variable term of the regulated tariff in Portugal for each level of the grid connection in 2012. In this year, for domestic consumers, the weight of the energy part of the variable term was 41.2%, while the grid access, the global use of the system, and the commercialization part, had a weight of 30.1%, 26.2% and 2.5%, respectively [330]. The Regulator still plays an important role in pricing by defining both the fixed and the variable reference tariffs (see Table 6.2). Accordingly, retailers in general still adopt a moderate approach in the market, proposing the variable reference (or regulated) term of the tariff to consumers, and making a small discount on the fixed reference term. Some retailers have already started offering small discounts on the variable term. However, this strategy is not common (when compared to offering discounts on the fixed term).

In the following case studies, we adopt a different approach. We maintain the fixed term of the tariff (we offer the regulated fixed term), and study different ways to offer more competitive values to the variable term. So, in order to not differentiate too much between regulation and competition, we follow a general tariff approach.

The objective of the case studies is to demonstrate how retailers can offer more competitive tariffs by being more restricted on the type and share of consumers, thus decreasing the desired risk premium (expected return) due to a reduction of the portfolio's VaR, while also obtaining efficient portfolios (risk-return optimization). This discriminatory way of persuading specific type of customers can guarantee more stable portfolios in terms of types of consumers, expected return and VaR, when compared to portfolios with no restrictions. Traditional retailers, i.e., retailers that accept every type of consumer and make small discounts on the reference tariffs, suffer of a high volatility in their portfolios, since consumers are always looking for more competitive tariffs and can change retailer easily.

The first case-study considers a non-discriminatory pricing strategy by offering an equal tariff to every consumer, with the objective of obtaining a minimum expected return (see the second strategy of section 6.6.3). This case-study illustrates the functionality of the model (see Fig 6.2). In particular, it illustrates how to obtain the portfolio's points to draw the Markowitz curves, as well as the Markowitz frontier, through a regression of the efficient points of all Markowitz curves.

The second case-study aims at improving the results of the first case-study by considering a “discriminatory tariff”, i.e., considers the possibility to offer different tariffs to consumers. First, we try to obtain different tariffs to every type of consumer that give similar expected returns to the retailer (see the first strategy of section 6.6.3). Then, to further improve the results, we perform a second simulation by using a strategy to minimize the VaR of the portfolio (see the fourth strategy of section 6.6.3) and combine it with the strategy used in the first case-study (see the second strategy of section 6.6.3). The results are slightly better than that of the first simulation. It is worth mentioning that the use of different pricing strategies leads to different Markowitz frontiers.

The third case-study considers a method to predict the arithmetic cost of every consumer (in the previous case studies the $[\gamma]$ matrix was the identity matrix), and also a “discriminatory tariff” (by taking into account the strategies used in the second simulation of the second case study). Again, the aim is to improve the results of the previous two case studies. Also, this case-study aims at both illustrating and testing the model.

For all case studies, and regarding the day-ahead prices, it was studied the yearly fluctuation of the prices which affect the covariance matrix in the optimization formulation, the calculation of the expected return and the VaR.

6.8.1 Case Study I: Equal tariff pricing strategy

The retailer agent offers a generic 3-rate tariff, with a fixed difference between the rate of each period (the same of the regulated tariff), in order to compute the share of the total energy to sell to each client. The tariff considers the usual 3-rate tariff in Portugal (winter time):

- Peak price (2.14 times the base price): from 9 a.m. to 12 a.m. and from 6 p.m. to 9 p.m.;
- Intermediate price (1.70 times the base price): from 7 a.m. to 9 a.m., from 12 a.m. to 6 p.m., and from 9 p.m. to 12 p.m.;
- Base price: from 12 p.m. to 7 a.m.

James Owen uses the “equal tariff” strategy (equation 6.3) and sets the period rates in accordance with the global demand, i.e., more expensive in periods where the demand is higher, cheaper when it is lower, following the regulated tariff difference.

In order to be competitive, Owen must propose a tariff lower than or equal to the regulated tariff in Portugal (see Table 6.2). Figure 6.6 presents the Markowitz curves of eleven different tariffs calculated by using the aforementioned pricing strategy. Every point of each Markowitz curve represents a different weight (percentage) of each consumer load profile (cluster) in the portfolio. The first tariff is the minimal

Figure 6.6: Markowitz curves

Figure 6.7: Markowitz efficient frontier

tariff that Owen can consider with a positive return. However, this agent only starts to obtain a positive return after the fourth point (portfolio division) of the first curve.

It is worth mentioning that not all points of the Markowitz curves are efficient (only those that limit the curves). Figure 6.7 and Table 6.3 present the positive points of the Markowitz efficient frontier and their respective tariffs in terms of risk-return and portfolio division.

Notice that, although one tariff could be higher than another, the return could be lower, because the portfolio of clients may be different. By observing Figure 6.7, we can verify that the considered market is a good market to invest, because large differences in return result in small differences in VaR (i.e., a large increase in the expected return leads to a small increase in the expected VaR).

In Table 6.3, we can verify that all tariffs calculated by James Owen are competitive and, on average, are above the regulated tariffs. Only for consumers directly connected to the high voltage grid, the peak tariffs after point seven are higher (see Figure 6.7). Comparing this highest tariff with the regulated tariffs, we can conclude that the former gives a discount of 7.7% to HV (Industrial) and 22.3% to LVR (Residential) consumers.

Table 6.3: Results of case study I: energy division by each client type using the “equal tariff” strategy

Tariff (€/MWh)			Energy share (%)			Return	VaR
base	inter	peak	SCom	SL	Ind	%	%
33.56	57.06	71.89	25.54	74.46	0.00	1.12	8.86
34.17	58.08	73.18	22.43	77.56	0.00	2.55	8.98
33.87	57.57	72.54	40.18	59.82	0.00	3.88	9.10
34.47	58.60	73.83	32.70	67.30	0.00	4.77	9.15
34.77	59.11	74.48	39.89	60.11	0.00	6.62	9.29
35.07	59.62	75.12	42.91	57.09	0.00	7.93	9.40
35.37	60.13	75.77	45.73	54.27	0.00	9.22	9.47
35.67	60.65	76.41	48.36	51.64	0.00	10.51	9.58
35.98	61.16	77.06	42.26	55.74	0.00	10.63	9.59
36.28	61.67	77.71	44.81	55.19	0.00	11.90	9.68
36.58	62.18	78.35	41.65	50.27	8.10	13.40	9.78

Increasing the return of the tariffs leads to small changes in the share of consumers: small commercial consumers vary from 22.43% to 48.36% and street lighting consumers from 50.27% to 77.56%. This result could be estimated by observing the matrices of variance-covariance and the expected return of each tariff.

The “equal tariff” pricing strategy conducts the retailer to focus on clients that increase the expected return and decrease the VaR, and also to different clients that reduce the risk of the two aforementioned types (risk mitigation), due to their type of consumption. The type of consumers that gives the highest expected return is the small commercial and the one that gives less risk is the street lighting. Retailers that want small returns have portfolios of SL and SCom consumers (more SL than SCom consumers). On the other hand, retailers that want high returns decrease the weight of SL consumers (in relation to SCom and Industrial consumers). These two conclusions consider moderate risk-averse retailers. For higher risk-averse agents, the percentage of SL consumers should be higher. On the other hand, for risk-seeking agents the percentage of SCom consumers should be higher. Also, for risk-averse retailers to obtain an expected return similar to that of risk-seeking retailers, there is a need to propose higher tariffs to consumers, thus increasing the difficulty of persuading them.

A key issue associated with this pricing strategy is that it suggests only SL and SCom consumers (as an efficient point for the portfolio). This occurs due to the characteristics of the retailer, the consumers and the tariff. The retailer is a moderate risk-averse agent, so it prefers to minimize the risk rather than maximizing the return. simply put, using the “equal tariff” pricing strategy, James Owen has a good basis to make offers to small commercial and street lighting consumers. However, another strategy should be considered in order to obtain good tariffs (in terms of risk-return) to offer to the other three types of consumers.

Figure 6.8: Markowitz efficient frontiers

Now, residential consumers are highly unpredictable, so they will increase the VaR of the portfolio, and their consumptions are small in relation to that of other consumers, and thus only in cases of high returns they will be desirable for the retailer. So, “discriminatory” tariffs or risk hedging measures (such as risk sharing [72]), should be used in order for this type of consumers be interesting for an optimized portfolio. Large commercial consumers have the problem of their consumption be correlated with small commercial consumers, but in a more high level of consumption. So, it will be hard for a moderate risk-averse agent to accept these two types of consumers without risk mitigation measures (risk sharing; see, for example, [72]).

6.8.2 Case Study II - Personalized pricing strategies

This case study “discriminates” consumers in order to increase the risk-return results and also considers other types of consumers in the optimized portfolio (in relation to the previous case-study). We consider two simulations and use three different pricing strategies. In the first simulation, we use the “equal return optimization” strategy (see the second strategy of section 6.6.2). It takes into account the market expected prices and the expected return of the retailer’s investment in order to obtain the tariff that guarantees an expected return with a VaR lower than the one obtained with the previous pricing strategy (for a three-rate tariff).

In order to try to improve the efficient frontier, we consider a second simulation, where we use two different strategies. The “minimize the VaR of a tariff at a minimum return” pricing strategy (see the third strategy of section 6.6.2) involves all consumers, except consumers of the type SCom. For SCom consumers, we use the “equal tariff” strategy, i.e., the strategy considered in the first case study. By using the “minimize the VaR of a tariff at a minimum return” strategy, a retailer aims at obtaining the tariff that minimizes the VaR of the consumers, for a target return.

The use of the two strategies together improves the efficient frontier (see the green triangles in Figure 6.8), but the optimized points of the frontier only consider SCom and SL consumers for the portfolio. Industrial and LCom consumers have higher electricity consumptions, and although they may lead to a

Table 6.4: Results of case study II: energy division by each client type using the “equal tariff” (SCom Tariff) and the “minimize the VaR of a tariff at a minimum return” (SL Tariff) strategies

SCom Tariff (€/MWh)			SL Tariff	Energy share (%)		Return	VaR
base	inter	peak	single	SCom	SL	%	%
33.56	57.06	71.89	48.82	10.65	89.35	1.11	8.39
34.17	58.08	73.18	49.32	13.81	86.19	2.59	8.51
33.87	57.57	72.54	49.83	19.16	80.84	3.86	8.64
34.47	58.60	73.83	50.08	20.53	79.47	4.80	8.70
34.77	59.11	74.48	50.33	31.20	68.80	6.61	8.88
35.07	59.62	75.12	50.84	33.85	66.15	7.94	8.99
35.37	60.13	75.77	51.34	36.54	63.46	9.25	9.10
35.67	60.65	76.41	51.85	38.21	61.79	10.46	9.19
35.98	61.16	77.06	51.90	38.51	61.49	10.94	9.20
36.28	61.67	77.71	52.35	38.64	61.36	11.91	9.27
36.58	62.18	78.35	52.86	42.48	57.52	13.39	9.39

higher expected return (in absolute terms), they are also more risky (increase the portfolio’s VaR). So, some risk sharing measures [72] should be taken into account to include these type of consumers in the optimized portfolio. Residential consumers typically lead to small absolute returns and have a higher variance than the other consumers. Since they give a large margin to the retailer (see Table 6.2), to include them in the optimized portfolio, the retailer should increase the tariffs, increasing the expected return of these consumers (in relation to others).

By using the “minimize the VaR of a tariff at a minimum return” strategy, we obtain a single tariff for SL consumers (see Table 6.4), which together with the pricing strategy used in the first case study (resulting in the tariff for SCom consumers), leads to better results, when compared with the results of the others simulations.

Taking into account that exist multiple pricing strategies that retailers could adopt in order to optimize their portfolio of clients, these results could also be improved, by not imposing any restrictions on the tariff discretization, and performing an optimization with the objective of obtaining the set of tariffs that minimize the VaR for a given expected return.

6.8.3 Case Study III - Personalized pricing strategy with a forecasting of the arithmetic cost of consumers

In this case study, we perform a simulation similar to the previous one, but include the values for the $[\gamma]$ matrix, obtained through the analysis of the day-ahead prices, electricity consumptions, and the share of renewable generation in the production of electricity between 2005 and 2011, in Portugal. Taking into account the different patterns of consumption of consumers, we obtain the arithmetic cost of each consumer for every year. Then we compute the forecasting of the arithmetic cost for 2012 (see

Table 6.5: Results of case study III: energy division by each client type using the “equal tariff” (SCom Tariff) and the “minimize the VaR of a tariff at a minimum return” (SL Tariff) strategies

SCom Tariff (€/MWh)			SL Tariff	Energy share (%)		Return	VaR
base	inter	peak	single	SCom	SL	%	%
33.46	56.88	71.67	50.07	7.16	92.84	10.02	9.04
33.66	57.21	72.09	50.43	10.14	89.86	11.04	9.17
33.88	57.60	72.57	50.76	13.01	86.99	12.00	9.25
34.14	58.03	73.13	51.09	15.97	84.03	12.98	9.33

section 6.6.5). After that, we obtain the $[\gamma]$ matrix (to resolve the optimization problem introduced in section 6.6.4).

In relation to 2011, we predict that the arithmetic cost of every consumer will be reduced between 3.4% (residential) and 6.7% (street lightning). This reduction is mainly due to the reductions in both the electricity consumption and the day-ahead market prices from 2009 to 2011, because of the economic crises, and also the increase of the renewable energy share in the electricity production since 2005 (the beginning of the data). In this case-study, we also consider the constraint that the expected return has to be higher than 10%.

6.8.4 Simulations Results

Table 6.5 shows the main results. By comparing the results of Table 6.5 with the results obtained in the previous case study (Table 6.4), SL is the type of consumer with a large share in the optimized portfolio, and also the type more affected with the predicted decrease in the day-head prices for 2012, thus the retailer can offer a more competitive tariff for 2012 (when compared to the reference tariffs in Table 6.2). Also, comparing, for example, the fourth tariff of Table 6.4 with the first tariff of Table 6.5, although they are almost equal for SL consumers, due to the introduction of the price prediction methodology, the latter has an expected return about 5% higher.

Analysis and discussion of the results

This section examines the real return of the retailer by considering both the optimized portfolios proposed above and real data from the MIBEL's day-head market. From 2011 to 2012, the average market prices decreased around 5% and the arithmetic cost of the consumers was around 3.1%, for residential consumers, and 5.3%, for SL consumers, a lower decrease when compared with the forecasts. Table 6.6 shows the real return of the optimized portfolio of consumers, using real data from 2012.

Due to the differences between the forecasts and the real values, the real return is about 2% lower (when compared with the expected return). This illustrates the importance of forecasting the market prices and also their volatility. Price volatility leads to an increase in the risk premium because retailers are subject to high uncertainty in relation to market prices and consumers consumption. One form of

Table 6.6: Results Test: Real return for the year 2012

SCom Tariff (€/MWh)			SL Tariff	Energy share (%)		Real Return
base	inter	peak	single	SCom	SL	%
33.46	56.88	71.67	50.07	7.16	92.84	7.88
33.66	57.21	72.09	50.43	10.14	89.86	8.89
33.88	57.60	72.57	50.76	13.01	86.99	9.84
34.14	58.03	73.13	51.09	15.97	84.03	10.82

retailers hedging against spot price volatility is by signing forward contracts to purchase electricity (but, although interesting, this approach is out of the scope of this work).

Now, taking into account other existing approaches to solve the problem of optimizing the portfolios of retailers, the use of deterministic approaches to obtain the optimized portfolio conduct to poor results, since they do not consider the influence of the uncertainty in both the market prices and the consumers consumption. For example, if we consider a risk-neutral retailer ($\lambda = 0$) and use the model to obtain an optimal portfolio of consumers, we are assuming that this portfolio is risk free and basically considering an investment in a portfolio close to a deposit with a guaranteed return tax. So, we want to invest in the deposit with the highest return tax. By considering the risk of contracts and using our model, the optimized portfolio consists only in Small Commercial consumers, because they maximize the return of the portfolio (more than 15% of return when using the first tariff of Table 6.5). However, this result lacks realism, since there is uncertainty and thus a need to perform a risk-return analysis to obtain consistent results.

In [71], we present a deterministic optimization model to solve the portfolio method. However, we used it to obtain the portfolio of consumers that maximizes the profit in a specif week. This kind of approach can be used when all information is known (risk free) and to make some optimizations taking into account past results. The optimization of a portfolio of consumers for the near future should be done by using a risk-return optimization.

So, we can use the deterministic model [71] to obtain the optimized portfolio since we have real data for 2012. Accordingly, the first tariff of Table 6.5, that gives an expected return of 10.02% and a real return of 7.88%, will give a return higher than 15%, if we consider 98% of Small Commercial, 1.5% of Industrial and 0.5% of Large Commercial consumers. This result is slightly different to the results obtained with the optimization model proposed in the current article for a risk-neutral retailer, because in the deterministic model we considered that the retailer can only comply with a maximum value for consumption, V_{max} . So, since it cannot have more Small Commercial consumers, because it will surpass the limit, to maximize the profit it also considers Large Commercial and Industrial consumers. This occurs due to the following: if, for example, a SCom consumer gives a return of 15% but a profit of 1000 mu (monetary units) and an Industrial consumer gives a return of 5% but a profit of 5000 mu, an optimization model that has the objective of increasing the return (as the model proposed here), for a risk-neutral agent, will obtain 100%

SCom consumers. And, otherwise, if it has the goal of increasing the profit (as the deterministic model proposed in [71]) it will obtain 100% Industrial consumers.

6.9 Conclusion

This article has presented a formal description of a model for optimizing the retailers' portfolio of clients. Also, this article has presented an overview of a multi-agent system to simulate energy markets, placing emphasis on the interaction between retailers and end-use customers. In addition, the article has presented three case-studies to test the optimization model using real data from the Iberian electricity market (MIBEL). The model was tested by considering a moderate risk-averse retailer agent.

The model can be adapted to both liberalized electricity markets and regulated markets to help addressing the challenges inherent to these markets. Although this article focuses on a day-ahead market, other electricity markets, or a mix of markets, can also be considered. The input data are market prices and consumers' consumption profiles (or clusters). The former are essential to compute the matrix with the expected return of each consumer. The later are essential to compute the covariance matrix. Both are essential to compute the gamma matrix, although the computation of this matrix is optional.

The model accounts for a risk-return optimization of the electricity retailers' portfolio taking into account the Markowitz theory. The metric used to characterize the risk is the VaR, but other metrics can be used, such as CVaR and variance. The main variable to characterize retailers is the risk preference or attitude, which can be classified as risk-averse, risk-seeking and risk-neutral. This variable plays a central role in differentiating the results between several retailers.

The Markowitz theory is used to obtain the efficient frontier for the portfolio optimization problem. When retailers change the expected return or VaR, this frontier guarantees that the resulting portfolios of clients are efficient, if they are "inside" the frontier. Taking into account the retailers' risk attitude and their restrictions to the minimum expected return and maximum VaR, there is the possibility to obtain the optimized points for a portfolio of consumers. Although this was not considered in the case studies, after computing the Markowitz frontier, and by making a risk-return analysis, we can obtain the optimized portfolio taking into account the characteristics of the retailers and consumers.

The first case study considered a strategy that takes into account an equal tariff to every consumer, and aimed at determining the optimized portfolio of clients. The second case study considered two other pricing strategies, with some limitations, taking into account the data from the Portuguese electricity sector and retail competition. The third case study aimed at improving the results by making a forecast for the future price of electricity and introducing it in the model.

The results obtained are consistent (there is a difference around two percent between the expected return and the real return of the efficient portfolios for 2012), but dependent of the forecasting method to predict future market prices. The technique (MTS) to forecast long-term market prices was considered. Short-term market prices can be predicted by simulation, using for example a multi-agent system able to simulate the day-ahead market.

In general, the results demonstrate that high risk-averse agents will prefer a majority share of street lightning consumers (reduce the VaR) in their portfolios, while high risk-seeking agents favour a higher share of small commercial and industrial consumers (increase the expected return of the portfolio). Since the difference between the VaR of them is only 1%, the demand can be considered inelastic (the consumers tend to keep patterns over time and have a small response to electricity prices volatility), and the supply of electricity can be considered an essential service, the electricity sector is favorable to high risk-seeking agents. This conclusion can be verified in the real-world, because electricity retailers follow a business as usual model, where they tend to propose tariffs with high returns (when compared to market prices) and accept all types of consumers, increasing the risk of their portfolio. In this article, we are more restricted in the share of consumers in the retailers portfolios. Accordingly, we can propose more competitive tariffs (smaller when comparing with the competition) to target types of consumers. We believe that this method leads to a more stable portfolio in terms of number of consumers, consumers share, relative return and VaR.

For future work we intend to study how optimized portfolios of retailers with different risk attitudes differ between them. We also pretend to test the application of risk sharing measures for consumers with high uncertainty consumption patterns, in order for them be important to an optimized portfolio of risk-averse retailers. To hedge against spot price volatility and maximize the risk-return relation, we want to consider more market options where a retailer can buy and sell electricity, increasing the consistency of the entire model.

Chapter 7

Conclusions

7.1 Achievements

The major achievements of the present work intend to cover some of the limitations of the state of the art. The core achievements are as follows:

- The analysis of the of the main measures of the EC proposal for regulating the EIME, allowing to realize that these measures are important to increase the efficiency of power systems with high levels of VRE, thus increasing the social welfare of the European citizens. Gate closures closer to real-time, shorter products, aggregation and centralized markets using locational pricing without incentives or bilateral agreements, are the key issues of future new market designs and products. However, increasing the flexibility of power systems will speed up the retirement of slow power plants (e.g., coal power plants that have not been retrofitted). Also, giving balance responsibility for RES can negatively influence the return of VRE investors;
- Changing the gate-closure of the day-ahead market to a time horizon closer to real-time operation is beneficial for VRE producers and retailers, by reducing their forecast errors and consequently their deviations, increasing their return from markets. However, coals power plants need around 6-8 hours for planning their operation. So, a significant postpone of the DAM gate-closure could lead to the retirement of these players, while a postpone of a few hours will not affect them;
- VRE producers and the demand-side are the main sources of deviations. The unbalances caused by these deviations have to be mitigated in balancing markets. To incentive the participation of these players in BMs is a key issue. A study where WPPs can participate in BMs allow to verify that they can reduce their deviations and significantly increase their remuneration from markets;
- The use of an optimization model for retailers to define their portfolio of end-use consumers, using the Markowitz theory, allow to conclude that the retail market is beneficial for profit-seeking retailers (players that desire high returns) with a risk-averse attitude. A risk-averse attitude allows retailers to have more stable portfolios, mainly when they fail in their forecasts, and their real return is similar to their expected return. However, risk-seeking retailers may have an advantage in

retail competition by offering more competitive tariffs, but have more risky portfolios and a more uncertain return.

The main research question indicated in section 1.2 is addressed by the results of the new elements of market design and rules introduced in the core work (as well as by the substantial changes that the EU is introducing in the new proposal for regulating the European Internal Market for Electricity). With the substantial increase of VRE in the European EMs, the European Commission presented a draft of a new proposal for regulating the EIME, with measures that focus on VRE integration, namely:

- gate closure of markets close to real-time operation in all time horizons (forwards, day-ahead, intraday and real-time);
- aggregated bids;
- participation of VRE producers and demand-side in BMs;
- a market time unit up to 15 minutes;
- balance responsibility to RES;
- possibility of market operators to develop new market products that promote the participation of demand-side (through demand-response) and VRE producers in BMs.

To respond to the first open question indicated in section 1.2, all these measures have been studied in the work performed in this thesis. All measures are positive for VRE integration in EMs. Furthermore, all measures, with exception to giving balance responsibility to RES, can increase the VRE remuneration from markets.

In general, the literature presents a large number of studies that proved the benefits of gate closures close to real-time operation and aggregated bids (partially responding to the sixth question indicated in section 1.2) in improving the forecasts of VRE. The work performed in this thesis also confirmed an increase in the wind energy value and a reduction of imbalances.

In relation to the participation of WPPs in BMs, the majority of the researchers are currently addressing the technical and control issues associated with such participation, some of them focused on the reduction of the costs of the system and the penetration of VRE in BMs. WPPs still have some issues at the technical and (efficient) operation levels, related with the waste of energy in case of downward regulation, and lack of energy in case of upward regulation. It is possible to consider WPPs participating in BMs with some constraints that guarantee the security of the power system and no waste of energy, such as submitting aggregated bids (specially with CG) and having limitations to their bids. Only a few part of the researchers are performing studies to quantify the increase in the wind energy value that the participation of WPPs in BMs can bring. Against this background, part of the work performed in this thesis focuses on four key dependent variables, namely the value of wind energy to the market, the system imbalances, the costs associated with BMs and the total cost of the system.

One of the market design issues that VRE producers face is the need to perform bids for power, not for energy, for hourly intervals, which, in case of complying with the schedule, contributes for an

inefficient operation of WPPs. If WPPs have to comply with set-points defined by their bids in spot markets, this will contribute to a waste of energy (in case of the schedule being lower than the real-time production) or lack of energy (in case of the schedule being higher than the real-time production). Changing the market time unit of BMs to 15 minutes, instead of 1 hour, is a good procedure, since BMs have to be fully activated in 15 minutes, and imbalance costs are also calculated for periods of 15 minutes. This measure also benefits WPPs, since they have less volatility in shorter time periods, which were verified in our studies by obtaining a reduction of almost three times in WPPs imbalances.

Responding to the third question indicated in section 1.2, changes in the market design, in the market rules and the development of new market products are very important, since spot and balancing markets are essentially designed to CG.

If WPPs could use products based on offers of energy instead of power, they will increase the efficiency of their operation, reducing their imbalances. So, the development of new market products should have in consideration that WPPs can easily meet schedules of bids based on energy, and face problems in meeting schedules of bids based on power, for longer time periods (products).

This work involved the study of three new market products that cover the problems associated with WPPs, but also with retailers, with the goal of increasing the efficiency of the operation of these agents and reduce their imbalances (and those of the global system).

The "Short-run Electronic Trading (SET)" considers a period of fifteen minutes for electronic trading of energy between sellers and buyers. All market agents can use this product with a minimum bid of 0.1 MWh. In particular, it is adequate for VRE and retailers bidding their deviations, reducing their imbalances and costs with deviations.

The "Energy Reserve Product (ERP)" is a product where VRE producers can bid their deviations (up to fifteen minutes before real-time) for a 15-minute period.

The "Renewable power band (RPB)" is a product very similar to the automatic-activated frequency restoration reserve (aFRR), where agents have to offer a power band based on their flexibility to vary capacity over time, but involves the reduction of the time period to five minutes, and the trading period until fifteen minutes before real time operation, which suits VRE producers, increasing their potential to participate in BMs without being aggregated to CG, contributing to a decrease in forecast errors, avoiding the waste of energy, and reducing imbalances.

In wholesale markets, while negotiating bilateral contracts, buyers and sellers of electricity can be supported by multi-agent systems, performing forecasts for the future price of electricity, using negotiation strategies appropriated for their goals, and a risk management process that can mitigate the risk of contracts. Furthermore, agents were equipped with negotiation strategies, utility functions and risk models adapted for their position and goals in EMs. Also, they are equipped with negotiation strategies, utility functions and risk models adapted for their position and goals in EMs.

By signing physical bilateral contracts, like forwards, sellers are more exposed to future risks than buyers, so there is significant risk asymmetry between them that makes sellers increase their requested risk premium, increasing the prices of bilateral contracts in relation to pool markets. The use of the *risk sharing* contract proved to be a good solution for sellers and buyers of electricity to mitigate their risks.

In relation to the return, it depends on the market results, but with a *risk sharing* contract it is possible to reduce the profit/loss difference between the two parties, such as the risk asymmetry.

In retail markets, retailers of electricity are in a similar option (but more risky than the one considered in wholesale markets). They sign customized long-term contracts with consumers, with fixed tariffs, but variable consumption, that is only limited by the contracted capacity of each consumer. In this case, the risk asymmetry between retailers and consumers is large, since retailers assume almost all risks. Thus, retailers request high risk premiums when sign bilateral contracts with consumers, proposing tariffs significantly higher than market prices.

Retailers have the same problem of VRE producers, since they have to submit bids based on forecasts, which result in imbalances between their schedules (bids accepted) and their real production. So, they have to pay substantial penalties for their imbalances.

Using a risk management process with the goal of optimizing the portfolio of consumers, and taking into account each retailer characteristics, mainly their risk attitude and expected return, it is possible to minimize the risk of portfolios and propose more competitive tariffs to key-consumers (addressing the fourth question indicated in section 1.2). By offering more competitive tariffs retailers can have more stable portfolios, reducing the risk of them.

A study for the Portuguese power system, using real data from 2011, allowed to verify that by offering a reduction in regulated tariffs up to 24%, retailers can have more stable portfolios, obtaining an expected return up to 14% with a VaR lower than 10%, so they have a guaranteed return of more than 4% (addressing the fifth question indicated in section 1.2). This study also verified that profit-seeking retailers have advantage in retail markets, because substantial variations in the return of their consumers portfolios lead to small variations in portfolios risk (VaR). However, in case different retailers expect similar returns, risk-averse retailers will probably obtain higher returns than risk-seeking retailers, because they have more stable portfolios. Otherwise, risk-averse retailers have advantage in wholesale markets, since small variations in the return of their markets options (where they buy the electricity to satisfy their consumers), lead to substantial variations in risk.

One of the main risks that retailers have to face is the consumption variability of their portfolios. They usually pay significant penalties due to the imbalances between the power that they acquire and the power that consumers use. One way to mitigate those risks is to sign demand response programs with consumers.

A study using real data from the Iberian market prices and from a real Portuguese library (with a 4-rate tariff), allowed to conclude that by signing a DLC contract (with a discount of 5% in the mid-peak period) with a retailer, is possible to reduce the library costs with electricity in 6%. By using DSM measures, as peak clipping and load shifting it is possible to reduce the library costs with electricity in 4%. Forming coalitions is one way of strengthening the consumers negotiation position, increasing their flexibility and obtaining more competitive tariffs. A study using data from real consumers in the United Kingdom allows to verify that by forming a coalition the smaller consumers can have a "virtual" benefit up to 50%, while the average benefit of the entire coalition is 6%. So, small consumers should be more interested in forming coalitions that big consumers, since their benefit is substantially higher (completing

the response to the sixth question indicated in section 1.2).

Other solution may involve the flexibility of consumers to reduce the DAM prices, using a DR program as the critical peak pricing. Retailers can establish contracts where consumers have to reduce a pre-defined amount of energy when the market prices are higher than the establish threshold. This solution can also be used for aggregations or coalitions of consumers. In a study performed in the Iberian market during the period between 2014 and June 2017, it was found an average price reduction up to 37.88 €/MWh (24%), for a threshold of 80 €/MWh and a 5% reduction in the demand, in a total of 239 events. However, from the point of view of retailers, this solution is not so beneficial, since by reducing market prices of DAM (through giving incentives to consumers participate in CPP programs), they are benefiting all demand-side players (including the competition).

DSM measures and DR programs are good options for consumers that have flexibility and the goal of reducing costs. DSM measures, as TOU tariffs, are good solutions for retailers that want to reduce peak consumptions in their portfolios, and DR programs can be used to reduce retailers imbalances and consequently, their penalties.

7.2 Future work

As future work we have the goal of testing how WPPs can act as active players in the electricity markets. Preliminary results show that taking into account the current market structure, the use of strategically bidding by WPPs leads to a remuneration far from the perfect forecast (less 12%) and half of the feed-in tariffs remuneration. So, some changes should be addressed to the current market structure, to make it appealing to investment in more VRE capacity without feed-in tariffs.

As stated before, retailers and VRE producers (wind, PV, etc.) have similar problems in relation to the deviations and the respective penalties. The new market products can partially resolve these issues. They do not resolve this problem totally, because VRE producers depend on the TSO to accept or not, their bids. Only very specific power plants can participate in the Portuguese balancing market products, which is a limitation (VRE producers can not).

The work performed in this thesis considered single bids of WPPs in BMs, a situation similar to the German case, with non strategic provision of regulating power. It also considered a gate closure of 15 minutes ahead and bids performed for products of either one hour or 15 minutes. Accordingly, some important aspects for future work are as follows:

1. Strategic bidding in DAMs, intra-day markets and BMs;
2. The possibility of aggregated bids in BMs;
3. A gate-closure of BMs between one hour and five minutes ahead of real-time operation;
4. BM products between five and fifteen minutes;
5. New BM products adapted to wind power.

Future work as the goal of testing the use of DR programs by retailers to minimize the consumption risk that they have in their portfolios. Theoretically, this can result in a win-win situation to retailers, because they can decrease the portfolios risk and at the same time try to increase their return (depending on the discounts offered to consumers that adhere to the DR programs and on the market prices). However, preliminary results show that by using DR programs retailers can increase their expected return, as expected, but they also increase their VaR (in the planning phase), which is not expected. This occurs because by using the DR programs to reduce some of the consumption just in a few selected hours of the day, retailers increase the variance of their return. Although, this increase in the variance is under control of retailers, the optimization problem does not have the ability to detect it, increasing the VaR of the portfolios.

Retailers have the same problem of WPPs, they can forecast their consumers consumption and make bids in the day-ahead and intraday markets such as sign bilateral contracts, to satisfy their consumers, but they normally have significant deviations in real-time operation, paying penalties for them. Thus, the use of DR programs can be very important to control the consumption deviations, by limiting or cutting some of the consumers power.

A solution to control the risks associated with spot prices volatility can be use *risk sharing* contracts, since these types of contracts can pass part of retailers risks to consumers. Preliminary results indicate that by using these types of contracts, retailers can propose more competitive tariffs to consumers, reduce the risk of their portfolios and increase their return. Consumers can also obtain better tariffs, but now they are subject to variations in their tariffs, depending on the market results. The authors also intend to study possible benefits/drawbacks of specific coalitions of end-use consumers from the retailer point of view.

As a more ambitious goal it is intended to develop strategies that help to address the challenges that a retailer has when buying electricity. The objective passes to obtain the optimal share of market options where retailers can buy electricity, in order to increase their risk-return ratio. Therefore, is intended to work on the strategically bidding that retailers can do in the spot markets, as future work. Considering a retailer with a fixed portfolio, as future work is intended to:

1. determine the quantities of power to buy in the spot market (day-ahead and intraday) and by signing forward contracts;
2. use the current risk mitigate options: CfDs, futures and option contracts;
3. perform more profound tests to the use of DR programs and analyse possible benefits/limitations they have;
4. do a deep analysis to the use of *risk sharing* contracts and verify the advantages/disadvantages they have;
5. do a experiment to analyse possible benefits/drawbacks of coalitions of end-use consumers;
6. use strategies to bid at spot markets, taking into account all the other options under contract (CfDs, futures, options, forwards, DR programs, *risk sharing* contracts, etc.).

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